

RADBOUD UNIVERSITY

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Wind Energy Ramp Events

ON THE METEOROLOGICAL EVENTS CAUSING SUDDEN CHANGES IN WIND ENERGY GENERATION

THESIS BSC PHYSICS & ASTRONOMY

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Abstract

This study investigates which meteorological events are responsible for sudden changes in wind energy generation, called *ramp events*, at the Belgian offshore wind farm cluster. Ramp events can lead to significant losses and instability in the grid, making them relevant to all stakeholders related to wind energy. Using power generation data from the entire cluster, individual farms and meteorological data from weather stations surround the cluster, 221 unique ramp events are identified between January 2021 and March 2025 across 154 days. Ramp events are categorised into three types based on a threshold definition: slow large ramps (1000 MW or more in 60 minutes or less), fast small ramps (500 MW or more in 15 minutes or less) and fast large ramps (ramps that satisfy both criteria). These ramp events and the time series are analysed for seasonal and diurnal patterns. A dashboard is developed containing synoptic weather charts, generation data and weather data to get insight into the meteorological situation during ramp events. Every ramp event is manually associated with a certain meteorological cause. Across all seasons, the majority of ramp events are associated with frontal passages. What kind of ramp occurs, seems to depend heavily on how isobars get deformed by the frontal passage. Ramp events directly associated with frontal passages are more prominent in cold seasons than in warm seasons. The second most common (likely) cause is pre- or post-frontal convection (troughs aloft, convergence lines, squall lines) and are a more prominent (likely) cause in warm seasons than in cold seasons. Frontal and low pressure core passages are associated with 5 and 4 cut-out events respectively. Low pressure core passages are associated mostly with long duration ramp events. Generally, fast (especially small) ramp events are more often associated with mesoscale effects than slow, large ramp events. It is important to note that while temporal associations between synoptic features and ramp events are observed, the analysis does not establish direct causality. Relatively few purely mesoscale ramp causing events (non-frontal convection or invisible on synoptic charts) are classified. This might suggest that the Belgian offshore zone is sufficiently large to be somewhat insensitive to these mesoscale features. To explore this idea, a method using hypothetical clusters as subsets of the real wind farm cluster is used to illustrate how the sensitivity to different ramp types change as a cluster grows in size. It seems that fast ramp events are less common for larger clusters. Asymptotic behaviour is observed, this might indicate that sensitivity will not decrease much further as the cluster keeps growing past its current size. The occurrence of slow large ramps does not change with increasing cluster size. This suggests that the total effect of slow large ramps on the electricity grid increases as the cluster grows in size. Assessing the relation between cluster size and sensitivity to certain meteorological features requires further research.

Keywords Wind energy - Wind farms - Energy ramp events - Meteorology - North Sea - offshore wind power

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Detailed summary

The aim of this study is to investigate which meteorological events are responsible for sudden drops or increases in wind energy generation, called *ramp events*, at the Belgian offshore wind farm cluster. Such events are relevant to all stakeholders related to wind energy. Ramp events can cause difficulties in load balancing for transmission system operators, leading to significant losses and instability in the grid. This issue is expected to become more severe as the share of wind energy in the total energy mix increases.

Four years of meteorological and power generation data from the southern North Sea (Southern Bright) is analysed to study the occurred energy ramp events. The diurnal and seasonal variation in wind energy production and multiple meteorological variables of stations around the offshore clusters are assessed. Furthermore, the relations between meteorological variables, production and how they change during ramp events is investigated. In addition, a novel approach is proposed for attempting to find low level jet activity in the power generation time series. This method does not seem to suggest that any noticeable low level jet activity is present at the Belgian offshore wind farm cluster, although this could mean this approach is flawed.

To associate every ramp event with a possible meteorological cause, a dashboard is developed that contains synoptic weather charts, power generation time series for the entire cluster and individual farms, and meteorological measurements from different weather stations surrounding the wind farm cluster. In the observing time range (2021-01-01 to 2025-03-09), 221 unique ramp events (overlap between types removed) occurred across 154 days. In this work, we distinguish three types of ramp events; 1000 MW or more in 60 minutes or less (slow, large, 67), 500 MW or more in 15 minutes or less (fast, small, 70) and ramp events that meet both criteria (fast, large, 84). Every ramp event is manually associated with a certain meteorological cause. This new data set is analysed for diurnal and seasonal patterns. Across all seasons, the majority of ramp events are associated with frontal passages (86). What kind of ramp occurs (up (43) or down (43)) seems to depend heavily on how isobars get deformed by the frontal passage. Ramp events associated directly with frontal passages are more prominent in cold seasons than in warm seasons (50 and 36 respectively). The second most common (likely) cause is pre- or post-frontal convection (51, troughs aloft, convergence lines, squall lines). This is a more prominent (likely) cause in warm seasons (32) than in cold seasons (19). Frontal and low pressure core passages are associated with 5 and 4 cut-out events respectively. Low pressure core passages are associated with 22 ramp events, from which 21 are long duration ramp events. Generally, fast (especially small) ramp events are more often associated with mesoscale effects (28) than slow, large ramp events (7). Relatively few purely mesoscale ramp causing events (non-frontal convection (29, very few in winter) or invisible on synoptic charts (21, mostly fast, short ramp events)) are classified. This might suggest that the Belgian offshore cluster is sufficiently large to be somewhat insensitive to these mesoscale features. It is important to note that while temporal associations between synoptic features and ramp events are observed, the analysis does not establish direct causality.

To explore how the sensitivity to certain ramp types depends on cluster size, a method using hypothetical clusters as subsets of the real wind farm clusters is used. For every possible subset of farms, the occurrence, average ramp size and ramp duration are computed. From this, it seems that fast ramp events are less common for larger clusters. Asymptotic behaviour is observed, this might indicate that sensitivity for fast small ramp types will not decrease much further as the cluster keeps growing past its current size. Absolute occurrence of slow large ramps does not change significantly with cluster size, but absolute ramp sizes increase with cluster size. A severity index is introduced, defined as the product between ramp occurrence and ramp size, this is a measure for the total effect of a ramp type on the electricity grid. The severity for slow large ramps increases with cluster size and decreases for fast small ramps. In conclusion, larger clusters ramp less frequently, but when they do, the events are more severe. Assessing the relation between cluster size and sensitivity to certain meteorological features requires further research.

Chapter 1

Introduction

The energy transition to renewable energy sources has accelerated in the last decade [1]. From 2013 to 2023 the share of energy from renewable sources in gross electricity consumption has increased from 26.8% to 45.3% for the European Union (12.5% to 31% for Belgium. 10.4% to 46.4% in The Netherlands, see Figure 1.1) [2]. The transition to clean sources can help to mitigate global warming [3] and leads to less pollution compared to fossil fuel based energy production. However, renewable sources such as solar and wind are inherently intermittent [4]. Electricity grids require generation and load to be balanced to maintain a stable frequency [5]. When the energy supply is greater than the demand, the grid frequency can increase. Conversely, when the demand is greater than the energy supply, the grid frequency can decrease. A grid frequency that deviates too much from the reference frequency (50 Hz in Europe) can damage equipment or cause power outages. Transmission system operators (TSO) are responsible for balancing the grid. TSOs can maintain balance by changing the energy production (starting reserve power plants or using constraint payments for producers), reducing energy use (peak shifting or load shedding) or importing or exporting electricity. As the fraction of renewable intermittent sources in the total (electrical) energy mix increases, the effects of their variability will become more pronounced. In addition, renewable energy sources have lower, if any, (mechanical) inertia than traditional power plants [6]. For this reason, research on the causes of the swings in energy production is important. Cumulatively, wind energy in Europe has increased from 161 GW in 2016 to 285 GW in 2024 [7], [8]. For the Netherlands this increase is shown in Figure 1.1. The development of offshore wind farms has been on the rise lately. These are popular for coastal countries with high population densities such as Belgium, Denmark and the Netherlands. The Netherlands has increased its offshore capacity from 1 GW in 2019 to 4.5 GW in 2023, and has plans to increase this to 21 GW in 2032. The North Sea has great potential for offshore wind power production. In 2023, 77% of power generated from offshore farms in Europe was from the North Sea. Due to the increasing dependence on these farms, research on this topic is becoming more important. Especially considering that electricity consumption will only increase due to the electrification of industrial facilities, the growing number of electric vehicles and the demand for more data centres. The main objective of this work is to assess the relation between rapid generation fluctuations at the Belgian offshore wind farm cluster and their meteorological causes.

Relative electricity production in percent of the domestic electricity usage in The Netherlands

Figure 1.1: Evolution of fraction of renewable electricity production in the Netherlands, Data source: Statistics Netherlands (CBS), URL: <https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline>.

This chapter sheds light on the current state of wind power generation and discusses some concepts in meteorology. Section 1.1 contains information about wind turbines, the conversion of wind energy to electrical energy and introduces the notion of a ramp event. Section 1.2 is a discussion of the different definitions used for detecting and classifying ramp events in the scientific literature. Section 1.3 outlines the different meteorological events that can cause ramp events and contains a review of the current scientific literature on the connections between the weather and ramp events. It also gives a brief introduction to meteorology for readers outside this field of study. Section 1.4 formulates the research questions and the problem this study aims to address.

1.1 Wind turbines

For wind energy, variable wind speed is the main cause of the variability in power generation. In Figure 1.2a the power curve of a typical wind turbine is shown. Below the cut-in speed $v_{\text{cut-in}}$ (typically $\sim 3 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$), the wind turbine does not generate any power. For wind speeds above the cut-in speed and below the rated wind speed v_{rated} (typically $\sim 11 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$), the generation is non-linear. This is due to the cubic dependency $P = C \cdot v^3$ [9], [10], [11]. This can be seen with a somewhat heuristic derivation. Assume an incompressible fluid ($\dot{\rho} = 0$) passing through a cylinder with speed v with cross section A . The flow encounters a wind turbine, which decreases the wind speed from v_1 to v_2 . From mass conservation we know the flow rate $\dot{V} = Av$ has to be conserved (incompressible continuity equation, $m = \rho V \Rightarrow \dot{m} = \rho \dot{V} = \text{const}$). Energy conservation and the continuity equation are stated as

$$\frac{1}{2}m_1v_1^2 = \frac{1}{2}m_2v_2^2 + E \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{V} = A_1v_1 = A_2v_2, \quad (1.1)$$

with the extracted energy E . The index 1 refers to the flow before passing through the wind turbine and the index 2 after passing through. Differentiating the energy conservation equation with respect to time, and then substituting for the masses m_i gives Equation 1.2. The system is in a steady state, so the time derivatives \dot{v}_i vanish:

$$m_1v_1\dot{v}_1 + \frac{1}{2}\dot{m}_1v_1^2 = m_2v_2\dot{v}_2 + \frac{1}{2}\dot{m}_2v_2^2 + \dot{E} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{1}{2}\rho A_1v_1^3 = \frac{1}{2}\rho A_2v_2^3 + P \quad (1.2)$$

Isolating the extracted power P and some factorising gives Equation 1.3. Substitution of v_2 into Equation 1.2 gives

$$P = \frac{1}{2}\rho A_1v_1(v_1^2 - v_2^2). \quad (1.3)$$

By rewriting the speed behind the turbine v_2 as a fraction of the starting speed v_1 , $v_2 = av_1$ with $0 < a < 1$, we get

$$P = \frac{1}{2}\rho A_1(1 - a^2)v_1^3 \quad \Rightarrow \quad P = C \cdot v_1^3 \quad \text{for} \quad v_{\text{cut-in}} < v_1 < v_{\text{rated}}, \quad (1.4)$$

with C an arbitrary constant. Above the rated speed, the generation plateaus. This is the region where the wings of the turbine themselves tilt (pitch control) to decrease drag such that the rotor does not rotate faster as the wind speed increases [12]. When the control systems of a turbine cannot decrease drag any longer as the wind speed further increases, a cut-out speed $v_{\text{cut-out}}$ (typically $\sim 25 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) is reached at which the turbine stops generating power.

Figure 1.2: (a) An abstract power curve with some typical values separating the regions. In reality, the non-linear part will taper off more gradually, similar to what can be seen in Figure 1.2b. (b) Resampled 10 minutely data to 15 minutes plotted against the load factor of the entire Belgian offshore wind farm cluster. Wind speed data is not measured at the turbine. For illustrative purposes only. The measured wind speeds will be different (higher) at turbine height.

Wind speed changes between v_{rated} and $v_{\text{cut-out}}$, and below $v_{\text{cut-in}}$ do not affect the power output of a wind turbine. But all other shifts in wind speed can result in large changes in generation. This is mostly

due to the high sensitivity in the cubic and cut-out part of the power curve. When looking at a whole wind farm, or cluster of farms, instead of a single turbine, the dependence of the power output on the wind speed becomes more spread out due to differences in wind speeds at different parts of the wind farms and the usage of different turbines within the wind farm cluster, which can be seen in Figure 1.2b. When multiple turbines experience a large change in wind speed in the sensitive parts of their power curves, the total output of the wind farm can change rapidly. This is known as *power ramp events*. Ramp events pose challenges for TSOs that schedule reserve holding in advance for system balancing [13]. This study focuses on the causes of these ramp events in the Belgian North Sea along the Belgian-Dutch border at 20-60 km from the coastline, see Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: Belgian Offshore Zone and the adjacent Dutch offshore cluster. Base layer: Google Maps.

As kinetic energy is extracted by wind turbines, the velocity of the wind reduces after passing through a turbine, this results in a lower wind speed for the turbine *downwind* (behind). This is called the *wake effect*. Wakes can cause significant *wake losses* in downwind turbines, downwind farms or even clusters [14]. A recent study on inter-farm wake losses has modelled the expected wake losses in the current Belgian offshore zone caused by the planned Princess Elisabeth zone [15]. Wake effects have been observed at 50 km away from a wind farm. The *wake recovery rate* is a measure of how fast the wake effect reduces. Wind farms do not only affect wind speed downwind. As wind farms are becoming more common, their influence on local to regional weather can no longer be neglected [11].

1.2 Ramp definitions

A *ramp event* or *ramp* refers to a significant and rapid change in power output within a short time period. The ramp definition is used to extract ramp events from generation time series. In the literature on the topic, different ramp definitions are used. The definitions can be categorised in three different types: Threshold-based definitions [16], [17], [18], Continuous wavelet transformations (CWT) [19], [20], [21] and Swinging Door Algorithm (SDA) [22], [23]. For a complete outline of the different ramp definitions, refer to [4]. The most common definition is the threshold definition because of the interpretability for TSOs.

In this study the threshold ramp definition is used. Generation data is used from Elia, the Belgian TSO. Elia manages the ~ 2250 MW offshore wind farm cluster. For this reason, ramp durations of 15 and 60 minutes and ramp magnitudes of 500 MW, 1000 MW and 1500 MW are used. A ramp can be up (increase in power) or down (decrease in power), and can happen due to human causes or meteorological causes. Human causes are changes in power output due to maintenance, purposefully producing below available capacity or due to interactions with other wind turbines or farms (wake effect). Meteorological events that can cause ramp events are called *ramp drivers*. Ramp drivers can have different spatial and temporal scales. A study on ramp events at the Thames Estuary cluster [16] found that large ramp events ($> 40\%$ of rated capacity in 4 h) were all associated with large (*synoptic*) scale events (discussed more thoroughly in Section 1.3), whilst shorter, 30-60 minute, ramp events were all associated with smaller *mesoscale* events or cut-outs. Other studies have found similar results [24], [25]. The literature suggests that large ramp drivers cause large ramp events, both in spatial scale and temporal scale. These can affect the whole cluster. Large scale effects are expected to be modelled and predicted well with numerical weather models, since they can often be modelled hydrostatically (scale analysis), with insignificant vertical movements. Smaller scale events seem to cause shorter ramp events and possibly only affect part of the cluster. These mesoscale effects are hard to model and predict, since vertical movement is non-negligible, hydrodynamic models have to be used. These local weather systems are likely highly sensitive to small perturbations and have short lifecycles, such as thunderstorms.

As stated in [4], a review study on the state of the field of research from 2007 to 2015, relating ramp events to their underlying meteorological causes is a very case-dependent problem. The meteorological conditions at a wind farm depend on the location. Specific terrain characteristics such as roughness, topography, land-sea interactions all affect the weather. Even the configuration of how turbines are structured might have an effect on ramp events caused by meteorological processes that involve wind direction shifts (wake effects). The size and spacing of farms within a cluster also seem to matter for what kind of ramp events are happening [26]. If farms have less spatial diversity, more ramp events are expected to happen, since a single small weather system can affect the whole cluster.

Some studies have used machine learning methods for associating ramp events to weather patterns. A series of studies using generation data from the Belgian offshore cluster [27], [28] has used *self organising maps* (SOMs, a non-linear generalisation of principal component analysis (PCA)) to cluster reanalysis (ERA5) mean sea level pressure data from 2002-2017 into 30 weather patterns. Then, for each ramp event, the associated transition in weather type is analysed. The study used generation data from 2015-2016 when the cluster had a capacity of 712 MW. The study found that the transition between weather patterns determined what kind of ramp would be caused (up or down). It states that ramp-up events tend to occur due to the transition from a high-pressure to a low pressure system, or the deepening of a low pressure system (see Section 1.3 for the meteorological background). Ramp-down events were associated with the transition from low pressure system to high pressure (blocking high) systems. This study used a CWT-based ramp definition and investigated generally longer duration ramp events than this work is concerned about. A different study [29] has done a similar task using PCA for Portugal.

The eventual goal of the research on power ramp events is to provide accurate forecast to TSOs for load balancing. The review study mentioned earlier [4] gives an outline up to 2015 of the status of this field. A study on machine learning regression techniques [30] compared how different regression techniques performed when using power ramp events as a *target* and reanalysis data (ERA-interim) as the input. Gaussian regression seemed to score the best. A different study on onshore wind farms in southern California used data mining techniques to extract important meteorological variables as indicators for ramp-occurring days. Another study, [31] discusses a similar approach for onshore wind farms in Spain. Finally, a study in the series on ramp events that uses the Belgian fleet [32], [33], has studied the possible occurrences of power ramp events under a changing climate. The study found that an increase in persistent high pressure areas is projected in the future, but this is beyond the scope of this study.

1.3 Meteorology

This section covers the basics of meteorology for understanding the contents of this work. A large portion of the theory presented in this section is adapted from [34], [35], [36], [37]. As discussed in section 1.2, meteorological features that can cause ramp events come in different temporal and spatial scales. These scales can be defined as followed (although the values are not universally agreed upon):

- Global scale - Circulations last for weeks to months - 5000 to 40 000 km.
- Synoptic scale - Circulations last from days to weeks - 100 to 5000 km.
- Mesoscale - Circulations last from minutes to hours - 1 to 100 km.
- Microscale - Circulations last under a few minutes - less than 1 km in size.

Synoptic scale events can be predicted quite accurately with numerical weather prediction models (NWP). Mesoscale effects are hard to predict due to mesoscale smoothing [22], [25], but still cause significant ramp events. Microscale events are too small to cause significant ramping, since it can only affect a few turbines at once.

Figure 1.4: Spatial and temporal scales for meteorological features in the mid latitudes. The styling is adapted from [34].

As the Sun heats up the Earth differently at different places, temperature differences are created. These temperature differences cause differences in air density. Air with lower density rises, this generates a non-uniform pressure field. This causes non-zero net forces on air parcels. This is called the Pressure Gradient Force (PGF). This force tries to push the parcel towards the lower pressure, i.e. towards a minimum in a pressure field. In mathematical form, this is stated as

$$\mathbf{a}_{pg} = -\frac{1}{\rho}\nabla P, \tag{1.5}$$

with pressure P , density ρ and ∇P points to the steepest pressure increase. Isobars are contours of constant pressure. The closer the isobars are to each other, the steeper the pressure gradient, the larger the pressure

gradient component \mathbf{a}_{pg} of the acceleration is. This indicates stronger wind. The Earth's rotation causes another force, the Coriolis force, to act on the air parcel. The Coriolis force is proportional to speed, and always acts to the right of the direction of motion in the Northern Hemisphere. In mathematical form this is stated as

$$\mathbf{a}_{\text{cor}} = -2(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{v}), \quad (1.6)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is the rotation vector of the Earth pointing along its rotation axis, and \mathbf{v} the velocity vector of the air parcel *relative* to Earth (that is, in a different reference frame than $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is) [38]. To get a usable equation, we define two frames. a global frame $(\hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z})$ such that $\boldsymbol{\Omega} = \Omega \hat{z}$, and a local frame $(\hat{i}, \hat{j}, \hat{k})$. Then $\boldsymbol{\Omega} = \Omega(\cos(\lambda)\hat{j} + \sin(\lambda)\hat{k})$ in the local frame with latitude λ . After carrying out the cross product in Equation 1.6, defining that $\mathbf{v} = u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} + w\hat{k}$ (u, v, w point to the local east, north and zenith respectively), gives

$$\mathbf{a}_{\text{cor}} = -2\Omega((w \cos(\lambda) - v \sin(\lambda))\hat{i} + u \sin(\lambda)\hat{j} - u \cos(\lambda)\hat{k}). \quad (1.7)$$

If we neglect vertical motions ($w = 0$) and consider that in the \hat{k} direction the Coriolis acceleration is very small compared to the gravitational acceleration, we can drop this term. To illustrate this, the Belgian offshore cluster is located at $\lambda = 52^\circ$ in the North Sea. The rotation of the Earth is $\Omega = 7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ radians per second. Then the vertical component of the Coriolis acceleration is $\mathbf{a}_{\text{cor}} \cdot \hat{k} \approx 0.00001u$. This means that even if the \hat{i} component of \mathbf{v} is $100 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (an unreasonably high speed), this component still only is $0.001 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$. This is negligible compared to the gravitational acceleration $g \approx 9.81 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$. The fact that the components of the Coriolis acceleration are small, shows that the effect is only important for large scale effects. After dropping these terms we get

$$\mathbf{a}_{\text{cor}} = 2\Omega(v \sin(\lambda)\hat{i} - u \sin(\lambda)\hat{j}) = 2\Omega \sin(\lambda) \begin{pmatrix} v \\ -u \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \text{where the vector } \begin{pmatrix} v \\ -u \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ is the} \quad (1.8)$$

horizontal part of \mathbf{v} rotated to the left (for $\lambda > 0$), perpendicular to \mathbf{v} . This can be written as

$$\mathbf{a}_{\text{cor}} = -f\hat{k} \times \mathbf{v} \quad \text{with the vector } \mathbf{v} = u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} \text{ and } f = 2\Omega \sin(\lambda), \quad (1.9)$$

called the *Coriolis parameter* or *Coriolis frequency*. If no friction is present, such as at high altitude, these forces will be the only forces acting in the horizontal plane. When these forces are balanced, the velocity \mathbf{v} will be perpendicular to both \mathbf{a}_{pg} and \mathbf{a}_{cor} . This is called *geostrophic flow*. When a flow is geostrophic, the wind travels along pressure isobars with speed

$$v_{\text{geo}} = \frac{1}{\rho f} |\nabla P|, \quad \mathbf{v}_{\text{geo}} = \frac{1}{\rho f} \hat{k} \times \nabla P. \quad (1.10)$$

In the Northern Hemisphere, wind travels counter-clockwise around pressure minima and clockwise around pressure maxima. This is called *Cyclonic flow* and *Anti-Cyclonic flow* respectively. This notion is called the *Buys Ballot Law*; In the Northern Hemisphere, if you stand with your back to the wind, low pressure will be to your left. This can be used to infer wind directions by just looking at pressure isobars on a weather chart. When talking about wind direction, meteorologists mean the direction from which the wind is blowing from. Since the direction of the wind is changing, there has to be a net acceleration. This deviation from geostrophic wind is referred to as *gradient wind*. In cyclonic flow, $|\mathbf{a}_{\text{pg}}| > |\mathbf{a}_{\text{cor}}|$, which will cause the flow to be *subgeostrophic* (slower than geostrophic), and vice-versa for anti-cyclonic flow, the flow will be faster than geostrophic flow (*supergeostrophic*). This speed can be calculated by solving

$$\mathbf{a}_{\text{grad}} = \frac{\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v}}{R} \hat{n} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla P - f\hat{k} \times \mathbf{v} \quad (1.11)$$

for $|\mathbf{v}|$ with \hat{n} the unit vector in the direction of curvature and R the radius of the osculating circle. In a gradient wind, all acceleration vectors act on the same axis, this allows us to reduce the problem to one dimension. By introducing the *Rossby number* R_o , one can quickly see if the Coriolis effect is significant or negligible. By considering the scalar version of Equation 1.11 and dividing by the Coriolis term we get

$$R_o = \frac{|\mathbf{v}|}{fR} = \frac{1}{f|\mathbf{v}|\rho} |\nabla P| + 1. \quad (1.12)$$

If $R_o \ll 1$, the centripetal acceleration (net acceleration) will be negligible and geostrophic flow may be assumed. If $R_o \sim 1$, gradient flow may be assumed. If $R_o \gg 1$, *cyclostrophic* flow may be assumed. In a cyclostrophic flow, the Coriolis effect does not play a role. An example of cyclostrophic flow is emptying a bathtub in the Northern or Southern Hemisphere, that is, the Coriolis force does not cause a toilet to flush in different directions in the Northern and Southern hemispheres. Meteorological examples of cyclostrophic winds are whirl winds (tornadoes, dust devils and waterspouts) [39].

1.3.1 Synoptic scale meteorology

At the surface, friction cannot be neglected. This means there is an extra force acting on an air parcel, acting against the velocity vector \mathbf{v} . The frictional force tries to oppose motion. This results in a decrease of the magnitude of the velocity. As a result, the Coriolis acceleration in Equation 1.9 will decrease. This causes a net acceleration opposite to the Coriolis acceleration. This is stated in mathematical form as

$$\mathbf{a} = -\frac{1}{\rho}\nabla P - f\hat{k} \times \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{f}_{\text{fric}} = -\frac{1}{\rho}\nabla P - f\hat{k} \times \mathbf{v} - f_{\text{fric}}\hat{\mathbf{v}} \quad \text{with } f_{\text{fric}} \text{ the drag, often a function of } |\mathbf{v}|. \quad (1.13)$$

This is a differential equation that can be numerically solved to get the velocity field, given a pressure field $P(x, y)$ depending on location and a friction field as a function of location and wind speed $f_{\text{fric}}(|\mathbf{v}|, x, y)$. In cyclonic flow, this means that at the surface the flow will converge counter-clockwise to the low pressure area (**L**) and will diverge clockwise away from a high pressure area (**H**) in anti-cyclonic flow. This is why **L** areas are associated with upward motion (clouds, humid weather) and **H** are associated with downward motion (clear skies, dry weather).

Often, the low and high pressure areas are not surrounded by closed isobars. These are called *troughs* and *ridges*. The flow around a trough is cyclonic (counter-clockwise, elongated **L**) and the flow around a ridge is anticyclonic (clockwise, elongated **H**).

Up until this point we completely neglected gravity. As alluded to before, the vertical components of the Coriolis acceleration are negligible compared to the gravitational acceleration. In synoptic scale dynamics, there is an almost exact balance between the vertical pressure gradient force and gravity. This can be seen by simplifying the full equation of motion, without only focussing on the horizontal part. The full equation of motion is

$$\mathbf{a}_{\text{actual}} = -\frac{1}{\rho}\nabla P + f \cdot \begin{pmatrix} v - w \cot(\lambda) \\ -u \\ u \cot(\lambda) \end{pmatrix} - f_{\text{fric}}(|\mathbf{v}|) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} + \mathbf{g} \quad (1.14)$$

for which the vertical component, after dropping the Coriolis effect (same reason as before) and frictional terms (friction decreases fast with altitude), is

$$a_z = \dot{w} = -\frac{1}{\rho}\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} - g. \quad (1.15)$$

If the vertical motion is ignored altogether ($a_z = 0$, $w = 0$), we obtain the *hydrostatic equation*:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} = -\rho g \quad (1.16)$$

The condition for using the *hydrostatic approximation* depends on the ratio between the vertical H and horizontal L extent of the circulation in question. This is called *scale analysis*. For synoptic scale circulations, this approximation is valid. For mesoscale events, the modelling becomes much harder.

Extratropical cyclones - Low pressure areas

Low pressure areas are *extratropical cyclones* (also called mid-latitude cyclones). In the Northern Hemisphere, this results in counter-clockwise flow converging to the low pressure core. They are powered by

the temperature contrast between the lower latitudes and the poles, transporting warm air masses to the poles and cold air masses to the equator. The barrier between these air masses are called (weather) *fronts*. A *cold front* transports dry cold air from the poles to the equator. A *warm front* transports warm moist air to the poles. Larger global circulations (polar front, jet stream and westerlies) are responsible for the formation and movement of extra-tropical cyclones (the Norwegian model), but this is outside the scope of this work. The result is that in the mid-latitudes ($30^\circ - 60^\circ$), these systems travel from west to east. In the colder seasons, their strength and propagation dominate (due to the polar front shifting southward and having an increased temperature contrast across the front). Especially in winter, the strong pressure gradients around extratropical cyclones can cause very high wind speeds. Often high enough for cut-out events to occur (Section 1.1). In a study at the Thames Estuary cluster all five of the cut-out events were in winter due to a strong pressure gradient around a **L** [16]. When meteorologist talk about seasons, they mean meteorological seasons; winter is December, January and February, spring is March, April and May, etc. The passage of a **L** can be recognized by the change in direction of the wind of almost 180° . An incoming deep **L** can cause a ramp-up event and outgoing deep **L** can cause a ramp-down event if the feature travels sufficiently fast.

High pressure areas

High pressure areas are *anti-cyclones* denoted with **H** on weather charts. They are associated with surface divergence (clockwise in the Northern Hemisphere), and bring dry weather with clear skies. Dry, cool air aloft (at high altitude) is transported downwards (*subsidence*) and heated adiabatically. The absence of moisture means the atmosphere often is stable during these weather patterns. In summer this results in clear, warm and dry weather during the day, but rapid cooling at night. In winter this results in very cold dry weather. Sometimes a large **H** becomes stationary and blocks other weather systems and flows from propagating eastward. This is called a *blocking high*. When this happens, the same weather pattern can last for weeks, often leading to droughts.

Cold front

A cold front is a boundary between a propagating cold (often dry) airmass into, or wedges under, a warm air mass. Cold fronts are indicated on weather maps by blue triangles that point into the direction of propagation. In Figure 1.5a, a schematic side view of a cold front is shown. Since cold air is heavier than warm air, it pushes warm air upwards, causing warm, often moist, air to lift up (strong *updraft*). This is called *frontal lifting*. This can cause clouds to form, possibly leading to precipitation and thunderstorm development (especially in summer). Precipitation can occur either ahead or behind a cold front and are often showers. A cold front propagates with a speed of 30 to $60 \text{ km} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, or 10 to 20 minutes to propagate 10 km . They can be recognised by a temperature drop, a wind direction change (often clockwise), sometimes a dip in pressure and stormy weather. The vertical structure of a cold front is quite steep, around 10 meters rise for every 1 km propagation. Since the wind direction differs across the boundary, we have strong vertical wind *shear* (change of speed with height) and *veer* (change of direction with height) and moist convection; the recipe for a squall line. A squall line is an organised linear structure of intense thunderstorms, often around 100 km ahead of a cold front. These pre-frontal mesoscale structures will be discussed in Section 1.3.2. When an extratropical cyclone is formed, the cold fronts travel from north to south and are located to the left of the core. By the time a cyclone reaches Europe, the cold front often travels from west to east. The stormy weather associated with a cold front can cause ramp events, either directly due to the contrast in meteorological variables or indirectly due to a storm that formed as a result of the cold front. According to the literature, cold fronts often cause ramp-up events [4]. Before a front passes, significant weather can pause temporarily (pre-frontal lull) which can cause a ramp-down event. After front has passed, ramp-down events can occur due to *post-frontal relaxation* [4], [19].

Warm front

A warm front is a boundary between a propagating warm air mass over a colder air mass. The warm front pushes into the colder air mass ahead. The symbol for a warm front is a red line with half circles in the

direction of propagation. In Figure 1.5b, a schematic side view of a warm front is shown. Since warm (especially moist) air has a lower density than cold (especially dry) air, the propagation speed of a warm front is lower than that of a cold front, around $20 - 30 \text{ km} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, or 20 to 30 minutes to travel 10 km. The vertical profile of the boundary is less steep than that of a cold front, around 5 meters vertically every 1 km horizontally. The lower propagation speed and the shallower vertical profile results in a slower updraft of warm (moist) air. Hence a warm front is associated with less severe weather than a cold front. A warm front is indicated by a sudden increase of temperature, and can bring precipitation. The precipitation is often steady drizzle or steady snow. When freezing rain or sleet occurs, it is most often because of a warm front. This happens ahead of the warm front (cold side) when precipitation freezes as it travels through the cold air ahead of the frontal boundary. Ramp events for warm fronts are similar to those of cold fronts.

Figure 1.5: (a) Schematic vertical cross-section of a cold front along the propagation axis. (b) Schematic vertical cross-section of a warm front along the propagation axis.

Occluded front

Warm fronts propagate slower than cold fronts. This results in a moist, warm region behind a warm front and ahead of a cold front. This region is called a *warm sector*. At a certain point, the cold front overtakes the warm front and forms an *occluded front*. Occluded fronts are a sign of a mature extratropical cyclone. On weather charts occluded fronts are indicated by purple half circles and triangles in the direction of propagation. An occluded front is associated with a mixture of weather patterns from the warm and cold front. Occluded fronts often travel with a propagation speed somewhere in between that of a warm and a cold front. Similarly, the steepness of the slope of the frontal boundary is somewhere in between. There are two types of occlusions. A *warm occlusion* is when the air in front of the warm front is colder than the air behind the cold front, before forming an occluded front. A *cold occlusion* is when the air in front of the warm front is less cold than the air behind the cold front. In the North Sea region, we are generally dealing with warm occlusions [34], [40]. In Figure 1.6, a schematic side view of both types of occluded fronts is shown. Occluded fronts can cause ramp events via the same mechanisms warm and cold fronts can.

Figure 1.6: Schematic vertical cross-section of (a) a warm occlusion and (b) a cold occlusion along the propagation axis. Cool air (light blue) is warmer than cold air (dark blue).

Stationary front

A stationary front occurs when the boundary between two airmasses is not moving. On weather maps it is denoted as a line with alternating red semicircles and blue triangles. The flat side of these symbols denote

the side where the cold and warm air masses are located. Even though the frontal boundary does not move, warm air is still moving up and over the cold air. Precipitation is often light, but weather patterns can last for multiple days. Wind often flows parallel to the frontal boundary. To the left as the stationary front is approached. The symbol used for a stationary front is shown in Figure 1.7a.

Troughs and ridges

A *trough* is an elongated region of low atmospheric pressure. We distinguish two types: *Surface troughs* and *troughs aloft*. Surface troughs directly relate to the pressure field at mean sea level. Different from extra tropical cyclones, surface troughs are not surrounded with closed isobars. In the Northern Hemisphere, troughs exhibit cyclonic (counter-clockwise) flow. Surface troughs often have a 180° wind direction shift across them. A *ridge* is the converse of a trough, it is an elongated region of high pressure. Fronts and troughs are intimately related. Surface based frontal boundaries force air to rise (especially cold fronts), creating elongated regions of low pressure along the frontal boundary. This leads to kinks in isobars around fronts, from which the wind direction change across a frontal boundary can be explained. Not all surface troughs are associated with fronts. Surface troughs are not explicitly denoted on weather charts from the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI) weather charts, but can be recognised by looking at isobars, closely packed **L**-areas along a line, or around slow moving fronts (often occluded and stationary fronts).

A trough aloft is a region of low pressure, often cold, air at high altitude. Troughs aloft can be *longwave troughs* (trough in prevailing westerly flow) or *shortwave troughs*. In this study we are only concerned with the effect of shortwave troughs, and we will omit the “shortwave” suffix in the remainder of this work. Troughs aloft are lower in density than its surroundings. This can cause enhanced upward motions and atmospheric instability ahead of the trough as warm, humid and less dense air from the surface rises to higher levels to replace the colder air mass. This convection can lead to cloud forming and precipitation and sometimes to the development of thunderstorms. Troughs aloft often trail behind cold or occluded fronts on surface weather charts, but also can exist without the presence of a front. Troughs aloft do not have a universally accepted symbol convention on weather maps. On the KNMI weather maps used in this study, upper level troughs are denoted by a thick blue line (see Figure 1.7b). In order to study upper level (aloft) troughs properly, one should look at *constant pressure charts* instead of *surface weather charts* since troughs aloft do not have a strong influence on the surface level isobars. This is however beyond the scope of this work. An additional type of trough aloft is a *pre-frontal trough* or *convergence line*. These are regions of convergence, often ahead of cold fronts (in the warm sector). These zones form when winds from two different directions meet and converge. The symbol for these warm troughs is shown in Figure 1.7d. These regions often have thunderstorm activity. Weather resulting from convergence lines is often more localised in comparison to the effect from the other types of troughs aloft. All of the above discussed troughs can have similar effects on surface weather, resulting in convergence, cloud formation and possibly thunderstorm development.

Figure 1.7: Symbols for (a) a stationary front, (b) a trough aloft, (c) a (thunder)storm zone and (d) a convergence line.

1.3.2 Mesoscale meteorology

There is interplay between the different meteorological scales. For example, thunderstorms can develop due to frontal activity. Thunderstorms, in turn, can develop microscale phenomena like tornadoes. In the

following section, an overview is given of these mesoscale features. At the smaller end of this scale features generally have a large Rossby number (Equation 1.12), which means the Coriolis effect does not have any significant effect. At the larger end of mesoscale features (such as low level jets) the Coriolis effect can have an impact. When modelling mesoscale effects, vertical motions become comparable in scale to horizontal motions, this means that the hydrostatic approximation (Equation 1.16) does not hold. This makes their prediction significantly harder than the prediction of synoptic scale features.

Thunderstorms

The vertical motion of the atmosphere is usually quite slow (\sim cm per second) but in thunderstorm updrafts, velocities in excess of $80 \text{ km} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ are often observed. *Moist convection* can occur if initially warm moist air is lifted via *orographic lifting* (topography, air forced to rise up mountain range for example), *frontal lifting* (discussed earlier in Section 1.3), *convergence* (when flows meet and are forced upwards, such as close to a cyclone core) or *convective mixing* (heating from below or added moisture, air becoming more buoyant). Convection is the transfer of heat through the movement of fluid. In meteorology, convection is used only for vertical transport, for horizontal transport, *advection* is used. Thunderstorms are an indication for an unstable atmosphere. Any process that results in heating air from below, or cooling from above, will decrease stability. Lifting a layer of air will also decrease stability. Any process that results in cooling from below or heating from above will increase stability. Lowering a layer of air will increase stability as well.

As an air parcel is lifted, it cools due to adiabatic expansion. An unsaturated air parcel will cool at the *dry adiabatic lapse rate* of $\sim 10^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}$ as it rises. A saturated air parcel will cool at the *moist adiabatic lapse rate*, which is less than $\sim 10^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}$, because of latent heat release from condensation. In addition, clouds are formed. Moist air is less dense than dry air. Warm air is less dense than cold air. The *Environmental lapse rate* is a measure of stability of the atmosphere. A stable atmosphere is successful in resisting vertical motion because the air parcels will cool faster than their environment, hence will stop rising. In an (absolutely) unstable atmosphere, air parcels will continue to be warmer than their environment, thus continue to rise. If the atmosphere is highly unstable, tall large towering clouds called *cumulonimbus* clouds can form causing a thunderstorm (see Figure 1.8a). Precipitation from this cloud can partially evaporate before it reaches the surface. Evaporation extracts heat from the surrounding. This results in a sudden drop in temperature of the air. In addition, *entrainment* (mixing) of cool air from outside the storm gets dragged downward. This is called a *downdraft*. This can cause a pressure increase locally at that location. At the updraft, a local pressure drop can be observed. From the downdraft, cool air comes down from the thunderstorm cloud and spreads as it hits the surface. This is called a *gust front* or *outflow boundary* and has similar characteristics to a cold front but with moist air instead of dry air. If a downdraft is particularly strong, it is called a *downburst*. If it is very narrow, it is called a *microburst*. The winds at a gust front travel radially outwards and are called *straight line winds*. Along the gust front, similar to a cold front, warm moist air can be wedged upwards, which in turn can trigger new thunderstorm development.

Figure 1.8: (a) Cumulonimbus cloud between Brussels and Ghent. A clear anvil structure is formed as the cloud presses against the tropopause. Photographed from Middelburg, 12 May 2025 21:13 CEST. (b) Cumulative discharge map. Source: KNMI, see Appendix A.3.1.

Thunderstorms come in different sizes. A single cell thunderstorm has only one updraft. If there are multiple updrafts, it is called a multicellular thunderstorm. If a system has only one, but large, updraft that rotates, it is called a supercell thunderstorm (referred to as a mesocyclone). There are multiple factors that can cause thunderstorm activity ahead of a cold front:

- *Convergence lines*: A pre-frontal trough is a zone of low pressure and wind convergence ahead of a cold front. This zone often lifts moist, warm air and results in a squall line of thunderstorms ahead of the cold front. These are linearly organised thunderstorms as has been alluded to in Section 1.3.1. The symbol for a convergence line in this study is shown in Figure 1.7d.
- *Gust fronts*: Gust front created by thunderstorms at the cold front, can in turn trigger new thunderstorm activity far away from the cold front.
- *Warm sector instability*: The area between the warm front and the cold front is often warm and moist. This can cause thunderstorm development ahead of the cold front.

When a thunderstorm outflow boundary comes in contact with its updraft, the thunderstorm dies off. If sufficient vertical wind shear and veer is present, the system can sustain itself as the updraft and downdraft are well separated.

A gust front is thought to be able to cause ramp events ([41], preprint at time of writing). Different from the synoptic scale fronts, the formation and effects of a gust front are much harder to predict. Since the development of a thunderstorm can inhibit or encourage the development of other thunderstorms at the same time, their location is quite hard to predict.

Land-sea breezes

Sea and land are heated at different rates. In the afternoon this causes the land to be hotter than the water in the warm seasons. This causes air to rise on land and sink above the sea. At the surface, this sets up a *sea breeze* from the water towards the land. At night the opposite happens, the land, and the air above it, cools faster than the air above sea. This induces a local (thermal) low pressure area causing warm air above the sea to rise. On land, the air sinks down. This causes a *land breeze* from the land towards the sea. A visual explanation is shown in Figure 1.9. The land-sea breeze circulation is very regular and effects are supposedly noticeable within 100 km from the coast [42]. For (classical, pure) land-sea breezes, the winds tend to flow directly to the lowest pressure, as the scale of these flows are too slow for the Coriolis effect to become noticeable (recent studies question this, refer to [42], [43] for *corkscrew*- and *backdoor*-type sea-breezes).

In some locations, such as Florida, the sea breeze in the afternoon often sets up a *sea breeze front*. This front has similar characteristics as a cold front, where cold sea air replaces warm air on land. If the incoming cold air is humid, this can trigger afternoon thunderstorms. In Florida, this uplift of warm air is sometimes enhanced by converging sea breezes from both sides of the peninsula.

In the mid latitudes (30° - 60°) land-sea breezes are strongest in the warm seasons. In the cold seasons, the temperature difference between land and sea is smaller. In addition, global scale effects such as west-lies (prevailing winds, wind from the most common wind direction for a given location) overshadow the land-sea breeze effects. Prevailing winds increase in strength during winter as the polar cyclone increases in strength, but this is outside the scope of this work.

Figure 1.9: A schematic illustration of sea and land breezes.

Low level jets

Normally, wind speed increases with height above the surface. The vertical wind profile is often described by a *power law* or *logarithmic* profile [39]. In normal conditions, these *wind profile parametrisations* are used for extrapolating readily available wind speed and direction measurements at 10 meters high to turbine height. However, sometimes the measured vertical wind profile seems to deviate from the expected profile. Instead of an ever increasing profile, sometimes there is a wind speed maximum at a relatively low altitude. This fast moving ribbon of air is called a *low level jet* (LLJ). Wind shear and turbulence intensity also differ from when the standard formulas are being used [44]. The term *low level jet* is given to every vertical wind profile, regardless of its physical forming mechanism. A schematic profile is shown in Figure 1.10.

Figure 1.10: Schematic view of a 'normal' log vertical wind profile and when an LLJ is present. The jet core height does not have to be at 100 meters height, this figure is only for illustrative purposes. The *fall-off* is the wind speed difference of the jet core to the wind speed minima above the core. A common criterion for a vertical wind profile with a maxima at low altitude is having a fall-off of $2 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. The figure is adapted from [44].

The wind speed at the surface must vanish (no-slip condition). Above this layer is *Prandtl* layer, which is up to 100 meters altitude. In this layer, forces due to turbulent viscosity dominate. In this layer the wind speed increases rapidly with height. Above this layer is the *Ekman* layer, here the Coriolis force becomes important and causes clockwise turning (in Northern Hemisphere) of wind with height (*veer* or *directional wind shear*) (small Rossby number, Equation 1.12). As discussed in Section 1.3.2 - Thunderstorms, an unstable atmosphere leads to vertical motions, which in turn causes vertical wind shear to be reduced (unstable stratification). Stable atmospheres suppress vertical mixing, which enables high speed winds to sustain at higher layers (stable stratification). The presence of turbulent mixing defines the height of the atmospheric boundary layer. During the day, the Earth heats up the lower part of the boundary layer which causes vertical mixing upwards (convection). This increases the boundary layer height. When the surface temperature drops, this forcing stops, turbulence dies off and the boundary layer becomes more stable and shallow. If a flow undergoes a change in atmospheric stability, the frictional forces due to turbulent mixing change as well. This can happen when a flow transitions from above warm land to above the colder sea, as the frictional forces suddenly decrease. At first, the pressure gradient force, Coriolis force and frictional force are in balance, but after this disruption, only the pressure gradient force and Coriolis force remain. This causes an increase in speed, which in turn causes an increase in the Coriolis force (Equation 1.9). This phenomenon is called an *inertial oscillation* and are clockwise in the Northern Hemisphere. As the wind speed increases, it becomes super-geostrophic, which causes the "nose" shape in the vertical wind profile. This formation mechanism for low level jets was introduced by Blackadar [45]. This forming mechanism is shown in Figure 1.11.

The transition in atmospheric stability can happen due to coastal transitions [46], or due to changes over time as the surface warms and cools during the diurnal cycle [45], [47]. The latter type is called a *nocturnal jet*. However, many contradictive claims are made about the occurrence of LLJ events.

Figure 1.11: (a): Forces are in balance whilst flow is above land. (b): Sudden drop in friction f_{fric} as flow enters more stable atmosphere such as a cool ocean in spring or summer, resulting in an increase in speed. (c): The aforementioned speed increase causes the Coriolis force to increase, since it depends on the velocity \mathbf{v} . (d): Net acceleration \mathbf{a}_{net} turn towards the Coriolis acceleration vector, which causes the velocity vector to turn.

There are more proposed forming mechanisms. The second commonly mentioned forming mechanism was first introduced by Holton [48], where horizontal temperature gradients cause tilting of isobaric surfaces, leading to a thermal wind, this can manifest itself as a low level jet. The specific working of this mechanism are outside the scope of this work, since a lot more terms should be introduced. Many studies agree on that LLJ formation requires very stable conditions. Temperature inversions, stable stratifications, clear skies and high pressure areas seem to be preferable. A study on LLJs [44] on the Dutch North Sea has found that LLJ's often occur in the warm seasons, especially in spring, often with an easterly component. This study used both observational data and reanalysis¹ (ERA5) data. It found that the representation of low level jets in ERA5 is poor in terms of quantities such as jet height. However, climatological characteristics such as the seasonal cycle and their occurrences with certain circulation types are represented quite well. It found a diurnal pattern with a peak in the evening. The study supports that weak, large high pressure systems and stably stratified conditions are preferable. According to this study, the jet core is at 50 to 200 meters altitude along the coast. LLJ's supposedly affects wake recovery rates [49] (Section 1.1), turbulence and increases wind speed at core height. Another study by the same author [50] studied LLJ events using only observational data from the Ijmuiden meteo mast. At the time the study was conducted, the surroundings of this mast were relatively undeveloped. This made it possible to get undisturbed wind measurements at a wide range of heights. It is important to keep in mind that low level jet formation might be inhibited by wind farms themselves due to the introduced turbulence. This study found that stable stratification in spring and summer leads to LLJ events up to 12% of the time.

A study that simulated LLJ activity on the East Coast of the US [51] suggested that the height of the jet core (nose) appears higher when a wind farm is present, claiming that wind farms might erode LLJs. A different study on low level jets at the North Sea region next to Denmark ([52], preprint at time of writing), based on a weather research model and LiDAR data, found that the diurnal cycle can vary in strength and phase for different locations. In addition, it found that most LLJs last one hour or less. From the Figures in the paper can be deduced that the maximum LLJ strength at the location from [44] is at 18:00, which is in accordance with that paper. A paper with case studies using the FINO1 mast (North of the Netherlands, in German waters) [53], found that LLJ have strong wind shear (and veer) below the core, in agreement with Figure 1.10 (wind veer not shown). That study also found that LLJs occurred 14.5% of the time and on 64.8% of 250 days. A study using only reanalysis data (ERA5) [54] argues that the directional shear (veer) is so identifiable that the wind direction change with height is a better definition for an LLJ than the fall-off definition. A study on low level jets at the English channel using LiDAR [55], found that at that location, LLJ wind profiles were detected 5% of the time. Since multiple studies found LLJ activity in the surrounding area of the Belgian offshore cluster, they might also play a role at the Belgian cluster.

Many studies agree that low level jet activity requires stably stratified conditions. There are multiple measures for atmospheric stability. A common measure is the *Bulk Richardson number* [56],

$$Ri_B = \frac{g}{\theta_{\text{virt}}} \frac{\Delta\theta_{\text{virt}}}{\Delta z} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{\Delta u}{\Delta z}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta v}{\Delta z}\right)^2}, \quad (1.17)$$

¹Reanalysis data is data produced by a weather model based on historical measurements, as a means of interpolating atmospheric variables.

where g the gravitational acceleration, θ_{virt} the virtual potential temperature, Δz the change in height with respect to some variable, u the zonal (local east) and v the meridional (local north) wind speed. Virtual potential temperature is a combination of the *virtual temperature*² and the *potential temperature*³. The numerator of Equation 1.17 is called the *buoyancy term*. If this numerator is smaller than zero, then $Ri_B < 0$, then the atmosphere is unstably stratified. If the buoyancy term is positive, turbulent mixing is suppressed which leads to a stably stratified atmosphere. [44], [50] found that low level jet occurrence is strongly related to positive Ri_B values, plateauing for Ri_B values over 0.08. Note that some authors, such as [32] refer to LLJs as being synoptic scale events.

1.4 This work

There is a significant body on power ramp events using reanalysis data. As established by [44], ERA 5 does not perform well at converting wind speed data measured at 10 meters high to 100 meter high at turbine level (see Section 1.3.2). This study aims to assess the interplay between ramp events and their meteorological causes, specifically at the Belgian offshore cluster. This brings us to the main research question:

What is the relationship between ramp event duration, size and the associated meteorological cause?

For answering this question, four subquestions are formulated:

1. How do power generation and meteorological variables differ between seasons and time of day, and how does this relate to ramp events?
2. How important are low level jets for power production at the Belgian offshore cluster and do they cause ramp events? Can low level jet activity be noticed in production data without wind measurements at turbine height?
3. What meteorological features are responsible for ramp events at the Belgian offshore wind farm cluster and in what quantities do these meteorological features occur? How can synoptic scale and mesoscale meteorological features be distinguished from each other in the power generation time series using meteorological data?
4. How does the occurrence and size of ramp events depend on wind farm cluster size?

This work will address these questions via the following methods listed below.

1. In Chapter 3, the seasonal and diurnal patterns of generation data, meteorological data and the relation between them is analysed. In addition, the seasonal and diurnal distributions of ramp event occurrences are presented.
2. In Section 2.3 and Section 3.4, a novel approach for searching low level jet activity in generation power curves is described and carried out. The main idea of this approach is looking for times at which the generation is higher than would be expected given the surface (10 meter) wind speed.
3. In Chapter 4, a few examples of typical meteorological situations that have caused ramp events are discussed. The tools presented in this chapter have been carried out for all ramp events that occurred in the observing time range. This approach is a classification task for associating ramp events with certain synoptic or mesoscale meteorological causes, based on the meteorological situation. How different wind farms react to a certain meteorological feature might tell something about the scale of such features. The results of this approach are presented at the end of Chapter 4.
4. In Chapter 5, the evolution of the number of ramps, the average ramp duration and the average ramp size of different hypothetical (smaller) farms is explored. The hypothetical clusters are made from subsets of different sizes of the real offshore cluster, using data from individual farms.

²This is the temperature at which dry air would have the same density as moist air at the same pressure. It is always larger than the actual air temperature because water vapour is less dense than dry air.

³This is the temperature a parcel of air would have if brought dry-adiabatically to mean sea level. It removes the temperature variation due to pressure changes.

To investigate the relation between energy ramp events and their meteorological causes, classes for different meteorological situations have to be defined. There are multiple ways of doing this. One possible way would be to classify the different features and their effects on ramping into many classes. This could include distinguishing pre- or post frontal effects, different kind of troughs aloft, different kinds of thunderstorm complexes and noting in what wind speed range the changes occur. However, since large offshore wind farms and the field of study on energy ramp events are quite new, data on energy ramp events in the Belgian offshore cluster is scarce. To prevent something analogous to overfitting to happen (like a histogram with a too small of a bin width). This study will only distinguish between the following meteorological features.

- **Low core passage** (Synoptic): This will include ramp events where the main reason for the wind and production change is due to an **L** core being in close vicinity of the wind farms. Cut-out events caused by extratropical cyclones are classified separately. Deep surface troughs will also be included in this class.
- **Low core cut-out** (Synoptic): This will include ramp events where the main reason for the production change is the vicinity of an **L** core to the cluster, causing a partial or total cut-out event. This event is separated from non cut-out events as cut outs can have different meteorological causes.
- **High core passage** (Synoptic): This will include ramp events where vicinity of a **H** area to the cluster is the main reason for the wind and production to change.
- **Frontal related** (Synoptic): This will include all ramp events where the main cause of the production change is the passage of a front. This can be cold, warm, occluded or stationary fronts. This will include prefrontal lulls (reduction of wind speed before a front), the actual passage of a front and post-frontal relaxations.
- **Frontal cut-out** (Synoptic): This will include events where the main cause of the production change is a cut-out event incurred by wind speed changes due to a frontal passage.
- **Complex** (Synoptic): All ramp events where too many effects are at play to determine what the main driver for the ramp event was.
- **Pre/Post-frontal convection** (Synoptic): Include events for cases where thunderstorm activity occurred and frontal related effects did occur, some time (<6 hours) before or after the ramp. May include troughs aloft, thunderstorm zones and convergence lines (Figure 1.7b, 1.7c, 1.7d).
- **Non-frontal convection** (Mesoscale): Include events for cases where thunderstorm activity occurred, but no frontal related effects were likely to occur. This includes effects from isolated troughs aloft, organised thunderstorm groups and convergence zones (Figure 1.7b, 1.7c, 1.7d). If a weak front was present, but the main cause for the ramp event was likely the accompanying convective storm, it will also be classified as non-frontal.
- **Unknown** (Mesoscale): This class includes ramp events that cannot be explained with a synoptic weather map or with surface meteorological data from stations around the wind farm cluster. Ramp events that are related to low level jet activity or land-sea breezes would be classified in this class.

An alternative way of defining classes is by sorting ramp events based on the location of synoptic features such as **L** and **H** areas (similar to the approach taken in [32]) or with any established weather type classification scheme. Or constructing a more local weather type classification for the southern North Sea. However, this is beyond the scope of this work.

Chapter 2

Methodology

In this chapter, the data used in this study will be explored and the methods of approaching the problems introduced in Section 1.4 will be discussed. The acquisition of production and meteorological data is described in-depth in Appendix A, along with code listings for acquiring and pre-processing of the data. All the data used in this study is publicly available. In Section 2.1 the data used in this study is outlined and some general information about the region of interest is presented. Section 2.2 is about what ramp events have been extracted from the generation time series, and how these ramp event dates are distributed over the observing time range. Section 2.3 introduces a novel attempt for finding low level jet activity using power curves from specially separated weather stations and farms. Section 2.4 outlines the tools used for the classification task for associating ramp events with their causes. The chapter ends with Section 2.5, where the hypothetical cluster approach is presented and the ramp extraction process.

2.1 Generation and meteorological data

Generation data of the entire cluster is provided by the Belgian transmission system operator (TSO), Elia. This dataset contains 15-minutely averages of the production in MW. A timestamp denotes the beginning of the observation period in UTC. Next to production data, this dataset contains the monitored capacity for calculating the load factor. The load factor is the ratio between the actual production and the max rated production. The load factor is useful when comparing different wind farm sizes. This data set also contains *decremental bidding dates*, where Elia has requested the wind farms to reduce production below its maximum capacity (curtailment). At these times, generation data is not representative of the wind speed. For more information on this dataset and the pre-processing steps taken, see Appendix A.1.

For the production of the individual wind farms, data is obtained from the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E). ENTSO-E itself gets the data from Elia. As with the Elia data set, a timestamp denotes the beginning of the observation period in UTC. The data is in units of MW. For more information of the process of this data, see Appendix A.2.

Farm	Capacity	Distance to shore	Farm	Capacity	Distance to shore
Norther	370 MW	23 km	Seastar	252 MW	40 km
Thorntonbank NE	148 MW	30 km	Nobelwind	165 MW	47 km
Thorntonbank SW	178 MW	30 km	Belwind	171 MW	49 km
Rentel	307 MW	34 km	Northwester 2	219 MW	51 km
Northwind	216 MW	37 km	Mermaid	236 MW	54 km

Table 2.1: Installed capacity per individual wind farm. Wind farms are ordered from closest to furthest from the coast. Sum of all is 2262 MW. The information about the installed capacity comes from ENTSO-E (Appendix A.2). Distance to shore data comes from the Belgian Offshore Platform (BOP), URL: <https://www.belgianoffshoreplatform.be/en/projects/> (Accessed on 2025-07-03).

Weather data comes from KNMI and Meetnet Vlaamse Banken. The relevant stations from which data has been used are shown in table 2.2. For more information of the data acquisition and pre-processing for these stations, refer to Appendix A.3.2 (Vlakte van de Raan, validated, 60-minutely), A.3.3 (Borssele Alpha, validated, 60-minutely), A.3.4 (Multiple Dutch weather stations, unvalidated, 10 minutely), A.3.5 (Multiple Dutch weather stations, unvalidated, 10 minutely), A.4 (Westhinder and Wandelaar, Belgian stations, 10-minutely).

Weather station	Number	Latitude	Longitude	Distance	Quantities
Westhinder		51.389	2.438	~40 km	wd, ws, wg, T, rh, MSLP, Tsea
Wandelaar		51.394	3.046	~26 km	wd, ws, wg, T, rh, MSLP
Borssele Alpha	06317	51.700	3.057	~14 km	wd, ws, wg, T, rh, MSLP
Vlakte van de Raan	06313	51.504	3.242	~26 km	wd, ws, wg
Cadzand	06308	51.380	3.379	~42 km	wd, ws, wg
Vlissingen	06310	51.441	3.596	~51 km	wd, ws, wg, T, rh, MSLP
Oosterschelde	06312	51.767	3.622	~52 km	wd, ws, wg

Table 2.2: wd : wind direction, ws : wind speed, wg : wind gust speed, T : air temperature, rh: relative humidity, MSLP : mean sea level air pressure, Tsea : sea temperature. For information on the availability of the data, see Figure 2.1.

The 10-minutely data from KNMI is not validated. Using the validated 60-minutely data from Borssele Alpha en Vlakte van de Raan, the 10-minutely can be checked if it contains sensical values.

Figure 2.1: Data availability plot for the relevant quantities from all the weather stations used in this study. White regions depict datetimes outside the bounds of the dataset. Black means the value for a specific datetime is missing, i.e. `NaN`. Sometimes availability can be underestimated due to the thickness of the black bars. The first part of a name (wd, ws, wg, T, rh, MSLP) denotes the quantity, the second part (10m, sensor, 1p5 (1.5 meters)) denotes the altitude of the data point. The third part (10minmax, 1minavg) is the interval over which the value has been averaged or maximised.

2.2 Grouping of ramp events

The ramp events used in this study are based on the threshold definition of a ramp event (Section 1.2). Ramp date times have been extracted from the Elia generation dataset by a PhD student at the Royal

Meteorological Institute of Belgium (RMI). The provided dataset contains 498 entries. For now, we differentiate between 4 different types of ramp events: `R100060`, `R150060`, `R50015` and `R100015`. With the first number the magnitude of the ramp in MW and the second part the duration in minutes. For each type we differentiate between a ramp-up and ramp-down (e.g. `RU100060`, `RD100060`,...). The different ramp types should be considered separately. For example, an `R150060`-type ramp will always also be an `R100060` ramp. If an `R100060` ramp is fast enough to change 500 MW in 15 minutes, it will also be an `R50015`-type ramp. The provided ramp datetime list contains the starting time of the interval the ramp criteria are met. This means that the dataset contains ramp sequences rather than actual starting times, therefore many entries in this set correspond to a single event if a ramp has a sufficiently long duration. Using the preprocessing steps described in Appendix A.5, starting and ending times are obtained. In this study, a ramp event will always be denoted by its starting datetime. A list of all ramp starting datetimes is provided in Appendix A.5.

Rtype	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	Total
RU100060	31	41	78	18	2	170
RD100060	19	49	47	14	1	130
RU150060	2	4	8	0	0	14
RD150060	1	6	3	1	0	11
RU050015	18	22	37	6	0	83
RD050015	11	31	34	10	0	86
RU100015	0	1	1	0	0	2
RD100015	0	1	1	0	0	2

Table 2.3: Number of ramp event *sequences* of each ramp type per year.

The analysed time range is from 2021-01-01 to 2025-03-09. The number of ramp events vary quite a bit year to year, as can be seen in Table 2.4.

Rtype	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	Total
RU100060	14	23	38	10	1	86
RD100060	8	27	22	7	1	65
RU150060	2	3	4	0	0	9
RD150060	1	4	2	1	0	8
RU050015	17	19	35	6	0	77
RD050015	11	28	31	8	0	78
RU100015	0	1	1	0	0	2
RD100015	0	1	1	0	0	2

Table 2.4: Number of ramp events of each ramp type per year.

The ending dates are obtained by taking every last datetime in a sequence of a certain ramp type and then adding the duration criterion. With the now extracted begin and end times, we do not have any doubly counted ramp events within a ramp type. Plotting the change in generation for each ramp event against the actual duration (not the duration criterion) allows us to check if the ramp extraction method worked properly. The spread of production plotted against the ramp duration is shown in Figure 2.2. `R100060` (blue and orange) occur over a broad range of durations. `R50015`-type ramp events are often 15 minutes, but rarely happen sequentially, these are very fast ramp events (more than a 1000 MW change in less than 30 minutes, brown and purple). The remaining types (`R150060`, `R100015`) occurred quite rarely. This Figure also illustrates that the number of ramp events extracted will probably be sensitive to the threshold, as the `R100060` (blue, orange) and `R50015` (purple, brown) are skewed toward the threshold boundary (at ± 1000 MW and ± 500 MW). This means probably quite a bit more ramp events would be flagged if the requirements would be loosened a bit. For the diurnal and seasonal patterns in ramp occurrences, refer to Section 3.3. In Figure 2.3, the occurrence of all the different ramp types is shown. In Figure 2.4 the distribution of dates where at least one ramp event has happened are shown, this could be important since some consecutive ramp events can be caused by a singular meteorological event.

Figure 2.2: Spread of change in generation for each ramp event. The coloured dots on the horizontal grid lines are the actual ramp events. The number above this series of dots is the number of ramp events of that type for that duration.

Figure 2.3: Ramp event distribution over the analysed time range. The coloured dots on the horizontal grid lines are the actual ramp events. The numbers in the boxes are the number of ramp events that occurred in that season of that year. A jitter has been added to illustrate the density of ramp events while preventing overlap.

Figure 2.4: Distribution of days where at least one ramp event has occurred. The numbers in the boxes are the number of days of ramp events that occurred in that season of that year. A jitter has been added to illustrate the density of ramp events while preventing overlap.

In the remainder of this work, there are two different ways in which the ramp events will be grouped into types:

1. Ramp types will be analysed completely separate (such as in Figure 2.2). This means there can be overlap between ramp events. A fast, `R50015`-type ramp that takes a long time can be counted as multiple ramp events, or as multiple different types of ramp events. The different types using this way of grouping are `R100060`, `R150060`, `R50015` and `R100015`. To reiterate, `R100015` means a change in production of 1000 MW or more in 15 minute or less. All these events are also `R50015` and `R100060`-type ramp events. The results for this way are presented in Section 4.2
2. The second way the ramp events can be grouped into types is by combining the above types. We recognise three different types. `Only R100060`, `R100060 and R50015` and `Only R50015`. When talking about these types, it is implied that `Only R100060`-type events can not be so fast that it also can be classified as any of the other type events. Thus this is a slow, large ramp. `R100060 and R50015` is a fast, large ramp. These types of ramp events have to meet both the `R100060` and the `R50015` criteria at least once during the time the ramp occurs. `Only R50015`-type ramps are fast and short. These ramps will only meet the `R50015`-criteria but not the `R100060`-criteria. The results for this way are presented in Section 4.3

In Chapter 3 the first method of grouping will be used (with the exception of Section 3.4. Chapter 4 will present the results for both methods of grouping. The latter method has the advantage that all ramp events are unique. By doing this, the ramp events can be analysed together without counting ramp events double. In Section 2.5, a more general ramp extraction method is presented, which extracts the same ramp datetimes as discussed in this section. The process of creating the different ramp types is shown in Figure 2.6.

2.3 The search for low level jets

This work contains a novel approach for searching for low level jet activity affecting wind power generation. The idea is based on that surface winds normally can be extrapolated to turbine height with a power or log law. This is not the case in the presence of a low level jet. One could expect that the wind speed conversions will be different when a low level jet is present. Normally, when the production is high, the wind speed is also high according to the power curve. Abnormally high production in combination with a relatively low surface wind speed could be an indication of low level jet activity. For this reason, a tool has been built that plots the load factor against a certain meteorological variable, split in time of day blocks and seasons. Using an interactive `matplotlib.pyplot` backend, each point can be clicked. When a point is clicked, the generation time series and the evolution of meteorological variables can quickly be inspected. This way specific production and speed or direction combinations can be investigated. The results of this approach are presented in Section 3.4.

2.4 Classifying ramp events

In order to get insight into the meteorological situation at the moment a ramp event occurs, a dashboard has been developed. The dashboard gives an overview of the relevant meteorological quantities in and around the region of interest (the Belgian offshore cluster). For this, data is used from different weather stations around the cluster. In addition, generation data from the entire cluster and from the individual wind farms is used. To get a sense of the weather on a synoptic scale (low and high pressure cores and fronts), synoptic weather maps from the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI) are used. In addition, lightning discharge maps from the KNMI are used as an indicator for thunderstorm activity (and thus, the (in)stability of the atmosphere in the region). To distinguish larger scale from smaller scale effects the synoptic maps can be used to see if a ramp event is associated with a synoptic scale effect or not (**L** or **H** core or front). The discharge map can be used as a indicator for thunderstorm activity. LLJ formation presumably takes place under stable conditions (Section 1.3.2). Thus, the presence of a thunderstorm will likely make it hard for LLJs to form due to the high turbulence intensity and presence of vertical motions. The acquisition of these KNMI maps is discussed in Appendix A.3.1. These maps contain isobars, low pressure core (**L**), high pressure core (**H**), cold front, warm fronts, occluded front, stationary fronts, convergence zones (lines, mentioned as often ahead of cold fronts), thunderstorm regions (mentioned as often as a result of a convergence zone) and troughs aloft (mentioned as cold air present aloft). The symbols used in these maps are shown in Figure 1.7 in the meteorology section (Section 1.3).

The dashboard has some interactive features. When opened for a date a ramp event has occurred, it will open with the first 6 hourly interval selected before that ramp. It will only show maps on 00, 06, 12 or 18 hours, since only at those times the KNMI weather maps are available. It will show two weather maps, one for the currently selected datetime, and one for the next (6 hours later). This is such that in one frame, both the synoptic situation before and after the ramp event can be inspected. When an interactive `matplotlib.pyplot`-backend is used, the dashboard will have usable buttons for skipping to the next or previous 6 hour interval. In addition, the plots can be zoomed in by selecting a smaller range in the upper generation plot. The buttons are intentionally left in in the 2023-11-02 case study (Figure 4.6). The pretty \LaTeX version is oriented in portrait and is used in Chapter 4 for discussing some case studies.

The dashboards are also used for classifying every ramp event that happened in the time range concerning this study. For this, a `PyQt6`-application has been built for easy opening of the dashboard and noting down the associated meteorological cause. The layout of the application is shown in Figure 2.5. The results of this classification task are presented in Section 4.2.

Figure 2.5: Python based program for ramp classification task with a graphical user interface, using `PyQt6`.

2.5 Clustering the Belgian offshore zone into smaller clusters

To construct hypothetical smaller clusters out of the real Belgian offshore cluster, multiple approaches can be taken. In this study, all possible subsets have been used. This has been done using the mathematical powerset $\mathcal{P}(S)$. A powerset is a set containing all possible subsets of a set. Consider a set $S = \{x, y, z\}$, then the powerset $\mathcal{P}(\{x, y, z\}) = \{\{\}, \{x\}, \{y\}, \{z\}, \{x, y\}, \{x, z\}, \{y, z\}, \{x, y, z\}\}$ contains $2^{|S|}$, ($2^3 = 8$) elements. An empty cluster is physically irrelevant, so we subtract the empty set $\{\}$ from the powerset. The Belgian offshore cluster contains 10 wind farms of varying sizes (Table 2.1), thus $2^{10} - 1 = 1023$ hypothetical clusters are possible with installed capacity ranging from 148 MW (Thorntonbank NE) to 2262 MW (the entire real offshore cluster).

All hypothetical clusters are ordered by increasing total capacity. For every cluster, a ramp extraction method is used to obtain ramp datetimes. When we are concerned with the real cluster, we distinguish between three ramp types: `Only R100060`, `R100060 and R50015` and `Only R50015`. For the smaller hypothetical clusters, these ramp criteria are scaled proportionally to their installed capacity, such that the ramp events are the same as before in terms of load factors. The real cluster has an installed capacity of 2262 MW, hence the ramp types defined in terms of load factors are denoted as `Only R_0.442_60`, `R_0.422_60 and R_0.221_15` and `Only R_0.221_15` respectively. For all the other parts of this project, a ramp extraction method from an RMI PhD student is used. This extraction method has been reverse engineered such that ramp events can be extracted from the hypothetical time series. This ramp extraction method is shown in Code Listing 1.

```

1 def RampExtractor(Size, Dt, UorD, gencol, only_first=True):
2     valid = eliadf['bidding'] == False
3     invalid = eliadf['bidding'] == True
4     gencol = gencol.copy()
5     gencol[invalid] = np.nan # Removal of decremental bidding datetimes
6     shift_periods = int(Dt / 15)
7     diff = gencol.shift(-shift_periods) - gencol # Calculating the forward difference
8     if UorD=='U':
9         ramp_mask = (diff > Size) & valid
10    if UorD=='D':
11        ramp_mask = (diff < -Size) & valid
12    df = pd.DataFrame(index=eliadf.index[ramp_mask])
13    df['time_diff'] = df.index.to_series().diff()
14    Dt_timedelta = pd.Timedelta(minutes=Dt)
15    df['start'] = df.index
16    df['end'] = df.index + Dt_timedelta
17    df['group_id'] = (df['time_diff'] > Dt_timedelta).cumsum()
18    df.drop(columns='time_diff', inplace=True)
19    df['Size'] = Size
20    df['Dt'] = Dt
21    df['U/D'] = UorD
22    if only_first == False:
23        return df # Overlap within ramp type allowed (Table 2.3)
24    if only_first == True:
25        starts = df.groupby('group_id').first()
26        ends = df.groupby('group_id').last()['end']
27        starts['end'] = ends
28        starts['prod_start'] = gencol.loc[starts['start']].values
29        starts['prod_end'] = gencol.loc[starts['end']].values
30        return starts # No overlap within ramp type (Table 2.4)
31
32 def classify_ramps_dynamically(df):
33     df = df.sort_values('start')
34     current_group = 0
35     current_group_end = pd.Timestamp.min
36     group_ids = []
37     for idx, row in df.iterrows():
38         if row['start'] > current_group_end:
39             current_group += 1
40             current_group_end = row['end']
41         else:
42             current_group_end = max(current_group_end, row['end'])
43         group_ids.append(current_group)
44     df['overlap_group'] = group_ids
45     df['ramp_type'] = df.apply(lambda r: f"{r['U/D']}_{r['Size']:.3f}_{int(r['Dt'])}", axis=1)
46     group_types = df.groupby('overlap_group')['ramp_type'].agg(lambda s:
47         ↪ tuple(sorted(s.unique())))
48     classification_map = group_types.map(lambda x: '+'.join(x))
49     df['class'] = df['overlap_group'].map(classification_map)
50     return df.groupby('overlap_group').first()
51
52 gen=eliadf['Measured & Upscaled']
53 rampU=pd.concat([RampExtractor(1000, 60, 'U', gen), RampExtractor(500, 15, 'U', gen)])
54 rampD=pd.concat([RampExtractor(1000, 60, 'D', gen), RampExtractor(500, 15, 'D', gen)])
55 rampUnique, rampDunique = classify_ramps_dynamically(rampU), classify_ramps_dynamically(rampD)

```

Code Listing 1: The first function (`RampExtractor`) is the ramp extraction algorithm. When `only_first=False`, the original ramp datetime sequences are found. When `only_first=True`, the sequences are removed and only the starting datetime of the ramp event is given. The second function (`classify_ramps_dynamically`) is for combining ramp events into `Only R.0.442.60`, `R.0.422.60` and `R.0.221.15` and `Only R.0.221.15`.

When applying the first function (`RampExtractor(..., only_first=False)`) on the Elia dataset (Section 2.2), the exact same datetimes are found as the datetimes provided by the RMI PhD student. This means that this code could have been used for the entirety of this project. Code Listing 1 produces ramp types that have to be considered separately. The second function (`classify_ramps_dynamically`) is used to combine them into the desired `Only R.0.422.60`, `R.0.422.60` and `R.0.221.15` and `Only R.0.221.15` classes. The functions described above also accept load factors, then `gen` has to be a `pandas` dataframe column containing load factors. This code can be used to extract the ramp events for all hypothetical clusters. The results of this approach are presented in Chapter 5. Figure 2.6 shows the different ramp extraction steps.

Figure 2.6: The different steps in producing the different ramp types. **A.** A decremental bid is placed, which would cause an invalid (human caused) ramp event. This point from the generation time series has to be discarded. **B.** The threshold-based ramp extraction method lists ramp sequences every 15-minutes the time series satisfy the ramp criteria (Table 2.3). **C.** Ramp sequences are removed, a start and end datetime is stored (Table 2.4). **D.** Overlap between the different ramp types are given their own class.

Chapter 3

Diurnal and seasonal cycle

It is useful to get a sense of how production and meteorological variables change over the year (seasonal), during the day (diurnal) and across locations (spatial spread weather stations). In Section 3.1, seasonal and diurnal cycle of the production is discussed. In Section 3.2 the different meteorological variables are analysed for temporal patterns and how they depend on location. In addition, this section goes into how the production depends on wind speed and wind direction. Section 3.3 discusses the temporal distribution of the ramp events detected in this study. Section 3.4 builds upon Section 3.2, incorporating the findings from the preceding sections to give an overview for the Borssele Alpha weather station.

3.1 Seasonal and diurnal patterns in production

In Figure 3.1, violin plots are shown to illustrate the evolution of the spread in load factor based on the time of day and season. Across every season and every location (entire cluster, or outer ends; Norther and Mermaid), the wind farms have a higher load factor in the late afternoon and evening. This can be seen by the width of the tops of the violin plots and the mean production (black dots). Especially in the warm seasons (spring and summer), a clear diurnal pattern is visible. As expected, the load factor overall is higher in the the cold seasons (winter and autumn) than in the warm seasons. Due to the non-linearity of the power curves (Section 1.1), the production distribution takes on a somewhat bimodal form.

Figure 3.1: Spread in load factor grouped by season, and time of day 4-hour blocks. Decremental bid dates are removed. Statistical quantities are calculated over all 15-minutely averaged values. The number of data points used in each violin plot is shown in small grey coloured numbers.

3.2 Seasonal and diurnal patterns in meteorological variables

In the upper plot of Figure 3.2, the 7-day average of air temperature of different stations and the 10-minutely sea temperature at Westhinder is shown. In the lower plot, the difference of the air temperature and the sea temperature is plotted. The air temperature at Westhinder (~ 30 km from the shore) deviates the least from the sea temperature. The closer to the shore, the more the air temperature deviates from the sea temperature (Wandelaar ~ 10 km, Vlissingen just onshore on an embankment). The cycles of air and sea temperatures are not in phase, as the sea temperature takes more time to rise and fall. In spring and summer, the average air temperature is sometimes higher than sea temperature, whilst in autumn and winter, the sea temperature is quite a bit higher than the average air temperature.

Figure 3.2: The seasonal variation in ambient temperature at different weather stations. Westhinder also has sea temperature data. The upper plot contains the 10 minutely sea temperature at Westhinder, which does not have significant daily fluctuations. The fluctuations in the background belong to the 10 minutely air temperature. To get a sense of how the trend of the temperature changes with seasons, the weekly averages are plotted. In the lower plot, the air temperatures at the different weather stations are shown *relative* to the sea temperature at Westhinder.

Figure 3.3: Diurnal cycle of hourly averaged air temperature relative to sea temperature at Westhinder, grouped by season. The shaded area represents the standard deviation calculated over all measurements in that hour and season combination.

In Figure 3.3, the diurnal cycle of the temperature is shown for each season. Agreeing with Figure 3.2, the further the weather station is from the shore, the closer the air temperature follows the sea temperature (the black horizontal zero line). Weather stations closer to the shore have larger daily temperature swings overall. In the warm seasons, Wandelaar and Vlissingen measure higher temperature on average than the sea temperature measured at Westhinder during the day. This could indicate a difference in turbulence intensity and friction between land and sea (Section 1.3.2). This could possibly promote the formation of LLJs. It could also be possible that land-sea interactions such as sea and land breezes could arise due to the diurnal cycle of temperature, as described in Section 1.3.2.

In Figure 3.4, violin plots are shown for analysing the diurnal and seasonal spread of the measured wind direction for different weather stations. The vertical axis is the wind direction (wind coming from the north is 0° , from the east is 90° , etc...). Wider parts of the violin plots indicate more frequent occurring directions. In the cold seasons (winter and autumn) the wind direction is quite broad and SW-dominant across all stations. No clear diurnal cycle is visible for the cold seasons. In contrast, in summer and spring, the spread in wind direction is more localised and bimodal. For the warm seasons, a clear diurnal pattern is visible. For Wandelaar, the flow becomes more westerly during the summer afternoon. As the evening passes, it becomes more southerly again. The same occurs at Cadzand, but more extreme. This could possibly be explained by mesoscale effects such as land-sea breezes, as discussed in Section 1.3.2. At Westhinder and Borssele, the shift of the “blobs” in the violin plots is not as strong as the shift observed at stations closer to the shore. In spring, the “blobs” are less localised than in summer. North easterly flows seem slightly more common in spring than in summer. This plot shows that statistical quantities such as the average value do not always represent the data correctly. In the warm seasons, the wind blows only rarely from the average wind direction.

In Figure 3.5, violin plots are shown for analysis of the diurnal and seasonal spread of the measured wind speed at the different weather stations. The spread in winds do not differ significantly between weather stations. On average, we observe a higher wind speed in the cold seasons, especially in winter. For most of the weather stations, no significant diurnal cycle in wind speed is visible. However, Cadzand (close to shore) and Vlissingen (on an embarkment), do show a diurnal pattern, especially in the warm seasons (spring and summer). At these stations, across all seasons, we observe a peak in wind speed in the afternoon. This could possibly be due to winds created by heating of the land during the day, causing thermal lows and turbulence, at night this forcing vanishes causing a drop in wind speed. On sea, the variability in temperature is smaller, as has been shown in Figure 3.3. In theory, plugging Figure 3.5 into a power curve would result in Figure 3.1. Due to the non-linearity of the power curve, large wind speed differences can result in big differences in load factor. Earlier was stated that at most stations, no diurnal pattern was visible. However, based on Figure 3.1, there probably is. If one really *tries* to find a diurnal pattern, one could argue that there is a very weak diurnal pattern in the warm seasons at the stations on the sea, as it has the same $-\sin(x)$ phase. A different explanation of the elevated load factor in the afternoon could be that the speed measurements at weather station height are not representative of the wind speeds at turbine height. A possible cause for this is the presence of low level jets, which are more common in the warm seasons (Section 1.3.2). To investigate this, a novel attempt for finding low level jet activity is presented in Section 3.4. One can try to find instances where production is relatively high for the measured wind speed.

Figure 3.4: Violin plots of seasonal and diurnal spread of wind direction. In gray the number of data points used for constructing the box plot is shown. Figure 2.1 and these numbers together have to make sense before comparing different violin plots.

Figure 3.5: Violin plots of seasonal and diurnal spread of wind speed. In gray the number of data points used for constructing the box plot is shown. Figure 2.1 and these numbers together have to make sense before comparing different violin plots.

To further investigate the relation between the meteorological variables and the resulting load factor, the load factor has been plotted against wind direction and wind speed in Figure 3.6. To associate 10 minutely wind speed and direction data with 15 minutely generation data, the wind measurements have been resampled using `pandas.resample("15 min").mean()`. Keep in mind that the weather stations are not at the same location and height as the turbines in the wind farms. This also results in a temporal shift. For example, when the wind speed at the farms increases the production increases accordingly, but the wind speed measured will not increase until the wind speed at the station location also increases. Figure 3.6 also contains a trend line which is calculated by binning the dots horizontally and then calculating the average value. Mathematically stated:

$$\text{Bins: } [b_i, b_{i+1}), \quad i = 0, \dots, N - 1 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} B_i &= \{(x_j, y_j) \mid b_i \leq x_j < b_{i+1}\} \\ x_i^* &= \frac{b_i + b_{i+1}}{2} \\ \bar{y}_i &= \frac{1}{|B_i|} \sum_{(x_j, y_j) \in B_i} y_j \end{cases} \Rightarrow \text{Trend line } :(x_i^*, \bar{y}_i) \quad (3.1)$$

For the trend line calculation in Figure 3.6, a bin count of $N = 30$ is used. For the calculations of the red numbers, two dimensional bin counts of 6×5 and 16×5 are used for the wind speed and wind direction plots respectively.

In addition to the trend lines and the red counts, meteorological data is fitted to common probability density distributions related to wind speed and direction. The shape of these distributions has already been hinted to in Figure 3.1, 3.4 and 3.5. The wind speed is often modelled using the *Weibull* distribution. The mathematical form for the Weibull distribution is

$$f(v|c, k) = \frac{k}{c} \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^{k-1} e^{-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^k} \quad \text{for } x \geq 0, \quad f(v|c, k) = 0 \text{ for } x < 0, \quad (3.2)$$

with the wind speed v , the shape parameter $k > 0$ and the scale parameter $c > 0$. The wind direction can be modelled using a *mixed von Mises* distribution [57], also known as a linear combination of circular normal distributions. A von Mises distribution in mathematical form is

$$g(\theta|\mu, \kappa) = \frac{e^{\kappa \cos(\theta - \mu)}}{2\pi I_0(\kappa)}, \quad (3.3)$$

where θ is the wind direction, μ is the mean value (centre of the ‘‘Gaussian’’), the concentration parameter κ (dictates how broad the spread is around its centre, large κ means less spread) and a zeroth order modified Bessel function for normalisation $I_0(\kappa)$. To get a mixed von Mises model, we take a linear combination of multiple of these distributions. This results in

$$p(\theta) = \sum_i w_i g(\theta|\mu_i, \kappa_i) \quad \text{with } \sum_i w_i = 1, \quad w_i \geq 0. \quad (3.4)$$

Using the `scipy.stats` and `scipy.optimize` modules, the parameters for these distributions are calculated and shown in Figure 3.6. These distributions could possibly be used to generate artificial data for model training purposes. For this, one could determine the distributions based on time of day and season, but this is beyond the scope of this study. For Figure 3.6, a mixture of two is used. However, one could argue that more are required since the histogram suggests that there are more peaks.

Figure 3.6 could be split into diurnal and seasonal blocks. These plots are shown in Section 3.4. It could be insightful to construct a trend line and do analysis of the wind speed and directions, analogous to in Figure 3.6. This could possibly give insights in wake effects and periodic cycles of these distributions. This has not been fully explored during this project.

Figure 3.6: Wind direction and wind speed plotted against the load factor of the entire wind farm. Trend lines are constructed by binning the data points horizontally.

3.3 Seasonal and diurnal patterns in ramp counts

In this section, the diurnal and seasonal distribution of energy ramp events are analysed. In this section we consider all the ramp events separate, overlap between types is possible. (Section 2.2).

1000 MW in 60 minutes - R100060

In Figure 3.7, the diurnal and seasonal distributions of ramps with a magnitude of at least 1000 MW and faster than 60 minutes are shown. In total, 151 ramp events occurred across 123 days. The colours in the heat plot are associated with the total number of ramps within that season and time block combination. During the time period considered in this study, more R100060 ramp-ups happened than ramp down. This is true for all seasons but autumn. Less ramps of this type occur in the early morning and the most take place between 20:00 and 00:00. Since the number of ramps considered is so low, one could question the quality of these trends.

Figure 3.7: Ramp counts with magnitude 1000 MW and a duration of 60 minutes.

1500 MW in 60 minutes - R150060

As can be seen in Table 2.4, Only 9 R150060 and 8 RD150060 occurred in the observed time range. Figure 3.8 shows the distribution of these ramp events. All of these ramp events are also R100060-type ramp events. These 17 ramp events took place across 16 days.

Figure 3.8: Ramp counts with magnitude 1500 MW and a duration of 60 minutes.

500 MW in 15 minutes - R50015

In Figure 3.9, the diurnal and seasonal patterns of R50015-type ramps are shown. In total, 155 ramp events of this type took place over 106 days. For this ramp type, there are roughly as many ramp-up as ramp-down events. Like the R100060-type ramps, in autumn ramp-downs seem to occur more than ramp-up events, with a contrast even stronger than for R100060 ramps. In the other seasons, ramp-down events occur more frequently, although with a weaker contrast than for R100060-type events. Diurnally, R50015-type ramps seem to be more evenly spread over the day than R100060-type events, although the same patterns as for R100060-type events can be recognised here. The same remark can be made here as for the other ramp events. The number of ramp events that happened in total is quite low for a proper distribution analysis. A suggestion of generating artificial ramps using fitted wind direction and speed distributions discussed at the end of Section 3 is presented in Section 6.4.

Figure 3.9: Ramp counts with magnitude 500 MW and a duration of 15 minutes.

1000 MW in 15 minutes - R100015

Only four ramp events with a size of a 1000 MW or higher in 15 minutes or less have occurred in the observing time range. All ramp events occurred on separate days. As can be seen in Figure 3.10, there are not enough events to suggest if a specific seasonal or specific pattern is present.

Figure 3.10: Ramp counts with magnitude 1000 MW and a duration of 15 minutes.

In Chapter 4, Section 4.2, the figures discussed in this section will be presented again, but with the classification results added.

3.4 Power curves for Borssele Alpha and Westhinder

This section will summarise all the findings of Chapter 3 in a series of figures for Borssele Alpha and Westhinder weather stations. Including all weather stations would not contribute to the explanation. In addition, this section presents the results of the novel approach for finding low level jets. In Figure 3.11 and Figure 3.12, the load factor of the entire cluster has been plotted against the (resampled) wind measurements of Borssele Alpha (light gray dots). Borssele alpha has been chosen since it has the shortest distance to the Belgian offshore cluster (~ 14 km to the center, Figure 1.3). These graphs are the same as those in Figure 3.6, but split into time blocks and seasons. The red numbers in the middle of each grid-square are the number of dots in that specific (direction, generation)- or (speed, generation)-range. These numbers can give insight in how the total production has been given the measured wind direction or speed. The cyan histogram is the distribution of observed wind directions. **The histograms have nothing to do with the load factor.** The black dashed lines are the trend lines made using Equation 3.1. In Figure 3.12 can be seen that in summer, there are less dots at the upper end of the plots than in winter. This is expected as, in general, the generation in summer is lower than in winter (Figure 3.1). The red number above each plot is the total number of data points plotted in each plot. This number has to be close between plots for them to be used in a comparison. This is where the Borssele Alpha weather station falls short, since it has less data points available during spring. As with Figure 3.6, the wind measurements are not the actual wind direction and speed at the turbine. Four main factors can introduce errors here:

1. There is a horizontal distance between the weather station and the wind farm cluster, wind turbines, and farms themselves, are spatially separated. This results in a more spread out plot (Section 1.1). This means that meteorological features can pass over the farms without, before or after passing over the weather stations. It is hard to correct for this effect. A hypothetical really fast moving feature travels at maybe at $60 \text{ km} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ (such as a cold front). To travel from Borssele Alpha to the farms, assuming its frontal boundary is perpendicular to the path between the cluster and Borssele Alpha, will take about 15 minutes. Depending on in which direction and how fast the meteorological feature travels, this can be longer or shorter.
2. There is a difference in what the timestamps mean between the generation datasets (it marks the begin of an interval) and the wind measurements (it marks the end of an interval). This will cause a temporal offset of 12.5 minutes. This is roughly as large as the error introduced by the horizontal distance discrepancy. Since the wind farm cluster is about 30 km by 10 km in size, this can get really complex. This has to be kept in mind when drawing any conclusions from these figures.
3. The production is dependent on wind speed at turbine height (~ 100 m). The wind speed used in this study is (reduced to, extrapolated to) 10 meters height. For Figures 3.11 and 3.12, the *actual* wind speed is not measured at 10 meters height. It is unclear at what height it is measured exactly, since there is conflicting information on at what height the sensor is at Borssele Alpha (Section 6.2, Appendix A). The extrapolation is done by KNMI assuming an exponential or logarithmic vertical wind profile. The wind direction is the direction measured at sensor height.
4. As discussed in Section 1.1, the wind speed can get affected significantly by the wake effect. Especially at Borssele Alpha, which is in the middle of the Dutch wind farm cluster. In Figure 3.6 or Figure 1.2b (which is also made with Borssele data), by comparing the production at low speeds. Borssele shows an extra “structure” of dots at these low speeds. These figures could possibly be used for looking at anomalous events. Events where the production is unusually high given a certain surface wind speed. This is where the novel approach for searching LLJ activity is based on.

Borssele Alpha - wdsensor10minavg - 2022-06-13 00:00:00 to 2025-03-09 22:45:00 (UTC)

Figure 3.11: Borssele Alpha wind direction plotted against production.

Borssele Alpha - ws10m10minavg - 2022-06-13 00:00:00 to 2025-03-09 22:45:00 (UTC)

Figure 3.12: Borssele Alpha wind speed plotted against production.

In these plots, the ramp event counts for the second way of grouping (`Only R100060`, `R100060` and `R50015` and `Only R50015`, Section 2.2) are shown. The coloured lines in Figures 3.11 and 3.12 are the paths of ramp events through the power curves, the corresponding (same coloured) number in the upper left of each plot is the number of unique ramp events (Section 2.2) in that specific season and time-of-day block. For example, 4 `Only RU100060`-type events of 1000 MW (or higher) in 60 minutes (or less) occurred between 20:00 to 24:00 in the summer. If no big dot at the beginning of the ramp path is shown, the ramp will have occurred across multiple hour blocks.

In Figure 3.11, the wind direction measured at Borssele Alpha is plotted against the load factor of the entire cluster. It can be seen that there are differences in wind directions preferable for high load factors. Across all seasons, we see that the highest production takes place for south to south west wind directions. In summer a clear separation is visible with almost no points in the south-east direction, in agreement with Figure 3.4. Ramp events with a somewhat vertical path are probably caused by features that did not have an effect on the wind directions.

In Figure 3.12, the wind speed measured at Borssele Alpha is plotted against the load factor of the entire cluster. From this plot it can be seen that most ramp events are signified by a change in wind speed in the non-linear part of the power curve. In the plot for autumn, between 12:00 and 16:00, a ramp-up due to a cut-out event is visible. The wind speed decreased which then caused the energy production to start again. Manual inspection of load factors corresponding to unusually low surface wind speeds did not lead to finding candidates for low level jets. In Appendix B, Figure B.1, the wind gust speed has been plotted against the production of the entire cluster. This plot has a similar structure as Figure 3.12.

Borssele Alpha does not have data for the full observation period. In Figure 3.14 and Figure 3.15, the power curves plots for Westhinder are shown. Westhinder is chosen for its similar distance to the shore as the wind farm cluster (Figure 1.3), although rather far away from the cluster (~ 40 km). For Westhinder, the data availability across different plots in the grid is similar, although Westhinder seems to have gaps in its measurements often whilst high wind speed events occur. Different from Borssele, Westhinder does not show an extra structure in the top left of the wind speed power curves in Figure 3.15. In Figure 3.13, the wind direction measured at the stations is plotted against the wind speed measured. Other than when plotting production data, these plots are not hindered by temporal and spatial differences. Comparing the left and right plots shows that the wind speed is generally lower at Borssele than at Westhinder. This could be due to wake effects or an incorrect conversion to 10 meters height by KNMI. We also see some gaps in the measured wind directions. This can also be seen in the histograms plotted in Figure 3.6. This could possibly due to the wake effect. In Appendix B, the wind gust speed plotted against the production of the entire cluster is shown.

Figure 3.13: Wind direction plotted against wind speed at the two weather stations (Borssele Alpha and Westhinder) considered in this section.

In this chapter, the diurnal and seasonal patterns of production, meteorological quantities and how they relate to ramping, have been discussed. In Chapter 4, the ramp events will be studied via time series.

Westhinder - wdsensor10minavg - 2021-01-01 00:00:00 to 2025-03-09 22:45:00 (UTC)

Figure 3.14: Westhinder wind direction plotted against production.

Westhinder - ws10m10minavg - 2021-01-01 00:00:00 to 2025-03-09 22:45:00 (UTC)

Figure 3.15: Westhinder wind speed plotted against production.

Chapter 4

Classification and case studies

This chapter contains case studies of some meteorological features that have caused a ramp event. These case studies are presented in Section 4.1. The type of procedure in this section has been carried out for all ramp events, but these analyses are not all presented in this work. Section 4.2 and Section 4.3 present the results of the classification task. Note that these are *likely* causes, but could be more complex.

4.1 Case studies

The following case contain some of the most extreme ramps that have occurred. These cases have been chosen to show how different meteorological features cause ramp events. Keep in mind that these cases could possibly be more complex than the dashboards might suggest. Unmarked red dashed lines in the graphs of the dashboard correspond to even larger slower ramp events (durations of 180 minutes).

4.1.0 Warm sector causing two 1500 MW ramps (2022-02-20)

On 2022-02-20, two large `RU150060`-type ramps occurred. A large extratropical cyclone caused a warm and a cold front to pass over the Belgian offshore cluster. The dashboard for the first ramp event that day is shown in Figure 4.2. Before the first ramp, a pre-frontal lull is observed, during which the wind speed drops significantly, almost simultaneously across all wind farms, indicating that the effect is rather large in scale. As the temperature rises, the wind speed follows as the wind farms enter the warm sector behind the warm front. First, the temperature rises at Westhinder, then at Wandelaar and then at Vlissingen. This is in agreement with the synoptic charts on how the feature moves across the North Sea. Interestingly, the relatively high pressure peak associated with the warm front is quite uncommon. After the first ramp, a very high wind speed is observed with a nearly constant wind direction and constant temperature. As the cold front comes closer, the isobars become even more compressed. This likely contributed to a further increase in wind speed, resulting in a partial cut-out event. The partial cut-out happened too slowly across all wind farms to cause a ramp-down event. Instead, it causes a ramp-up event as the wind speed slightly drops after the cold front has passed, and the farms start generating again. In Figure 4.1, the associated KNMI synoptic weather charts are shown for the second ramp. The cold front passage has typical cold front signature. A sudden drop in temperature, a dip in pressure and a clockwise change in wind direction. When comparing the rate at which the meteorological quantities change for the cold and warm frontal passage, one can see that a cold front travels faster than a warm front, this agrees with the theory discussed in Section 1.3. There were also frontal related thunderstorms that day. These did not cause any ramp events and are overshadowed by the synoptic scale events. This was quite a violent day for ramp events. Out of 9 `RU150060` ramps recorded in total (Section 3.3), two were on this day. The second ramp in particular is also classified as an `RD50015` and a double `RU50015`-type ramp, as can be seen from the coloured dots above the power generation time series. This storm was part of a sequence of storms, Storm Dudley (2022-02-16), Eunice (2022-02-18) and Franklin (2022-02-20). Together, accounting for 4 out of 5 frontal cut-outs.

Figure 4.1: The synoptic charts for the second cut-out ramp event on 2022-02-20. Images are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Figure 4.2: Dashboard for 2022-02-20. Warm sector causing two 1500 MW ramps. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

4.1.1 Low pressure core passage causing a 1500 MW ramp event (2023-01-16)

On 2023-01-16, a low pressure core passed over the Belgian offshore cluster. The dashboard of the ramp event is shown in Figure 4.3. As the feature went away, the production ramped-up significantly. The effects of the **L** passage can be seen in the time evolution of the meteorological variables. The pressure is at a minimum, as would be expected. The **L** core travels from SW to NE, as can be seen on the synoptic maps and from the order of which the weather stations are affected. Westhinder gets affected first. At 12:00, the **L** core has already passed Westhinder, but not yet over the other weather stations. This can be seen by looking at the wind directions or the arrows on the maps belonging to 12:00 and 18:00. The rather slow movement of the **L** core can also be seen by the moment the individual wind farms get affected. Mermaid reacts earlier than Norther does. In this case, the **L** core being over the wind farms and weather stations results in a decrease in wind speed (and production). This extratropical cyclone has a region of slow wind speeds at its core.

4.1.2 Storm Ciarán causing a 1500 MW ramp-down event (2023-11-02)

On 2023-11-02, a low pressure core passed right beside the Belgian offshore cluster. The dashboard for this event is shown in Figure 4.4. The **L** core passed in close vicinity to the cluster instead of directly over it (previous case study), this resulted in a very different outcome than the previous case study. The wind speed got so high that it caused a cut-out event. Note that before the cut-out, some decremental bid occurred. This means that Elia (TSO) asked the farms to reduce power. Storm Ciarán was also quite a slow moving feature, as can be seen from the wind direction plot in Figure 4.4. The pressure gradient was large enough to measure a significantly lower pressure at the offshore weather stations than in Vlissingen.

4.1.3 Unexplainable event (2023-02-26)

In Figure 4.5 the dashboard for 2023-02-26 is shown. A **H** pressure area is located above Scotland. The isobars are not really close to each other. No lightning discharges have been detected by KNMI that day. Despite not seeing any large synoptic feature passing over the wind farm cluster, a massive ramp of 1203 MW in 15 minutes time occurs. This event can be classified as an **R100060**, **R150060**, **R50015** and an **R50015**-type event. In the load factor plot, one can see that Mermaid gets affected first, whilst Northwester 2 stops producing as the rest of the farm ramp up. In the temperature graph, a slight drop in temperature is first noticed by Borssele, then by Wandelaar and then at Westhinder, meanwhile, the temperature at Vlissingen increases. This all happens *before* the ramp event occurs. Behind the wave of temperature change, we see a wave of wind speed change. This is first measured at Oosterschelde and about 30 minutes later at Borssele and Vlake van de Raan. As soon as this “feature” reaches the latter two weather stations, the ramp event begins. After the ramp, a quite long period of elevated generation has been observed, with a steady decrease during the day. Later in the day, a second ramp event occurs, this **R50015**-type event does not have a clear meteorological cause either. Appendix B lists all other unexplainable cases. One of which is somewhat similar to this event (2023-03-27, Figure B.3), although less violent.

4.1.4 Complex event (2023-11-10)

Sometimes, multiple meteorological features are present simultaneously. This can make the classification difficult. The dashboard shown in Figure 4.6 shows the meteorological situation before and after an **RD100060** and an **RU100060**-type ramp. Before the ramp events, the synoptic maps shows a trough aloft and a small weather system, meanwhile after the ramp events, an occluded front and a trough aloft at the same location as before is present. Before the ramp events occur, the wind direction has already shifted at some weather stations, These wind shifts coincide exactly with decreases in wind speed and temperature decreases. This could be a mixture of the effects of a frontal passage, pre- or post-frontal convection and even due to the passage of a low pressure area.

Figure 4.3: Dashboard for 2023-01-16. Low pressure core passage causing a 1500 MW ramp event. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Figure 4.4: Dashboard for 2023-11-02. Storm Ciarán causing a 1500 MW ramp-down event. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work. Interactive buttons intentionally left in.

Figure 4.5: Dashboard for 2023-02-26. Unexplainable event. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Figure 4.6: Dashboard for 2023-11-10. Complex event. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

4.1.5 Prefrontal convection - thunderstorm zone (2023-06-20)

In Figure 4.7 the dashboard is shown for a structured thunderstorm related to a weather front. This meteorological event coincides with a sudden spike in production. A lot of lightning discharges were detected that day. The pressure measurements show a wiggle with bumps, this is a signature for thunderstorm activity. This could be linked to the passage of a down and updraft region. Westhinder gets affected first, then Wandelaar and Borssele, and finally Vlissingen. This order holds true for the other meteorological measurements. The line of thunderstorms is associated with a rapid decrease in temperature, accompanied by a sudden increase in wind speed, as can be seen in the wind speed and wind gust speed plots. Not all farms are affected equally. In plot **B**, one can see that only the closest farms to the shore are affected in a significant way (Norther, Thorntonbank NE, Rentel). Meanwhile, Mermaid and Northwester 2 are barely affected at all.

4.1.6 Typical warm frontal passage (2025-01-05, Storm Floriane)

In Figure 4.8, the dashboard for a typical warm frontal passage is shown. From the SW direction, the temperature increases steadily. This is first noticed at Westhinder, then at Wandelaar, and finally at Borssele and Vlissingen. With this passage, we get a clockwise wind direction change. This is typical for passing weather fronts. In general, this clockwise wind direction is often only clearly noticeable with cold fronts, but this warm front seems to be strong enough to have a significant effect on how the isobars curve. An interesting thing that remains unexplained is that the wind speed at Westhinder and Borssele gets affected quite a bit more than the other weather stations. This passage coincides with an `R100060`-type ramp event, resulting in a prolonged period of high generation. However, this is not always the case. Note that here, different than in Figure 4.2 (2022-02-22 case study), the cold front does not seem to have any effect on the meteorological variables nor the production, even though the cold front passes over the area between 18:00 and 24:00.

4.1.7 Prefrontal convection - convergence line (2024-04-08, Storm Pierrick)

In Figure 4.9, the dashboard for 2024-04-08 is shown. The passage of a convergence line ahead of a cold front coincides with a fast but small `R50015`-type ramp. This convergence line is part of the storm Pierrick. Similar to the case study on 2023-06-20, Figure 4.7, bumps in the pressure signature can be seen. These bumps coincide with the moment the temperature drops suddenly. First, a local elevation of pressure is measured at Wandelaar and later at Vlissingen. Meanwhile, Borssele and Westhinder do not show this increase in pressure. This might be because some stations are in updraft or downdraft regions, whilst others are not. In terms of wind measurements, first a sudden temporary wind direction change is measured at Wandelaar, then at Vlake van de Raan and Cadzand, the wind direction between different stations does not follow the same evolution as the wind speed measurements do. This reflects the localised nature of the thunderstorms in this convergence line. In terms of production data, not all farms respond at the same time. Northwester 2 in particular does not have a clear spike.

4.1.8 Ramp down likely caused by frontal passage (2024-08-20)

As has been alluded to before, there is no clear correspondence between certain types of fronts, if they are approaching or leaving the area, and their effect on ramping. Figure 4.10 is an example of a frontal passage that is followed by a 3 hour period of lowered power generation. As the cold front leaves the area, production increases again. This feature is a large scale effect, as can be seen by the tightly packed load factor curves of the individual farms all responding in a similar manner. The cold front comes in from the west, as can be seen by the order in which the weather stations and wind farms graphs change. However, this cold front is quite slow moving and does not have a large temperature contrast; the typical temperature drop one would expect from a cold front is absent here.

Figure 4.7: Dashboard for 2023-06-20. Prefrontal convection - thunderstorm zone. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Figure 4.8: Dashboard for 2025-01-05. Typical warm frontal passage. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Figure 4.9: Dashboard for 2024-04-08. Prefrontal convection - convergence line. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Figure 4.10: Dashboard for 2024-08-20. Ramp down likely caused by frontal passage. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

4.1.9 Non-frontal convection - thunderstorm (2021-07-27)

In Figure 4.12, an example of a non-frontal zone of convection is shown. On 2021-07-27, an isolated trough aloft passed over the wind farm cluster according to the synoptic weather charts. This trough aloft coincides with an `RU100060` and an `RU50015`-type ramp event at 7:00. All farms have an increase in production, except for Northwester 2. A lot of lightning discharges were detected along the Dutch coastline. In addition, the is ramp accompanied by fluctuating temperature measurements at different weather stations. In terms of wind measurements, we see that Westhinder and Wandelaar do not have data available for the entire duration of the elevated production period, as is often the case. Of the stations that have data available, Vlakte van de Raan shows an increase in wind and wind gust speed first, followed by Cadzand and later Oosterschelde. The pressure graph does not show bumps as clear as the other case studies involving thunderstorms. Later in the day, at 13:15, another `RU50015`-type ramp event occurs. This time there is a significant difference in how the individual wind farms react. Mermaid has its peak 60 minutes later than Norther and Thorntonbank SW. The synoptic situation for the second ramp event is shown in Figure 4.11. The figure shows that yet another trough aloft passes over the area. In Figure 4.12, one can see quite a large temperature fluctuation during this ramp event. This second trough is accompanied by a less significant wind speed increase, and thus resulted in a less extreme ramp event than the first one.

4.1.10 Unexplainable event (2023-09-28)

In Figure 4.13, the dashboard is shown for 2023-09-28. On this day, an `RD50015`-type ramp occurred at 15:00. Before and after the ramp, there were no synoptic meteorological features passing through the area, according to the synoptic weather charts at the bottom of the dashboard. Also no thunderstorm discharges were detected that day. At the time of the ramp event, we see a sequence of events happening in the wind direction plot. First, Wandelaar measures a slight shift in wind direction towards the west, then Vlakte van de Raan measures the same shift slightly later. Cadzand observes a sudden peak in the same direction for approximately half an hour. The wind speed measured at these stations shift in the same order, except that Cadzand measures a slight dip in wind speed, whilst the others measure an increase. What really happened here cannot be explained by the dashboard. Maybe the slight shift to a westerly wind is caused by a sea breeze, but this can only be confirmed by further analysing this ramp event.

4.1.11 Post frontal relaxation (2025-01-01)

On 2025-01-01 a textbook example of post frontal relaxation occurred. The dashboard for this event is shown in Figure 4.14. Before any ramp events occur, the wind speed is quite high, probably just shy of the cut-out speed $v_{cut-out}$. At 15:00, a cold front passes over the area. As can be seen on the dashboard, the isobars are quite compressed ahead of the frontal boundary, whilst behind the frontal boundary, pressure gradient seems quite shallow. This is an example of post frontal relaxation. At 15:00, the wind direction rotates clockwise, the pressure reaches a minimum and the temperature drops, as is typical for a cold frontal passage. In addition, a large drop in wind speed is observed. However, the wind speed is still high enough for any ramp events to happen. Around 23:00, an occluded front passes, again signified by a clockwise rotation of wind direction, but this front has no significant effect on temperature and pressure. Behind the occluded front, the isobars are even more spread out. This causes the wind speed to drop into the non-linear part of the power curve (Figure 1.2a), which results in an `RD100060`-type ramp event.

Figure 4.11: The synoptic charts for the second `RU50015`-type ramp event on 2021-07-27. Images are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Figure 4.12: Dashboard for 2021-07-27. Non-frontal convection - thunderstorm. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Figure 4.13: Dashboard for 2023-09-28. Unexplainable event, and my birthday. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Figure 4.14: Dashboard for 2025-01-01. Post frontal relaxation. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

4.2 Classification results - separate ramp types

In this section, the result of the classification task is presented. The class definitions are listed in Section 1.4. The information presented has some overlap with Figures 3.7, 3.8, 3.9, 3.10. It contains counts of which meteorological feature likely was the cause of the occurred ramp events. These (likely) causes will be referred to as *ramp drivers*. For Figures 4.15, 4.18, 4.19, 4.22, the area of the rectangles in the heat plot (lower left) are proportional to the counts of ramp drivers that occurred in that specific season and time of day block. The areas are not supposed to be compared between different season and time block squares. In contrast, the areas of the rectangles in the barplots (upper left and lower right) can be compared between different time blocks and seasons. The table in the upper left contains the counts and fraction of synoptic and mesoscale ramp drivers.

Change of 1000 MW or more in 60 minutes or less - R100060

a change under ± 1500 MW. All other non-frontal convection ramp drivers took at most 75 minutes. For the unknown, presumably mesoscale effects (gray), one 105 minute ramp with a magnitude of ~ 1700 MW has been observed (upper right). This is the ramp event discussed in the 2023-02-26 case study.

Figure 4.17: R100060-type ramp event spread and duration per ramp driver. The box plots have a vertical offset, the coloured dots are the actual values of ramp magnitudes and duration.

In Table 4.2, the number and fraction of occurrences of each ramp driver is shown. This table also includes counts and fractions from the other thresholds considered in this study.

Change of 1500 MW or more in 60 minutes or less - R150060

Figure 4.18: Ramp driver distribution grouped by season and time of day block for R150060-type ramps. Columns with U are ramp-up counts and D are ramp-down counts.

In Figure 4.18, the result of the classification task for R150060-type ramp events is shown. All these ramp events are extreme cases of R100060-type events. Two out of six R100060 cut-outs (Figure 4.15) are also of this type. Both of these cut-out events are discussed as case studies (2022-02-20 and 2023-11-02). One unknown mesoscale effect has been classified. This is the the event discussed in the 2026-2-26 case study (Figure 4.5).

Change of 500 MW or more in 15 minutes or less - R50015

Figure 4.19: Ramp driver distribution grouped by season and time of day block for R50015-type ramps. Columns with U are ramp-up counts and D are ramp-down counts.

Figure 4.21: R50015-type ramp event spread and duration per ramp driver. The box plots have a vertical offset, the coloured dots are the actual values of ramp magnitudes and duration.

In Figure 4.21, the spread in ramp magnitude and duration is shown for the different ramp drivers for R50015-type ramp events. Many of these events coincide with the R100060-type events, but only the part with the largest rate of change. The most extreme cases are classified as R100015-type ramps. No R50015-type ramp event has been associated with a change larger than ± 1500 MW. The largest ramp-down for this type is an unknown ramp driver that occurred on 2023-03-27. The dashboard for this event is shown in Figure B.3 in Appendix B, with a meteorological situation somewhat similar to case study 2023-02-26.

Change of 1000 MW or more in 15 minutes or less - R100015

Figure 4.22: Ramp driver distribution grouped by season and time of day block for R100015-type ramps. Columns with U are ramp-up counts and D are ramp-down counts.

In Figure 4.22, the results of the classification task for `R100015`-type ramps is presented. These are very fast ramps. All `R100015`-type ramps are also `R100060` and `R50015`-type ramps. None of the `R100015` ramps were classified as cut-out events. All four ramp events of this type are listed in Table 4.1. Again, the case study of 2023-02-26 is present.

Start datetime	Ramp driver	Ramp magnitude
2022-04-02 5:45:00	Non-frontal convection (meso)	-1142.34
2022-09-06 19:15:00	Frontal related (syn)	1284.68
2023-02-26 3:00:00	Unknown (meso)	1203.23
2023-11-09 13:45:00	Frontal related (syn)	-1213.57

Table 4.1: All `R100015`-type ramp events.

Summary for separate ramp types

In the table below, counts and fractions of the classified ramp drivers are shown. It summarises the numbers found and discussed in Figure 4.15 and Figure 4.19, omitting the diurnal and seasonal variation. To reiterate, most ramp events are associated with frontal related features (44% for `R100060` and 32% for `R50015`). The second most common likely cause is pre- or post-frontal convection (21% for `R100060` and 27% for `R50015`). `R100060`-type events are more often associated with **L** passages (14%) than `R50015`-type events (8%). `R50015`-type ramp events are more often associated with non-frontal convection and unknown ramp drivers (15% and 12% respectively) than `R100060`-type events (11% and 4%). In the following tables, slightly shorter names for all ramp drivers have been used. This is intentional for preserving space.

Ramp driver	R100060			R50015		
	Ramp-up	Ramp-down	Total	Ramp-up	Ramp-down	Total
L passage	13 (0.15)	8 (0.12)	21 (0.14)	9 (0.12)	3 (0.04)	12 (0.08)
L cut-out	2 (0.02)	1 (0.02)	3 (0.02)	2 (0.03)	2 (0.03)	4 (0.03)
Frontal related	36 (0.42)	31 (0.48)	67 (0.44)	23 (0.30)	27 (0.35)	50 (0.32)
Frontal cut-out	2 (0.02)	1 (0.02)	3 (0.02)	1 (0.01)	3 (0.04)	4 (0.03)
Complex (syn)	2 (0.02)	1 (0.02)	3 (0.02)	0	0	0
Frontal convection	20 (0.23)	12 (0.18)	32 (0.21)	24 (0.31)	18 (0.23)	42 (0.27)
Non-frontal convection	6 (0.07)	10 (0.15)	16 (0.11)	10 (0.13)	14 (0.18)	24 (0.15)
Unknown (meso)	5 (0.06)	1 (0.02)	6 (0.04)	8 (0.10)	11 (0.14)	19 (0.12)
Total	86 (0.57)	65 (0.43)	151	77 (0.50)	78 (0.50)	155

Table 4.2: Number of occurrences of each meteorological ramp driver for `R100060` (left) and `R50015`-type events (right). The number in the parenthesis are fractions of the total number of ramp-ups, ramp-down and total number of ramp events.

4.3 Classification results - ramp types combined

Some of the ramp events (84 events) are fast and long events. These events are classified both as an `R100060` and an `R50015`-type event. Table 4.3 shows the number of ramp events when these overlapping ramp types are separated into an additional ramp type. This table allows us to distinguish between slow large ramps (`Only R100060`), fast large ramps (`R100060 and R50015`) and fast small ramps (`Only R50015`). As before, the most prominent ramp drivers are frontal related and pre- or post-frontal convection. For slow large ramps (`Only R100060`) 54% of ramps are directly related to frontal passages but only 15% are likely caused by pre- or post-frontal convection. For fast large ramps (`R100060 and R50015`), 37% of all ramps are associated with frontal passages but 26% are associated with pre- or post-frontal convection. In other words, for fast large ramps the indirect effects of a frontal passage matter more than for a slow large duration ramp. This division between direct and indirect effects from frontal passages is even more evenly distributed for fast small ramps (`Only R50015`). This ramp type is associated with the direct consequences of a frontal passage 27% of the time (pre-frontal lull, post-frontal relaxation, isobar compression

ahead or behind the frontal boundary) and also 27% of the time associated with indirect frontal causes, i.e. pre- or post-frontal convection (convergence lines ahead thunderstorm zones ahead or troughs trailing behind the frontal boundary). Frontal cut-outs have occurred for all of the three ramp types. In contrast, cut-out events likely caused by the passage of low pressure cores seem to be associated with faster ramps. Keep in mind that the number of cut-out events is quite low. This prevents us from making a general statement for the occurrence of these ramp drivers. Non-cut-out events associated with passages of low pressure cores seem to cause longer duration ramp events (Only R100060 15%, R100060 and R50015 13% and Only R50015 1%). The raw classification results are listed at the end of Appendix A.5.

As for mesoscale ramp drivers, Only R100060-type events are associated significantly less with non-frontal convection (7%) than R100060 and R50015 (13%) and Only R50015 (19%) events are. For unknown ramp drivers only 3% of ramp drivers that were associated with an Only R100060 type event were classified as unknown. R100060 and R50015 has an unknown cause for 5% of the time. Meanwhile, Only R50015 has significantly higher percentage of unknown causes, with 21%. Keep in mind that Table 4.3 has its fractions normalised to a specific ramp type (Only RU100060, Only RD100060, RU100060 and RU50015,...). These percentages indicate the number of times a given ramp type had a certain ramp driver as its likely cause, *not* the other way around, then the fractions summed over different columns would give 1. This is shown in Table 4.4. In Table 4.5, the fractions are normalised by the total number of unique ramp events (221) that happened in the observing time range.

Ramp driver	Only R100060			R100060 and R50015			Only R50015		
	RU	RD	Total	RU	RD	Total	RU	RD	Total
L passage	5 (0.13)	5 (0.18)	10 (0.15)	8 (0.17)	3 (0.08)	11 (0.13)	1 (0.03)		1 (0.01)
L cut-out				2 (0.04)	1 (0.03)	3 (0.04)		1 (0.03)	1 (0.01)
Frontal related	20 (0.51)	16 (0.57)	36 (0.54)	16 (0.34)	15 (0.41)	31 (0.37)	7 (0.23)	12 (0.30)	19 (0.27)
Frontal cut-out	1 (0.03)		1 (0.01)	1 (0.02)	1 (0.03)	2 (0.02)		2 (0.05)	2 (0.03)
Complex (syn)	2 (0.05)	1 (0.04)	3 (0.04)						
Frontal convection	7 (0.18)	3 (0.11)	10 (0.15)	13 (0.28)	9 (0.24)	22 (0.26)	11 (0.37)	8 (0.20)	19 (0.27)
Non-frontal convection	2 (0.05)	3 (0.11)	5 (0.07)	4 (0.09)	7 (0.19)	11 (0.13)	6 (0.20)	7 (0.17)	13 (0.19)
Unknown (meso)	2 (0.05)		2 (0.03)	3 (0.06)	1 (0.03)	4 (0.05)	5 (0.17)	10 (0.25)	15 (0.21)
Total	39 (0.18)	28 (0.13)	67 (0.30)	47 (0.21)	37 (0.17)	84 (0.38)	30 (0.14)	40 (0.18)	70 (0.32)

Table 4.3: Number of occurrences of each meteorological ramp driver for Only R100060 (left), R100060 and R50015 (center) and Only R50015-type events (right). The number in the parenthesis are fractions of the total number of ramp-ups, ramp down, and total number of ramp events of that type. The percentage of a certain likely cause given the ramp type. This table is essentially the same table as Table 4.2, but with the overlap in ramp type separated. All fractions summed in every column add up to 1. The last total row has fractions that do sum up to one. For example, 18% of all ramps was an Only RU100060-type ramp event.

Ramp driver	Only R100060			R100060 and R50015			Only R50015		
	RU	RD	Total	RU	RD	Total	RU	RD	Total
L passage	0.23	0.23	0.45	0.36	0.14	0.5	0.05	0.0	0.05
L cut-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.25	0.75	0.0	0.25	0.25
Frontal related	0.23	0.19	0.42	0.19	0.17	0.36	0.08	0.14	0.22
Frontal cut-out	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.0	0.4	0.4
Complex (syn)	0.67	0.33	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Frontal convection	0.14	0.06	0.2	0.25	0.18	0.43	0.22	0.16	0.37
Non-frontal convection	0.07	0.1	0.17	0.14	0.24	0.38	0.21	0.24	0.45
Unknown (meso)	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.14	0.05	0.19	0.24	0.48	0.71

Table 4.4: Fractions normalised to number of ramp driver occurrences. In contrast to Table 4.3, the numbers represent the fraction of times a certain ramp type (Only RU100060...) associated with a given ramp driver (such as a L passage). Rows sum up to 1.

Ramp driver	Only R100060			R100060 and R50015			Only R50015			TOTAL
	RU	RD	Total	RU	RD	Total	RU	RD	Total	
Counts										
L passage	5	5	10	8	3	11	1	0	1	22
L cut-out	0	0	0	2	1	3	0	1	1	4
Frontal related	20	16	36	16	15	31	7	12	19	86
Frontal cut-out	1	0	1	1	1	2	0	2	2	5
Complex (syn)	2	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Frontal convection	7	3	10	13	9	22	11	8	19	51
Non-frontal convection	2	3	5	4	7	11	6	7	13	29
Unknown (meso)	2	0	2	3	1	4	5	10	15	21
Total	39	28	67	47	37	84	30	40	70	221
Fractions										
L passage	0.023	0.023	0.045	0.036	0.014	0.05	0.005	0.0	0.005	0.10
L cut-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.009	0.005	0.014	0.0	0.005	0.005	0.018
Frontal related	0.09	0.072	0.163	0.072	0.068	0.14	0.032	0.054	0.086	0.389
Frontal cut-out	0.005	0.0	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.009	0.0	0.009	0.009	0.023
Complex (syn)	0.009	0.005	0.014	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.014
Frontal convection	0.032	0.014	0.045	0.059	0.041	0.1	0.05	0.036	0.086	0.231
Non-frontal convection	0.009	0.014	0.023	0.018	0.032	0.05	0.027	0.032	0.059	0.131
Unknown (meso)	0.009	0.0	0.009	0.014	0.005	0.018	0.023	0.045	0.068	0.095
Total	0.176	0.127	0.303	0.213	0.167	0.38	0.136	0.181	0.317	1.0

Table 4.5: Fraction and number (counts) of occurrences of each meteorological ramp driver for Only R100060 (left), R100060 and R50015 (center) and Only R50015 -type events (right). The numbers are fractions of the total number of ramp events. This table is essentially the same table as Table 4.3, but with fractions that sum up in total to 1.

Figure 4.23, Figure 4.24 and Figure 4.25 show the diurnal and seasonal patterns for Only R100060, R100060 and R50015 and Only R50015 respectively. These figures contain the same information as the tables above. In the upper right tables of the figures, one can see the division between synoptic ramp drivers and mesoscale rampdrivers. Note that pre-/post-frontal convection is counted as synoptic, since they are indirectly associated with a frontal passage. This definition is a point of discussion. The combined counts of all the unique ramp events are shown in Figure 4.26.

Figure 4.23: Ramp driver distribution grouped by season and time of day block for Only R100060 -type ramps. Columns with U are ramp-up counts and D are ramp-down counts

Figure 4.24: Ramp driver distribution grouped by season and time of day block for R100060 and R50015-type ramps. Columns with U are ramp-up counts and D are ramp-down counts

Figure 4.25: Ramp driver distribution grouped by season and time of day block for Only R50015-type ramps. Columns with U are ramp-up counts and D are ramp-down counts.

Figure 4.26: Ramp driver distribution grouped by season and time of day block for all unique ramp events. Columns with U are ramp-up counts and D are ramp-down counts.

In Table 4.6, the main results of the classification task are summarised. In this table, the ramp duration and ramp size (production change) of all `Only R100060`, `R100060 and R50015` and `Only R50015`-type events have been retrieved from the generation time series. Using the actual effect of the ramp-event instead of the criteria, we can combine these types to get insight in the relation between ramp duration and ramp size (somewhat of a combination of Figures 4.17, 4.21). This relation is shown in Figure 4.27. From the least squares linear fits can be seen that for both ramp-up and ramp-down events the duration of the ramp event increases as the size of the ramp increases. Synoptic scale ramp drivers are associated with the largest changes in production (L-passage, frontal related and complex). Pre-/Post-frontal convection likely causes ever so slightly shorter duration ramp events (shorter ramp-up events, similar length ramp-down events as frontal related causes). Non-frontal and unknown (presumably mesoscale) ramp drivers are even

shorter. From Table 4.6 can be seen that some of the error bars are calculated using a very small number of data points, this has to be kept in mind. Interestingly, the slopes and coefficients of determination of both fits are quite similar:

$$\text{Ramp-up events: } t_{\text{dur}} = 0.07495 \cdot \Delta P - 22.09, \quad R^2 = 0.8473 \quad (4.1)$$

$$\text{Ramp-down events: } t_{\text{dur}} = -0.07507 \cdot \Delta P - 24.50, \quad R^2 = 0.8508 \quad (4.2)$$

Ramp driver	#RU	#RD	#R	RU duration (minutes)	RD duration (minutes)	R duration (minutes)	RU size (MW)	RD size (MW)
L passage	14	8	22	75±24	82±14	78±21	1299±372	-1359±277
L cut-out	2	2	4	75±0	60±64	68±38	1215±100	-1202±867
Frontal related	43	43	86	67±27	57±29	62±28	1173±357	-1043±358
Frontal cut-out	2	3	5	75±21	40±43	54±38	1152±67	-923±615
Complex (syn)	2	1	3	75±21	75±0	75±15	1384±507	-1425±0
Frontal convection	31	20	51	50±27	52±34	51±30	948±291	-1044±399
Non-frontal convection	12	17	29	42±30	48±29	46±29	919±251	-966±348
Unknown (meso)	10	11	21	48±36	22±18	34±30	972±435	-725±300
Total counts and averages	116	105	221	60±30	53±33	56±31	1088±365	-1025±405

Table 4.6: Number of unique ramp-up and down events, average ramp event duration (in minutes) and average ramp event size (in MW), grouped by ramp driver. The values in the last row below the counts, denoted with '#', are totals. The numbers below the ramp durations and size are average values. The error is the standard deviation, and the combined error in the weighted mean error propagation (Equation 4.3).

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum n_i \mu_i}{\sum n_i}, \quad \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum n_i (\sigma_i^2 + \mu_i^2)}{\sum n_i} - \bar{x}^2} \quad (4.3)$$

Figure 4.27: Ramp event size versus ramp event duration for all unique ramp events (Only R100060, R100060 and R50015 and Only R50015). The coloured dots are ramp events associated with a certain ramp driver. A slight vertical jitter has been added to illustrate the distribution of points, their actual duration is always a multiple of 15 minutes. For every ramp driver, the average duration and size (production change) of the associated ramp event is plotted. A least squares fit for all unique ramp-up (gray, dashed) and all ramp-down (black, dashed) is plotted.

Chapter 5

Hypothetical wind farm clusters

In this chapter, the results are presented on the evolution of ramp statistics as a wind farm cluster grows in size. Smaller clusters are modelled as subsets of the farms of the real Belgian offshore cluster. For this chapter, only the latter way of grouping ramp types discussed in Section 2.2 is used, as has been discussed in Section 2.5. Recall that *slow large* ramps are denoted by `R_0.442_60` (the proportionally scaled version of `Only R100060`-type ramps), *fast large* ramps are `R_0.221_15+R_0.442_60` (the proportionally scaled version of `R100060` and `R50015`-type ramps) and *fast small* ramps are `R_0.221_15` (the proportionally scaled version of `Only R50015`-type ramps).

Figure 5.1: Ramp counts for every hypothetical cluster, clusters are ordered from smallest to largest.

In Figure 5.1, the number of each ramp type that occurred during the entire observing time range has been computed for every of the 1023 hypothetical clusters. From the figure one can see that the total number of ramp events that occur seems to decrease with cluster size. The fast small ramps (purple and brown) decrease the fastest. The fast large ramps (red and green) also see a decrease for an increasing cluster size. Slow large ramp occurrences (blue and orange) do not decrease significantly.

Figure 5.2: Ramp counts plotted on a semi-log plot.

Note that the powerset of all possible clusters contains much more clusters with installed capacities around 1000 MW than clusters with an installed capacity at the lower and upper end of the spectrum. Figure 5.2 is the same plot as Figure 5.1, but with a logarithmic scale to examine if the relation between ramp occurrence and cluster size can be modelled by an exponential function. An exponential function becomes a straight line when plotted on a (vertical) semi-log plot. Consider an exponential function f described by

$$f(x) = g^{ax+b}. \text{ Taking the } \log_{10} \text{ of both sides results in } \log_{10}(g^{ax+b}) = (ax + b) \log_{10}(g). \quad (5.1)$$

Inspection of Figure 5.2 shows that the relation between the number of ramp events and the cluster size might be slightly convex, suggesting that the relation is sub-exponential, which means the relation decreases more slowly than exponentially. Although the linear fits do not model the log-relation correctly, it can still be seen that the sensitivity to faster ramps gets affected more than the sensitivity to slower ramps as the cluster increases in size. Ramp-up and ramp-down events within each ramp type behave quite similar. Across all clusters and for all ramp types, there are often more ramp-up events than ramp-down events.

Figure 5.3: In the upper plot, the same information is plotted as in Figure 5.1, but as a stacked plot to illustrate how the absolute number of ramps change as the cluster increases in size. The peak for very small clusters is cut off for clarity. In the lower plot, the number of ramp events from each ramp type as a fraction of the total number of ramps, similar to a market share graph.

In Figure 5.3, the share of each ramp type to the total number of ramp events is shown. In the upper plot, one can see that slow large ramps occurrence (blue and orange) do not change significantly with cluster size, however, their relative occurrence does increase. In contrast, fast small ramps (purple and brown) occur less when the cluster grows in size, both in a relative and an absolute sense. Fast large ramp occurrence decreases in an absolute sense but stays roughly constant in a relative sense.

In Figure 5.4, the average duration of each ramp type is computed over the entire observing time range for all hypothetical clusters. The average ramp duration of fast large ramps increases the most as the cluster increases in size. Fast small ramps (`R_0.221_15`) do not have a large spread in duration, because when two happened consecutively, it is automatically a `R_0.221_15+R_0.442_60`-type event. It is interesting that there still is a spread around the purple and brown lines for some hypothetical clusters.

Figure 5.5 shows the fraction of the total time that the cluster is in a ramp event. In the scientific literature, this measure is often used to talk about how often ramp events occur. As with the number of ramp events that occur (Figure 5.1), the fraction of the time that the cluster is ramping decreases as the cluster increases in size. The decrease in ramp occurrence and fraction of time in a ramp event slows down as the cluster grows in size. The slow large ramps occurrences (and ramping time fraction) change significantly with cluster size.

Analogous to the vertical semi-log plot for the ramp counts, a semi-log plot for the this measure is shown in Figure 5.6. The fraction of the time that the cluster is ramping decreases the most for short small ramps (purple and brown).

Figure 5.6: The fraction of the time that the cluster is enduring a ramp event. Plotted with a logarithmic vertical axis.

Figure 5.7: The average time between ramp events of each ramp type.

In Figure 5.7, the mean time between ramp events is plotted against the hypothetical cluster size. For all ramp types, the time in between ramps seems to increase. Especially for fast (small and large) ramps. This is in line with the other figures; if these types of ramps occur less, the time in between them will increase.

Figure 5.8 shows the average ramp size in terms of the load factor of each ramp type for all different clusters. One can see that these stay quite constant for an increasing cluster size. Note that fast large ramp events (green and red) are often larger than slow large ramp events.

In Figure 5.9, the average ramp size in an absolute sense is plotted. It is the data plotted in Figure 5.8, but multiplied by the installed capacity of each cluster. Since the load factors in Figure 5.8 are nearly constant, the lines in this plot become increasing (or decreasing for ramp-down event) straight lines as the cluster grows. This is to be expected, since a ramp event in a larger cluster results in a larger production change. Figure 5.10 shows the product between the ramp occurrence (Figure 5.1) and ramp size (Figure 5.9). This figure captures the effects of both the larger power swings and the change in ramp event occurrence on the electricity grid. From this figure, it can be seen that the total effect of fast short ramps is decreasing and the total effect of large (especially slow) ramps is increasing, as the cluster size increases. Note that “Total ramp energy” is not a real physical quantity, but some sort of *severity index*.

Figure 5.8: Average ramp size plotted against hypothetical cluster size in terms of load factor. The shaded area corresponds to the standard deviation computed over the entire time range.

Figure 5.9: Average absolute ramp size plotted against hypothetical cluster size. The shaded area corresponds to the standard deviation computed over the entire time range.

Figure 5.10: A severity index as the product between ramp occurrence and average ramp size as a measure of the total effect on the electricity grid of a ramp type.

Chapter 6

Discussion and conclusion

This chapter discusses the findings and results of this study and their implications. This chapter is divided into four main parts, in Section 6.1 the result of the approaches that aim to address the research questions in Section 1.4 are discussed. Section 6.2 discusses the limitations of the approaches used in this study, such as suboptimal meteorological data that has been used and the methodological limitations. Section 6.3 follows up on these limitations by outlining improvements on the methods that have been used. In addition, it contains suggestions for a few other applications these methods could be used for, that are not explicitly discussed in this work. Section 6.4 contains some more general suggestions for future research that came up during this study. In addition, it contains some open questions.

6.1 Findings and implications

This section addresses the questions posed in Section 1.4. It also reflects on how the results relate to finding from other studies in the field.

6.1.1 Discussion on diurnal, seasonal and spatial patterns in production and ramping

Recall the question formulated in Section 1.4 this part of this work aims to address:

How do power generation and meteorological variables differ between seasons and time of day, and how does this relate to ramp events?

In Chapter 3, the diurnal and seasonal cycle of production and meteorological variables in the region of the Belgian offshore wind farm cluster is presented. In Figure 3.1 can be seen that in the warm seasons a clear diurnal cycle is visible, with a production peak at 16:00-20:00. This is in line with what previous studies found [20] (also at the Belgian offshore cluster). In Figure 3.3, one can see that only in the warm seasons, the temperature is sometimes higher on average than the sea water temperature (and the air temperature above sea level). This could give rise to land-sea breezes. The air temperature difference between Westhinder and Vlissingen is larger during the day. This could mean that sea breezes during the day may be stronger than land breezes during the night. This could explain the slight shift in mean wind direction measured at some of the weather stations shown in Figure 3.4, as in the warm seasons Vlissingen and Cadzand measure a more westerly flow during the midday than Westhinder does (on average). From Figure 3.4 follows that the wind speed on average is around $8-10 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. This is exactly in the non-linear part of the power curve, making ramp events a common phenomenon. This is underlined by the power curve plots with paths of ramp events Figures 3.12 and 3.15.

The ramp events defined in Chapter 3 have been further split into slow large ramp events (`Only R100060`), fast large ramp events (`R100060 and R50015`) and fast small ramp events (`Only R50015`). The diurnal and seasonal patterns are shown in Figures 4.23, 4.24 and 4.25. The combined counts of all the unique ramp events are shown in Figure 4.26. In winter, roughly the same number of ramp-up and ramp-down event occur. In spring and summer, more ramp-up event occur. In autumn, more ramp-down events occur than ramp-up events. Diurnally, we observe more ramp events in the late evening (20:00-24:00). Overall, the seasonal and diurnal ramp event counts differ quite a bit from the findings of a previous study on the Belgian offshore cluster ([20], *Figure 8*)¹, although a different, continuous wavelet transform ramp definition has been used (discerning 2 hour, 8 hour and 15 hour ramp durations) in that study and a different observing time range (2015-2016), the installed capacity at the time was 712 MW). In the observed time range in our work, the cluster has grown to (2261 MW). Besides, more extreme ramp events have been studied in this work.

¹By this I mean Figure 8 in [20]

6.1.2 Discussion on power curves and the presence of low level jets

This section will discuss the result of the novel approach for searching low level jet activity. Recall the question formulated in Section 1.4:

How important are low level jets for power production at the Belgian offshore cluster and do they cause ramp events? Can low level jet activity be noticed in production data without wind measurements at turbine height?

Using the introduced method, no clear low level jet activity related to ramp events has been found. This could mean the method is flawed. It assumes that when a low level jet is present at turbine height, the surface wind speed is lower than would be expected for a certain load factor. The validity of this assumption has not been assessed in this study. It could also mean that more points need to be investigated. Since this part of the project was not the main objective of the study, not all the proposed candidate-points have been inspected.

6.1.3 Discussion on the classification of ramp event causing meteorological features

This section aims to address the following question formulated in Section 1.4:

What meteorological features are responsible for ramp events at the Belgian offshore wind farm cluster and in what quantities do these meteorological features occur? How can synoptic scale and mesoscale meteorological features be distinguished from each other in the power generation time series using meteorological data?

From the case studies, it seems that there is no one-to-one correspondence between meteorological feature and the direction of the ramp (up or down) it causes. For synoptic scale events, the type of ramp event seems to be largely determined by how a meteorological feature deforms the isobars. The case studies (Section 4.1) alone, included multiple examples where the passage of a cold front and a warm front both were associated with ramp-up and ramp-down events, both whilst approaching and leaving. Despite this, still some things can be learned from the classification task.

For the Belgian offshore cluster, the majority of all ramps are either directly (due to isobar deformation of a frontal passage, 39%, Table 4.5) or indirectly (due to convective storms around the front, 23%) associated with weather fronts. Even more than the 46% found in [19]. Note that this study used a different ramp definition, and that the wind farm was an onshore farm with a total installed capacity of 131.2 MW in Australia. From Figure 4.26, one can see that the mesoscale effects that are not associated with frontal passages (green and gray) are more common in the warm seasons (20% in winter, 29% in spring, 22% in summer and 18% in autumn). Besides, the fraction of ramp events associated with pre- and post-frontal convection is higher in the warm seasons than in the cold seasons. Cut-out events seem very uncommon in the warm seasons. When considering the ramp types split into three different types; `Only R100060`, `R100060 and R50015` and `Only R50015`, the association between ramp size and duration can be investigated. In Figure 4.23 and/or Table 4.3, few `Only R100060` ramp events are associated with mesoscale effects (only 10%, not including pre and post-frontal convection). In addition, the number of pre and post-frontal convection ramp driver is quite low for this ramp type (15%). For `R100060 and R50015`, these percentages are 18% and 26% respectively (Table 4.3, Figure 4.24). For fast, small short duration `Only R50015`-type ramps, mesoscale features are 40% the likely cause of the ramp event. Pre and post-frontal convection is the ramp driver 27% of the time. (Table 4.3, Figure 4.25). This suggest that there is an association between the ramp type and the ramp driving meteorological feature. Fast (especially fast, small `Only R50015`) ramp events (28 out of 70) are more often associated with mesoscale ramp drivers than slow, large (`Only R100060`) ramp events (7 out of 67). Many cut-out events have led to `R100060 and R50015`-type ramp events (5 out of 9 cut-out events). These fast long ramps are also more often associated with mesoscale effects (15 out of 84) than `Only R100060`-type events.

A previous study on ramping in the Belgian offshore cluster [27], which studied longer duration ramp events using a smaller 712 MW cluster, claims that ramp events are commonly caused by changing large scale weather patterns (probably non-cut-out low passages and passages of blocking areas). In our work,

we dealt with much faster ramp events. That could be an explanation for why our more extreme ramps are more commonly caused by frontal related meteorological features rather than changing weather patterns as defined by [27], [32]. This could also be the reason why in our work, no ramp event was associated directly with a high pressure area. Indirectly it might have caused some ramp events by affecting the isobars around fronts. However, these references only looked at mean sea level pressure to cluster weather patterns and the transitions thereof. Since frontal features are often caused by extratropical cyclones (low pressure areas), the collinearity between these features are a point of discussion. This highlights the complexity of classification task with classes that are closely related to each other.

Synoptic scale ramp drivers can be recognised by homogeneous (lasting) changes in meteorological (especially wind direction and pressure) variables across different weather stations and closely packed production curves from the individual farms, that is, they respond roughly in the same manner. This can be seen in the case studies that have been discussed in Section 4.1. Mesoscale effects are harder to explain using the dashboards since they are not visible on the synoptic weather charts. However, thunderstorm activity often shows a bumpy signature in the pressure graph. This could possibly be caused by thunderstorm updraft and downdraft regions (local depression and bump). Thunderstorms are often signified by a drop in temperature, rapid but temporary changes in wind direction and wind speed, and a difference between how individual wind farms react to the ramp event. If a thunderstorm is organised, like when they are associated with weather fronts (troughs aloft, convergence lines, squall lines), they still can bring homogeneous changes to the variables described above. In this study, post and pre-frontal convection has been treated as a synoptic scale event, since they are associated with frontal passages and visible on synoptic weather charts. The actual thunderstorms that can form in these zones (convergence lines, squall lines and troughs aloft) are mesoscale structures. It is therefore debatable that these are being classified as synoptic scale. This should be kept in mind when comparing results from this work to other studies. Note that the presence of a certain meteorological feature that are known for causing ramp events are not guaranteed to cause a ramp event. It depends on the initial and final wind speed during the passage of such a meteorological feature. If the wind speed change occurs within the constant part of the power curve (Section 1.1), no power ramp event will occur.

In Table 4.6 and Figure 4.27, the relation between ramp duration and ramp magnitude (change in production) is shown. From this, one can see that longer ramp events are associated with larger changes in production (see linear fit lines). From the distribution of the scattered points and the error bars, it can be seen that the average effect of different ramp drivers follow the trend lines quite nicely. In conclusion, both ramp-up and ramp-down events associated with mesoscale meteorological features tend to be shorter in duration and smaller in magnitude compared to ramp events linked to synoptic scale meteorological features.

6.1.4 Discussion on the ramp statistics of hypothetical wind farm clusters

This section will discuss the ramp statistics (counts, average size, average duration and mean time in between ramp events). Recall the question formulated in Section 1.4:

How does the occurrence and size of ramp events depend on wind farm cluster size?

In Chapter 5 and Section 2.5, a method for examining the effect of cluster size on the number of ramp events, the average ramp duration and ramp size has been discussed. In Figure 5.1, one can see that the total occurred ramp events decreases as the cluster grows. This is almost entirely due to the loss in sensitivity to fast ramps. From the results for the real cluster (Section 4.3, Table 4.3), one can see that of the total number of unique ramps (221), 67 were slow large ramps, 84 were fast large ramps and 70 were fast small ramps. Figure 5.1 suggests that this division could be vastly different for smaller clusters, with many ramps being shorter ramps. In contrast, slow large ramps are not significantly less common for the real cluster than for smaller clusters. The decrease in ramp occurrence seems to behave asymptotically. This might suggest that the cluster will not become much less sensitive to ramps as the cluster grows past its current size. Figure 5.3 shows the distributions of the different ramp types for increasing cluster size. Note that the total number of unique ramps according to the largest possible cluster is only ~ 175 .

Furthermore, when applying the ramp extraction functions described in Section 2.5 Code Listing 1 to the sum of all the individual farms instead of the Elia dataset, only 143 unique ramp types are extracted (not shown). This underlines the sensitivity of the number of ramps based on the ramp criteria. This confirms the suspicion discussed in Section 2.2.

In Figure 5.4, it can be seen that large clusters experience slightly longer ramps on average than small clusters. This could be caused by the fact that meteorological features are able to cause ramping for a longer time, since they can be above the cluster for a longer time. The increase in duration is the strongest for the most extreme (fast and large) ramps as the cluster size increases.

The relative average ramp size does not change as the cluster grows, as can be seen from Figure 5.8, however, this might be because different ramp types are classified as different ramp types for different clusters. In an absolute sense, larger clusters endure larger ramp events than smaller clusters (Figure 5.9). Figure 5.10 shows the product between ramp occurrence and the average ramp size. This can be used as a measure for ramp severity. It takes cluster size into account (larger clusters are responsible for a higher fraction of the total energy mix). From this figure, it can be seen that the effects on the electricity grid of large ramps (especially slow) might become more severe, whilst the effects of short small ramps might become less severe. This agrees with the findings of a technical report [26], which discusses how ramp sensitivity will be affected by the planned integration of the Princess Elisabeth Zone into the Belgian offshore fleet.

6.2 Limitations

The meteorological data used in this study is not perfect. The data is non-validated and no bias or accuracy of the data is known. Sometimes the data is unreasonably constant, or the data stream stops exactly at a high wind speed event (often for Westhinder and Wandelaar, such as on 2021-06-19, not shown). Tracking ramp events in power curves for these stations is not feasible (Section 3.4). The data from these weather stations can be used to get a sense of how the meteorological features affect the weather and wind at the surface. The wind and direction at 10 metres height are not always representative of the conditions at turbine height. Frontal boundaries are known to have a slope and vertical wind shear, but many mesoscale effects can have even larger differences between the atmospheric conditions at turbine height and on the surface. This difference in conditions at turbine height and at the surface, is exactly where the power curve method of finding low level jets is based on. In addition, the weather stations are not located at the same locations as the wind farms. This is convenient for tracking how meteorological features propagate over the area. However, it is not representative for what *exactly* happens at the time of a power ramp. Furthermore, as is documented in the research data management (RDM) (Appendix A), some data is extrapolated vertically using a log or power curve. In other words, some data is measured at a different height, and then converted to 10 m height (1.5 m for temperature, mean sea level for pressure). Some datasets discussed in the RDM, have exactly the same data, but are reported to be measured at a different sensor height. Another point to note is that wind direction data has a very large variability when the wind speed is low. Experience has learned that this variability decreases as the wind speed exceeds $5 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. One could argue that all wind direction measurements for speeds lower than $5 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ should be discarded when analysing the diurnal and seasonal pattern analysis of wind direction (Figure 3.4) and the effect on production.

The approaches taken in this project do have some limitations and points of discussion. Many mesoscale effects might go unnoticed. The difficulties in wind energy production and ramp forecasting often arise from these kind of mesoscale features. It is important to note that whilst temporal associations between synoptic features and ramp events are observed, the analysis does not establish direct causality. Some events might be classified as a synoptic or large mesoscale effect when they are actually caused by a smaller mesoscale effect occurring simultaneously, but being invisible on the dashboards. Besides, it has not been quantified how often a certain meteorological event actually causes a ramp event. The entire classification task is done by a human², and humans make mistakes. Although I tried to not introduce any bias, I cannot guarantee this did not happen. For example, can the fact that a certain ramp event takes place during

²me

the summer influence my decision to classify that event as a non-frontal thunderstorm caused by a moist sea breeze on a summer afternoon? I tried to prevent this, but this is a serious flaw in the method. The introduced bias does not even have to be introduced by the user of the dashboards, it can also be caused by the makers of the KNMI synoptic charts. The classification of ramp drivers depends heavily on these synoptic maps. During this study, no knowledge has been obtained about how these synoptic weather charts are produced. It is peculiar that sometimes errors are present in the synoptic charts. An example of an error is two consecutive synoptic charts being exactly the same. This is likely an error made by KNMI. Multiple examples of weather charts with errors in the timestamp legend have been found, such as wrong dates and inconsistent capitalisation of the first letter of months. For some events, charts from the UK Met Office and the German Wetterdienst have been used to validate the KNMI charts. However, these maps are not updated as frequently as the KNMI maps (12-hourly for Met Office, daily for Wetterdienst) and do not include as many meteorological features as the KNMI weather charts.

As can be seen in some of the case studies (vertical dashed yellow lines), the generation time series does contain some decremental bidding dates (where Elia (TSO) has requested the wind farms to reduce production below its maximum capacity). Ramps that could have occurred at these times have not been flagged. In total, 2109 out of 146784 15-minute intervals are flagged as a decremental bid (across 393 unique days). This is not much, but can be placed on moments of sudden increases of production. This can interfere with the results presented in this study, and should be studied in further detail. Besides, sometimes the summed up ENTSO-E data, the generation over all farms, does not agree with the Elia generation data. Sometimes it has an offset of 15 minutes, sometimes one has deeper dips or higher peaks than the other. Sometimes a dip is only present in one of the curves. Sometimes they are completely different and sometimes they are exactly the same. There are cases where, according to one dataset, it should be a ramp event, whilst it would not meet the ramp criteria using the other dataset. This is unexpected since the provider of the ENTSO-E generation data is Elia. In 2024, the graphs line up most of the time. Another peculiarity is that sometimes the production Elia reports is negative (7610 out of 146784 intervals, across 312 unique days), whilst the summed up ENTSO-E data is never negative.

The number of ramp events that occurred in the observing time range is quite small to do meaningful statistical hypothesis testing on. Especially when splitting the data into time-of-day blocks and seasons. This can be seen from the ramp event counts in the heat plots in Section 4.2. Besides, as can be seen in Figures 4.16 and 4.20, the number of ramp events and their associated ramp drivers can vary quite a bit year to year. Especially 2023 was a really active year in terms of ramp events, whilst in 2024, very few ramp events occurred (Table 2.3). As discussed in case study 2022-02-20, 4 out of 5 frontal cut-outs happened in a timespan of 5 days. This means that a short period of time with many ramp event occurrences can skew the results of this work dramatically. This is one of the reasons why fronts are not classified into more classes (cold front, warm front, occluded front, stationary front) and why the pre-/post-frontal convection class is not subdivided into the different types of mesoscale convective systems that can arise. The latter would be quite difficult using the dashboard in its current form, but as can be seen from the case studies, different types of weather fronts can be distinguished quite easily. In Appendix B, Figure B.4, an example of a possible error in the KNMI synoptic maps is shown. The weather data shows an exact fingerprint of a rather strong cold front (a rapid drop of 10 °C), but no cold frontal passage is visible on the synoptic charts. The difference between non-frontal convection and pre- or post-frontal convection is based on if the ramp event has occurred within 6 hours or the frontal passage. This somewhat arbitrary window is a point of discussion. It has been chosen because often after 6 hours, the isobars are restored to being parallel after a frontal passage has occurred. Some other authors use a window of 12 hours after a frontal passage to be post-frontal activity [19].

In this study, no interactions between different turbines, farms or clusters (wake effects) have been taken into account. The prevailing wind direction at the Belgian offshore cluster is a south westerly flow (Figure 3.6). Fortunately, the Belgian wind farms (as of 2025) are ordered linearly almost exactly perpendicular to this wind direction (Figure 1.3). This might result in minimal wake losses between the Belgian farms (Section 1.1). However, wake losses can still occur.

In the approach taken for examining how many ramps occur for hypothetical smaller clusters it is assumed that this is a viable method of modelling smaller clusters. However, farm to farm interactions have not been accounted for in this approach.

6.3 Improvements

This section discusses what could have been done to improve this study, if more time and data had been available.

The approach taken for Figure 3.6 could have been worked out more thoroughly. Figure 3.6 split into different seasons and time-of-day blocks might provide valuable insights in the distribution of generation and wind direction depending on time. The data could have been filtered to include only direction data for a certain small range of wind speeds. Possibly this could have allowed us to spot wake effects (Section 1.1) or mesoscale effects such as low level jets or sea breezes (Section 1.3, how upwind wind farms affect production). This could have been done by modifying Figure 3.11, but it would have cluttered the figure. It would have been interesting to see if the power trends and wind direction distribution (von Mises mixture) would have a distinct shape and location of peaks diurnally and seasonally. This is something that could be explored further in future research. This could possibly be used, under careful consideration, for generating synthetic time series, similar to [22] that uses CorWind for generating time series using reanalysis data with added fluctuations.

By adding (doppler) radar data (reflectivity and radial velocity), details on thunderstorms could possibly be made out. Currently, only cumulative lightning discharge locations are used. The cumulative discharge data can be useful as an indication where a thunderstorm was, but it would be valuable to change it to a time series of discharge data. Unfortunately, this data is not (yet) publicly available (it might be in the future URL: <https://data.gov.be/en/datasets/lightning>). Precipitation measurements could also add value to the dashboard. This could be used for locating where certain meteorological features are, similar to the case studies discussed in [16], [19]. LiDAR data could give some insights about the vertical wind speed profile and has promising effects on improving wind and power predictions ([58], preprint at the time of writing). There are LiDAR measurements taken at Borssele Alpha, available via the KNMI Data Platform (Appendix C.2) and at Westhinder, but these are not yet used in this work. This could be used to look for LLJ activity.

It could be useful to explore the integration of reanalysis data (ERA5) into the dashboard. This could give insight in how certain meteorological variables behave at the northeast side of the wind farm cluster. No weather station data for that location is available. In addition, it would be interesting to see how ERA5 models the meteorological situation during a ramp event since many studies largely depend solely on this dataset. Furthermore, the expected wake effects, and their effect on the production could be calculated using `PyWake` [59], [60].

Incorporating measurements at turbine height (SCADA data, data used for control systems of the turbine) would probably add tremendous value. This data is often proprietary, but has been used in other studies before such as in [14]. SCADA data is acquired from sensors that are nacelle (turbine enclosure) mounted. The measurements are often distorted by the turbine itself, or affected by the wake effect from other wind turbines or farms (Section 1.1). SCADA data might still add some value. because it would give information about the meteorological situation at turbine height at the farms themselves instead of around the farms like the weather stations in this study.

As has been discussed in Section 1.3.2, multiple studies on low level jets in coastal regions have found LLJ activity at latitudes above [44], [50] and below [55] the Belgian offshore cluster. Both studies agreed on that in this region, low level jet activity when a high pressure area is located above Europe, causing a easterly wind component at the southern North Sea. It could be interesting to filter the graphs and dashboards produced in this work for those specific conditions, to look for LLJ activity. Obtaining hodographs, model soundings or skew-T diagrams could also help with LLJ identification.

Although the dataset resulting from the classification task is small for statistical purposes, it was still a very tedious process to do manually. If one is specifically searching for anomalous events, like case study 2023-02-26 (unexplainable event), one could exclude all ramp events associated with meteorological features that are visible on the synoptic charts by counting coloured pixels on these images in the area of interest. This is a very simplistic method, but could help filter for unexplainable events. More advanced

methods for detecting synoptic scale events are known. For example, [61] discusses an algorithm for detecting cyclones and [62] discusses an algorithm for detecting cold fronts. It would also be valuable to include atmospheric stability and turbulence intensity measures in the dashboard. Many mesoscale effects (thunderstorms, low level jets, sea breezes via thermal lows) are caused by convection (Section 1.3) and atmospheric stability is a good indicator for convection. Calculating a measure of atmospheric stability could be useful to have an idea of what kind of mesoscale features are likely to exist at a point in time. For this, the Richardson bulk number could be used, or some other measure such as environmental lapse rate, CAPE, helicity or lifted index. Turbulence intensity, defined as

$$TI = \frac{\sigma_v}{\bar{v}}, \quad (6.1)$$

where σ_v is the standard deviation and \bar{v} the average wind speed, could also be useful since it could have a strong relation with the *gust factor* [19], [50]. The gust factor is the wind gust speed divided by the wind speed. Some exploratory analysis during this project has found that ramp events often coincide with spikes in the gust factor evolution. This could be studied in further detail. It could be interesting to see how the size of these spikes relate to the kind of meteorological ramp driver. Another interesting variable to include might be the *Charnock parameter*, calculated by:

$$\alpha = \frac{H}{T\sqrt{gd}}, \quad \text{with } H \text{ the wave height, } T \text{ the period and } g \text{ the gravitational acceleration.} \quad (6.2)$$

According to ([50], *Figure 6*³), there is a relation between LLJ occurrence and how close the Charnock parameter is to 0. Wave data could be obtained from the Thorntonbank South Buoy (Appendix A.4).

One could explore the relation between ramp events and the ageostrophic wind component. For this, the geostrophic wind could be estimated using Equation 1.10. This could possibly be used to differentiate between the effects due to large scale circulations and smaller scale circulations.

As discussed, the number of ramp events is not that high. The classification task, and the tools used to perform it, could be made using real-time data, such that an ongoing stream of new data is added to the new dataset. For example, it would be interesting how the *Spanish plume* on 2025-06-14, that caused heavy thunderstorms over North France, the southern North Sea and the east side of the UK has affected the wind farm cluster in terms of ramping.

6.4 Recommendations for further research and open questions

The power curve method used for trying to find LLJ activity discussed in Section 3.4 did not find any LLJ activity. The method could be checked against known situations when low level jets were indeed present. For example, by applying the method to a different wind farm, where LLJ are a known cause for elevated generation periods and/or ramp events.

It would be interesting to delve deeper into the unexplainable ramp events (case study 2023-02-26, case study 2023-09-28, Appendix B Table B.1), to see what really took place in these cases.

As discussed in the previous section, the vast majority of ramp events studied in this project can be associated with meteorological features using the dashboards. The events that could not be classified, are listed in Table B.1 in Appendix B. This suggest that the Belgian offshore cluster is sufficiently large that it is quite insensitive to mesoscale features that can cause ramp events. This idea can be explored in further detail by considering how a ramp event would look like if the wind farm cluster were smaller. Farm-to-farm interactions such as wake effects aside, this could already be done using the ENTSO-E data for the individual farms. In Chapter 5, using the hypothetical cluster method, more ramp events were found for smaller clusters with the same (scaled versions) of the ramp definitions. It would be interesting to see if more unexplainable mesoscale ramp drivers would be encountered when associating these ramp

³By this I mean Figure 6 in [50]

events with meteorological ramp drivers. A similar suggestion can be made for hypothetical larger clusters. If one could acquire data from the Dutch Borssele wind farm cluster (1.5 GW, spread over a larger area, the current Belgian offshore cluster has structured its turbines quite densely compared to many other wind farms [26]), it could be interesting to see what the differences in ramp events and their corresponding meteorological causes would be. Chapter 5 could be extended to include larger clusters. Furthermore, it could be interesting to explore how the spatial distribution of farms in the hypothetical cluster method affects the spatial smoothing of ramp events.

The classification task could be extended to include less extreme ramp events and ramp events with longer durations. This would lead to many more events to classify. It would be interesting to see if even larger scale effects than frontal passages will start to dominate ramp causes. It would be useful to try and make a dataset large enough to do some proper statistics on, or even use it as a training set for a machine learning model. *If* this would be accomplished, this machine learning model could use a weather forecast as the input for possibly predicting what kind of ramp events will occur based on the forecasted weather. Furthermore, it could be interesting to assess how accurate historical production forecasts during ramp events have been, and to investigate if there is a relation between prediction accuracy, real production and the type of meteorological cause.

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Code availability and supplementary material

In the shared folder linked below (via the QR-code or the link), a supplementary Jupyter Notebook will be available with all the code used for data preprocessing and producing the figures presented in this work. The shared folder also contains the newest version of this document. In addition, it contains the slides that have been used for presentations during the project.

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1wGrOLmNAOH10-nDdaAnD_d8P1UajwiGx?usp=sharing

Statement on LLM-use: No artificial intelligence has been used for text generation in this work. All of the text in the main body is human-written. However, large language models have been used for coding, and advise on the L^AT_EX structure. It has mostly been used for inspiration and examples for how to approach certain programming tasks. None of the figures are purely AI-made, but AI has often been used somewhere in the process (repetitive tasks and inspiration mainly).

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Appendix A

Research data management

In this appendix the methods of acquiring data are presented. All data used in this project is publicly available. This chapter also contains information on the datasets and their pre-processing pipelines. During the course of this project, all the data has been stored locally, since it is all publicly available. None of the data providers are affiliated in any way with this project.

A.1 Elia generation data

Generation data from the entire Belgian Offshore cluster. Data source details:

- Dataset identifier: ods031
- Datetime range: from 2021-01-01 00:00 (GMT +1) to 2025-03-09 23:45 (GMT +1)
- UTC: from 2020-12-31 23:00 to 2025-03-09 22:45:00
- Offshore data. All are managed by Elia (as of 2025-5-16)
- URL: `https://opendata.elia.be/explore/dataset/ods031/table/?sort=datetime&q.timerange.datetime=datetime:%5B2020-12-31T23:00:00Z+T0+2025-03-09T22:59:59Z%5D&refine.offshoreonshore=Offshore`
- Relevant columns:
 - Datetime: Time at which the interval starts. So data reported on 21:15 is the averaged values over the interval [21:15,21:30). Data is 15-minutely (PT15M).
 - Measured & Upscaled: The power output in megawatts (MW) averaged over the time interval. There are 26 missing values in the time series. (2021-10-31 00:00:00 to 2021-10-31 00:45:00) and (2023-06-24 01:30:00 to 2023-06-24 11:15:00)
 - Monitored capacity: Total available capacity. This is used to calculate the load factor. On 2023-06-12 the capacity went from 2254.4 MW to 2262.1 MW.
 - Incremental bid indicator: Elia has requested the wind park to reduce production below its maximum capacity. At these times, generation data is not representative of the wind speed. There are 2109 of these datetimes in the time series. These datetimes are spread over the entire time period.

With the use of the `pandas` module [63], [64] in `python`, the data is processed and formatted to the desired form using Code Listing 2.

```

1 import pandas as pd
2 path_elia = r"<PATH_ELIA>" #USER INPUT
3 path_save_df_elia = r"<PATH_ELIA_SAVE>" #USER INPUT
4 df_elia = pd.read_csv(path_elia, delimiter = ";") # Reading .csv
5 df_elia = df_elia[::-1] # Ordening from earliest to latest datetime
6 df_elia.Datetime = pd.to_datetime(df_elia.Datetime, utc=True)
7 df_elia = df_elia.set_index("Datetime")
8 df_elia = df_elia.tz_convert(None)
9 df_elia["LFcalc"] = df_elia["Measured & Upscaled"]/df_elia["Monitored capacity"]
10 df_elia["bidding"] = df_elia['Decremental bid Indicator'] != ""
11 df_elia[df_elia["bidding"]].index # Decremental bidding datetimes
12 df_elia[df_elia["Measured & Upscaled"].isna()] # Missing datetimes
13 df_elia = df_elia[['Measured & Upscaled', 'Monitored capacity', 'LFcalc', 'bidding']].copy()
14 df_elia.to_csv(f"{path_save_df_elia}//df_elia.csv")

```

Code Listing 2: Data preprocessing of Elia generation data of the entire offshore wind farm cluster.

A.2 ENTSO-E data

Generation data from individual wind farms within the Belgian Offshore cluster. This data is provided to ENTSO-E by Elia. It contains 15-minutely power generation data of Norther, Thorntonbank NE, Thorntonbank SW, Rentel, Northwind, Seastar, Nobelwind, Belwind, Northwester 2 and Mermaid. As of 2025-5-16, there is a bug on the ENTSO-E transparency platform that prevents the desired data set to be exported using simple means. The suggested route would be to use an API call instead. However, the SFTP share contains only hourly data and not the 15-minutely data. Data source details:

- Dataset identifier: Actual Generation Output per Generation Unit [16.1.A]
- Dataset range: 1 date, from 00:00 to 23:45 (UTC). Timestamps indicate the beginning of the time interval. The data at 21:15 is the average value over the [21:15,21:30) interval.
- Area: Belgium (BE)
- Production Type: Wind Offshore
- Data in megawatts (MW)
- URL: https://transparency.entsoe.eu/generation/r2/actualGenerationPerGenerationUnit/show?name=&defaultValue=false&viewType=TABLE&areaType=BZN&atch=false&dateTime.dateTime=01.01.2025+00:00|UTC|DAYTIMERANGE&dateTime.endDateTime=01.01.2025+00:00|UTC|DAYTIMERANGE&area.values=CTY|10YBE-----2!BZN|10YBE-----2&masterDataFilterName=&masterDataFilterCode=&productionType.values=B18&dateTime.timezone=UTC&dateTime.timezone_input=UTC&dv-datatable_length=50

To acquire 15 minutely generation data of the individual farms for the entire period 2021-01-01 to 2025-03-09, a web scraper was built in `python` using the `selenium` module. It is programmed to find elements on a web page using `XPath`, and can then interact with it by clicking and typing. The website has a request limit per IP-adress, To circumvent this problem, the wait times between request can dynamically adjust. When the server is fast (at night), the artificial wait time goes up to not trip the request rate limit, during the day, the artificial wait time goes down. This way the scraping of data is as fast as possible. Note that the site needs a re-login after 10 hours. After this time the buttons for getting to the 15-minutely data disappears without warning. Using 4 systems on different IP-addresses, it took over a hundred hours to get all the required data. For the full scraping script, see Code Listing 17 in Appendix C. This script produces files per day. To combine the files to a dataset similar to the processed Elia data set, Code Listing 3 is used.

```

1 import os
2 import pandas as pd
3 path_entso_csvs = r"<PATH_TO_DAILY_CSVs>" # USER INPUT
4 path_save_entso_df = r"<PATH_SAVE_ENTSODF>" # USER INPUT
5 files = os.listdir(path_entso_csvs) # Folder where all the csv files are located
6 dfs = [pd.read_csv(f"{path_entso_csvs}/{file}", delimiter = ",") for file in files]
7 df = pd.concat(dfs)
8 df=df.loc[:,["Datetime" ,"Norther", "Thorntonbank NE", "Thorntonbank SW", "Rentel", "Northwind",
9 ↪ "Seastar", "Nobelwind", "Belwind", "Northwester 2", "Mermaid"]]
10 df["Datetime"] = pd.to_datetime(df["Datetime"])
11 df_entso = df.set_index("Datetime")
12 df_entso["combined"] = df_entso.sum(axis=1)
13 df_entso.to_csv(f"{path_save_entso_df}/{df_entso.csv}")

```

Code Listing 3: Script for combining the daily scraped files to a single dataframe containing data from 2021-01-01 to 2025-03-09.

To calculate load factors, another dataset from ENTSO-E is used. This data set only contains the installed capacity of the wind farms. Data source details:

- Dataset identifier: Installed generation capacity per unit [14.1.B]
- Dataset range: 1 year
- Area: Belgium (BE)
- Production Type: Wind Offshore
- URL: https://transparency.entsoe.eu/generation/r2/installedCapacityPerProductionUnit/show?name=&defaultValue=false&viewType=TABLE&areaType=BZN&atch=false&dateTime.dateTime=01.01.2025+00:00|UTC|YEAR&area.values=CTY|10YBE-----2!BZN|10YBE-----2&productionType.values=B18&DataTables_Table_21_length=50

A.3 KNMI data

In this study, six different products/data sets are provided by the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI).

A.3.1 KNMI weather charts

Historical weather charts Europe

Every six hours (at 00:00, 06:00, 12:00 and 18:00) the KNMI generates a synoptic weather chart (URL: <https://www.knmi.nl/nederland-nu/klimatologie/daggegevens/weerkaarten>). These charts can be accessed using a `python` program via a direct link (such as https://cdn.knmi.nl/knmi/map/page/klimatologie/daggegevens/weerkaarten/analyse_2025051212.gif). It shows the locations of low and high pressure cores, isobars, cold fronts, warm fronts (surface and aloft), troughs (aloft, cold air present aloft), squall lines and convergence lines. Sometimes, the date noted on the image itself is not correct. The code for obtaining the weather maps via `python` is shown in code listing 4.

```

1 import urllib.request, requests
2
3 def download(url, output_path): # output_path is the location to save the image on the system
4     try:
5         urllib.request.urlretrieve(url, output_path)
6     except:
7         response = requests.get(url, verify=True)
8         if response.status_code == 200:
9             with open(output_path, 'wb') as f:
10                f.write(response.content)

```

Code Listing 4: Procedure for downloading images weather maps from KNMI. The function first attempts to download the images using the `urllib` module. If this does not work, it attempts to download via the `requests` module.

Historical lightning discharge map of The Netherlands

Every day all the detected discharges are accumulated in these plots (URL: <https://www.knmi.nl/nederland-nu/klimatologie/geografische-overzichten/onweer>). Not all discharges are registered, so these plots can only be used to get a general idea of thunderstorm activity. The dots that are plotted are between 0 to 4 km accurate and can either be a cloud-cloud or a cloud-ground discharge. These images can be accessed via `python` using a direct link (such as <https://cdn.knmi.nl/knmi/map/page/klimatologie/geografische-overzichten/onweer/20250512.png>). The same script as for the KNMI weathermaps can be used to download these images through `python` (Code Listing 4).

A.3.2 Weather station Vlakte van Raan/Het Zoute (validated, hourly)

At the end of the Westerschelde, near the Belgian-Dutch border, the Vlakte van de Raan weather station is located roughly in halfway of the distance from the Belgian coastline to the nearest wind farm (Norther). <https://meteostat.net/nl/station/06313?t=2025-05-02/2025-05-09> URL: <https://www.knmi.nl/nederland-nu/klimatologie/uurgegevens>

- Dataset identifier: uurgeg_313_2021-2030
- Dataset range: from 2021-01-01 01:00 (UTC) to 2025-03-31 24:00 (UTC)
- Meteostat (International) number: 06313 (KNMI: STN313)
- Location: 51.5036, 3.2419
- URL: <https://www.knmi.nl/nederland-nu/klimatologie/uurgegevens>
- Relevant columns:
 - `YYYYMMDD`: The date. To make a proper `Datetime` column, some processing is needed.
 - `HH`: The hour of the measurements. it is the end of an interval. The data is hourly. So the data at 01:00 is the average over the interval (00:00,01:00]. NOTE: this is different from the generation data discussed in section A.1 and section A.2.
 - `DD`: The average wind direction in degrees ($^{\circ}$) over the last 10 minutes of the hour (360 : North, 90 : East, 180 : South, 270 : West). This numbers are only meaningful when the wind speed is not too low (greater than $5 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$).
 - `FH`: Averaged wind speed in $0.1 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ over an hour.
 - `FX`: Strongest 3-second averaged wind gust measured during the hour.

For the wind speed and direction, no mention of measurement height is mentioned in the data documentation. It is likely measured close to the ground at 1.5 - 10 m height. The data pre-processing is shown in Code Listing 5.

```

1 import pandas as pd
2 path_raan = r"<PATH_RAAN_60>" # USER INPUT
3 path_save_df_raan = r"<PATH_SAVE_DF_RAAN>" # USER INPUT
4 # Mean wind direction (in degrees) for the 10-minute period preceding the observation time stamp
5 df_raan = pd.read_csv(path_raan, delimiter = ",", header = 28, skipinitialspace = True)
6 df_raan["Datetime"] = pd.to_datetime(df_raan['YYYYMMDD'], format='%Y%m%d') +
  ↪ pd.to_timedelta(df_raan['HH'], unit = 'h')
7 df_raan = df_raan.set_index("Datetime")
8 df_raan = df_raan.dropna(axis=1,how='all')
9 df_raan = df_raan.drop(columns = ["# STN", "YYYYMMDD", "HH", "FF", "IX"])
10 df_raan["FH"] = df_raan["FH"] * 0.1 # Windspeed in m/s
11 df_raan["FX"] = df_raan["FX"] * 0.1 # Windspeed in m/s
12 df_raan.to_csv(f"{path_save_df_raan}//df_raan.csv")

```

Code Listing 5: Data preprocessing of weather station Vlakte van de Raan.

A.3.3 Weather station Borssele Alpha (validated, hourly)

In between the wind farms of the Dutch Borssele cluster, meteorological data is obtained from the grid connection system platform Borssele Alpha. The measurements at sensor level are not at the standard heights. The reported values are estimates of the wind speed that would have been measured at 10 m height, based on the sensor height measurements.

- Dataset identifier: uurgeg_317_2021-2030
- Dataset range: from 2023-06-15 01:00 (UTC) to 2025-03-30 24:00 (UTC)
- Station number: 06317 (KNMI: STN317)
- Location: 51.7, 3.0567
- URL: <https://www.knmi.nl/nederland-nu/klimatologie/uurgegevens>
- Relevant columns:
 - `YYYYMMDD`: The date. To make a proper `Datetime` column, some processing is needed.
 - `HH`: The hour of the measurements. it is the end of an interval. The data is hourly. So the data at 01:00 is the average over the interval (00:00,01:00]. NOTE: this is different from the generation data discussed in section A.1 and section A.2.
 - `DD`: The average wind direction in degrees ($^{\circ}$) over the last 10 minutes of the hour (360 : North, 90 : East, 180 : South, 270 : West). This numbers are only meaningful when the wind speed is not too low (greater than $5 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$).
 - `FH`: Averaged wind speed in $0.1 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ over an hour.
 - `FX`: Strongest 3-second averaged wind gust measured during the hour.
 - `T`: Temperature (in $0.1 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 1.50 m at the time of observation.
 - `P`: Air pressure (in 0.1 hPa) reduced to mean sea level, at the time of observation.

The data pre-processing is shown in Code Listing 6.

```

1 import pandas as pd
2 path_borssele = r"<PATH_BORSSELE_60>" #USER INPUT
3 path_save_df_borssele = r"<PATH_SAVE_DF_BORSSELE>" #USER INPUT
4 # Mean wind direction (degrees) for the 10-minute period preceding the observation time stamp
5 df_borssele = pd.read_csv(path_borssele, delimiter = ",", header = 22, skipinitialspace = True)
6 df_borssele["Datetime"] = pd.to_datetime(df_borssele['YYYYMMDD'], format='%Y%m%d') +
↳ pd.to_timedelta(df_borssele['HH'], unit='h')
7 df_borssele = df_borssele.set_index("Datetime")
8 df_borssele = df_borssele.drop(columns = ["# STN", "YYYYMMDD", "HH", "FF", "TD", "VV", "WW",
↳ "IX", "M", "R", "S", "O", "Y", "TZ"])
9 df_borssele["FH"] = df_borssele["FH"] * 0.1 # Windspeed in m/s
10 df_borssele["FX"] = df_borssele["FX"] * 0.1 # Windspeed in m/s
11 df_borssele["T"] = df_borssele["T"] * 0.1 # Temperature in Celsius
12 df_borssele["P"] = df_borssele["P"] * 0.1 # Pressure in hPa
13 df_borssele.to_csv(f"{path_save_df_borssele}/{df_borssele.csv}")

```

Code Listing 6: Data preprocessing of weather station Borssele Alpha.

A.3.4 Weather data KNMI Data Platform (unvalidated, 10 minutely, archived)

On the KNMI Data Platform, unvalidated, but higher temporal resolution weather data is available. The relevant data sets can be accessed via the Open Data API, for which a key can be requested at <https://developer.dataplatform.knmi.nl/apis>. Some older data is archived and split per variable. The script for downloading datasets using the API key is available in Code Listing 18 in Section C. This script only downloads the data. Different datasets of on the Data platform are packaged in different ways, and therefore require a different preprocessing pipeline. The datasets for the individual variables are packaged in `.gz`-files. Code listing 7 is used for decompression, and converting them to `.csv` files. The structure of the `.gz`-files has been inspected before running the `KNMIgzprocessor` with 7zip and Notepad++ in order to pass the `widths` argument. Before running the `KNMIgzdatapicker`-function, the desired stations have been chosen from the list the `KNMIgzprocessor`-function prints.

```

1 import pandas as pd, gzip, os
2 import numpy as np
3 folder_path = r"<PATH_TO_GZ_FILES>" #USER INPUT
4 output_folder = r"<SAVE_LOCATION>" #USER INPUT
5 # skiprows is the line (-1) where the headers are. Widths is a list of column-widths
6 def KNMIgzprocessor(folder_path, skiprows, widths):
7     all_dfs = []
8     for filename in os.listdir(folder_path):
9         print(filename)
10        if filename.endswith('.gz'):
11            file_path = os.path.join(folder_path, filename)
12            df = pd.read_fwf(file_path, widths=widths, skiprows=skiprows, compression='gzip')
13            all_dfs.append(df)
14        combined_df = pd.concat(all_dfs, ignore_index=True)
15        print(np.unique(combined_df.NAME)) # For determining what stations to get
16        return combined_df
17 # q : A string, the quantity. NAMES : A list containing the desired stations
18 def KNMIgzdatapicker(combined_df, q, NAMES, output_folder):
19     for name in NAMES:
20         df_select = combined_df[combined_df["NAME"] == name]
21         df_select.to_csv(f'{output_folder}/{name.replace(" ", "_")}{q}.csv')

```

Code Listing 7: Procedure of extracting relevant data from the `.gz`-files

The different datasets acquired are listed below, along with the associated function calls to get the desired weather stations. To get a single dataframe per location containing all relevant quantities, the dataframes are combined via Code Listing 8. This script reads all the dataframes belonging to different quantities

and stations for the combination process. Some stations have multiple dataframes with overlapping data or a different timespan.

```

1 import os
2 import pandas as pd
3 folder_path = r"<OUTPUT_PATH_CODE_LISTING_6>" # USER INPUT
4 dataframes = {} # Dictionary to hold DataFrames
5 for i,filename in enumerate(os.listdir(folder_path)):
6     print(i,filename)
7     file_path = os.path.join(folder_path, filename)
8     df = pd.read_csv(file_path,low_memory=False)
9     name = os.path.splitext(filename)[0] # Remove ".csv" extension
10    dataframes[name] = df
11 # station_dataframes_same_datetimerange : list of dataframes of single quantities
12 def combiner_GZ(station_dataframes_same_datetimerange):
13     dfs=[]
14     for dataframe in station_dataframes_same_datetimerange:
15         df = dataframes[dataframe] # Calling a dataframe from the dictionary
16         df["Datetime"] = pd.to_datetime(df["# DTG"]) # Ensuring proper datetime indexing
17         df = df.set_index("Datetime")
18         dfs.append(df)
19     return dfs # Returns a list that has to be concatenated
20 # Borssele is an example of a station which has different data frames for different timespans.
21 Borssele_Alpha_locatie_SG = pd.concat(combiner_GZ(["Borssele_Alpha_locatie_SGwind",
↵ "Borssele_Alpha_locatie_SGpressure", "Borssele_Alpha_locatie_SGtemp",
↵ "Borssele_Alpha_locatie_SGbewolkingsgegevens"]), axis=1) # Horizontal concatenation
22 platform_BSA_locatie_SG = pd.concat(combiner_GZ(["platform_BSA_locatie_SGwind",
↵ "platform_BSA_locatie_SGpressure", "platform_BSA_locatie_SGtemp",
↵ "platform_BSA_lokatie_SGbewolkingsgegevens"]), axis=1) # Horizontal concatenation
23 BORSSELE_GZ=pd.concat([platform_BSA_locatie_SG,Borssele_Alpha_locatie_SG]) # Vertical
↵ concatenation
24 RAAN_GZ = pd.concat(combiner_GZ(["Vlakte_van_de_Raanwind", "Vlakte_van_de_Raan_locatie_awind"]),
↵ axis=0) # Vertical concatenation
25 CADZAND_GZ = pd.concat(combiner_GZ(["Cadzandwind", "Cadzand_locatie_awind"]), axis=0) #
↵ Vertical concatenation
26 OOSTERSCHELDE_GZ = pd.concat(combiner_GZ(["Oosterscheldewind", "Oosterschelde_locatie_awind"]),
↵ axis=0) # Vertical concatenation
27
28 def dropperGZ(df):
29     column_map = {"wdsensor10minmin": "DDN_10", "wdsensor10minavg": "DD_10", "wdsensor10minmax":
↵ "DDX_10", "wdsensor10minstd": "DD_STD_10", "wssensor10minavg": "FF_SENSOR_10",
↵ "wssensor10minstd": "FF_10M_STD_10", "wgsensor10minmax": "FX_SENSOR_10",
↵ "ws10m10minavg": "FF_10M_10", "wg10m10minmax": "FX_10M_MD_10", "T1p5m10minavg":
↵ "T_DRYB_10", "rh1p5m1minavg": "U_10", "MSLP1minavg": "P_NAP_MSL_10"}
30    df_new = pd.DataFrame({new_col: df[old_col] if old_col in df.columns else np.nan for
↵ new_col, old_col in column_map.items()})
31    return df_new
32 # The dataframes have the desired structure and data
33 df_borssele_10_GZ = dropperGZ(BORSSELE_GZ)
34 df_raan_10_GZ = dropperGZ(RAAN_GZ)
35 df_oosterschelde_10_GZ = dropperGZ(OOSTERSCHELDE_GZ)
36 df_cadzand_10_GZ = dropperGZ(CADZAND_GZ)

```

Code Listing 8: Procedure for combining data from Code Listing 7 in to desired dataframes. The exact same procedure has been done for Vlissingen.

Wind - windspeed, direction, standard deviation at a 10 minute interval

- Dataset name: windgegevens

- Dataset version: 1.0
- URL: <https://dataplatform.knmi.nl/dataset/windgegevens-1-0>
- Relevant columns:
 - `DD_10`: Wind direction in degrees at sensor height. Values are averaged over 10 minutes and correspond to the time interval preceding the timestamp. To obtain consistent naming of values across datasets and stations, this has been renamed to `wdsensor10minavg`
 - `FF_10M_10`: Wind speed in $\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ converted to 10 metres above mean sea level. The values are averaged over 10 minute intervals corresponding to the preceding interval. This has been renamed to `ws10m10minavg`.
 - `FX_10M_10_MD`: Wind gust speed in $\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ converted to 10 metres above mean sea level. The values are averaged over 10 minute intervals corresponding to the preceding interval. This has been renamed to `wg10m10minmax`.

```

1 wind = KNMIgzprocessor(r"...\\windgegevens", skiprows=22,
  ↪ widths=[21,20,48,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20])
2 KNMIgzdatapicker(wind, "wind", ['Borssele Alpha locatie SG', 'Borssele Alpha locatie SG1',
  ↪ 'Borssele Alpha locatie SG2', 'Cadzand', 'Cadzand locatie a', 'Oosterschelde',
  ↪ 'Oosterschelde locatie a', 'Vlakte van de Raan', 'Vlakte van de Raan locatie a', 'Vlissingen
  ↪ locatie A', 'Vlissingen locatie B', 'Vlissingen locatie a', 'Vlissingen locatie b',
  ↪ 'platform BSA locatie SG'],output_folder)

```

Code Listing 9: Function call for needed in Code Listing 7 for extraction of wind speed and direction data.

Weather and airpressure - atmospherical pressure and weathercodes at a 10 minute interval

- Dataset name: `weer_en_luchtdruk`
- Dataset version: 1.0
- URL: <https://dataplatform.knmi.nl/dataset/weer-en-luchtdruk-1-0>
- Relevant columns:
 - `P_NAP_MSL_10`: Mean sea level air pressure in hPa. The data has been averaged over 10 minutes and reduced to MSL. The data has been renamed to `MSLP1minavg`. NOTE: In the documentation of this dataset is stated that it is the 10 minute average. However, in a different dataset (Appendix A.3.5), that seems to exactly coincide at almost all datetimes, the values are stated as 1 minute averages. This could be due to an error at KNMI.

```

1 pressure = KNMIgzprocessor(r"...\\weer_en_luchtdruk", skiprows=20,
  ↪ widths=[21,20,48,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20])
2 KNMIgzdatapicker(pressure, "pressure", ["Borssele Alpha locatie SG", 'platform BSA locatie SG',
  ↪ 'Vlissingen locatie A', 'Vlissingen locatie a'],output_folder)

```

Code Listing 10: Function call for needed in Code Listing 7 for extraction of pressure data.

Humidity and temperature - air temperature, humidity, dewpoint, wetbulb temperature and water vapour pressure at a 10 minute interval

- Dataset name: `vochtigheid_en_temperatuur`
- Dataset version: 1.0
- URL: <https://dataplatform.knmi.nl/dataset/vochtigheid-en-temperatuur-1-0>

- Relevant columns:

- `T_DRYB_10`: Air temperature in degrees Celcius. The values are 10 minutely averaged. This has been renamed to `T1p5m10minavg`. The temperature data clearly follows the values from the validated set described in Appendix A.3.3. Hence it will be assumed that these values are measured at 1.5 meters altitude, as in Appendix A.3.3.
- `U_10`: Relative humidity (%). The values are 10 minutely averaged. This has been renamed to `rh1p5m1minavg`. NOTE: In the documentation of this dataset is stated that it is the 10 minute average. However, in a different dataset (Appendix A.3.5, that seems to exactly coincide at almost all datetimes, the values are stated as 1 minute averages. This could be due to an error at KNMI. Besides, the relative humidity data clearly follows the values from the validated set described in Appendix 6. As with the temperature, it is assumed that this is also measured at 1.5 meter altitude.

```

1 temp = KNMIgzprocessor(r"..\vochtigheid_en_temperatuur", skiprows=21,
↳ widths=[21,20,48,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20,20])
2 KNMIgzdatapicker(temp, "temp", ['Borssele Alpha locatie SG', 'Borssele Alpha locatie SG1',
↳ 'platform BSA locatie SG', 'Vlissingen', 'Vlissingen locatie B', 'Vlissingen locatie a',
↳ 'Vlissingen locatie b'],output_folder)

```

Code Listing 11: Function call for needed in Code Listing 7 for extraction of temperature an relative humidity data.

A.3.5 Meteo data - actual synoptic observations KNMI the Netherlands per 10 minutes

A more modern dataset is available on the KNMI Data Platform. with many variables. For a full description of the dataset. The reader is referred to <https://english.knmidata.nl/open-data/actuele10mindataknmistations>. Analagous to Appendix A.3.4, Code Listing 18, shown in Appendix C, can be used to interface with the open data platform. Data source details:

- Dataset name: Actuele10mindataKNMIstations
- Dataset version: 2
- URL: <https://dataplatfom.knmi.nl/dataset/actuele10mindataknmistations-2>
- Relevant columns:
 - `dd`: Wind direction ($^{\circ}$). Values are 10 minute averages at sensor height corresponding to the preceding time interval. This value is with marked discontinuities. A marked discontinuity is an abrupt shift in wind speed or direction ($5 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, 30° , minimum 2 minutes) within a 10-minute interval. After a marked discontinuity, the values before the marked discontinuity are no longer included in the 10-minute average. As per (World Meteorological Organization) WMO and International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) guidelines. For coherency between datasets, this is renamed to `wdsensor10minavg`.
 - `ff`: Wind speed ($\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$). Values are 10 min averages reduced to 10 meters altitude. This dataset is with marked discontinuities (previous point). This column is renamed to `ws10m10minavg`.
 - `gff`: Wind gust speed ($\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$), reduced to 10 meters altitude. The values are 10 minute averages with marked discontinuities (see first point). Renamed to `wg10m10minmax`.
 - `ta`: Ambient air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 1.5 meters altitude. Values are averaged over 10 minutes. Renamed to `T1p5m10minavg`.
 - `rh`: Relative humidity (%) at 1.5 meters altitude. Values are averaged over 1 minute. Renamed to `rh1p5m1minavg`. NOTE: As alluded to earlier in Appendix A.3.4, the relative humidity in

this dataset are 1 minute averages. instead of 10 minutely averages. When plotted, the curves coincide when they exist. In addition, they both agree with the values from the validated 1-hourly dataset discussed in Appendix A.3.3.

- `pp`: Air pressure (hPa) reduced to mean sea level. In the documentation of this dataset it is stated that these values are 1 minutely averages. As with the previous point (relative humidity), these values perfectly coincide with the 10 minutely averages from the other datasets, and follow the validated 1 hourly dataset in a logical way. This column is renamed to `MSLP1minavg`.

The data is packaged in 10 minute blocks. For the full 4.25 years analysed in this study, 40 GB of `.nc`-files have been downloaded from the KNMI Data Platform. In Code Listing 12, the conversion from the downloaded NetCDF-files (NetCDF is a array oriented data format for storing scientific data, commonly used by meteorologists and climatologists) to `pandas` dataframes is shown. For this study, about 200 MB is extracted from the 40 GB NetCDF files.

```

1 import xarray as xr
2 import pandas as pd
3 import os
4 from tqdm import tqdm
5
6 folder_path = r"<PATH_TO_NETCDF_FILES>" # USER INPUT
7 selected_stations = {'06317', '06313', '06312', '06308'} # USER INPUT, Station numbers
8 output_folder_path = r"<PATH_TO_SAVE>" # USER INPUT
9
10 filtered_dfs = [] # Output container
11 nc_files = [f for f in os.listdir(folder_path) if f.endswith('.nc')] # List all .nc files
12 for file in tqdm(nc_files): # Process files one-by-one to avoid memory overload
13     file_path = os.path.join(folder_path, file)
14     try:
15         ds = xr.open_dataset(file_path) # Load only what's needed
16         df = ds.to_dataframe().reset_index()
17         filtered_df = df[df['station'].isin(selected_stations)].copy() # Filter by station
18         filtered_df['source_file'] = file # For troubleshooting
19         if not filtered_df.empty: # Append if non-empty
20             filtered_dfs.append(filtered_df)
21         ds.close() # Close dataset to free memory
22     except Exception as e:
23         print(f"Error processing {file_path}: {e}")
24
25 result_df = pd.concat(filtered_dfs, ignore_index=True) # Combine all filtered data
26 result_df.to_csv(f"{output_folder_path}\filtered_station_data.csv", index=False) # Save to CSV

```

Code Listing 12: Converting NetCDF (`.nc`) files to `.csv` files for implementing the dataset into the other tools. The station numbers '06317', '06313', '06312', '06308' are Borssele alpha, Vlakte van de Raan, Oosterschelde and Cadzand respectively. Meteorological data from Vlissingen have also been acquired (06310) (not shown).

After extracting the relevant stations, the resulting dataframe has been split into separate dataframes for each station with a coherent structure and naming scheme to the other dataframes. The script to accomplish this is shown in Code Listing 13.

```

1 df=pd.read_csv(r"...\filtered_station_data.csv", low_memory=False)
2 df["time"] = pd.to_datetime(df["time"])
3 df["Datetime"] = df["time"]
4 df = df.set_index("Datetime")
5 df6317 = df[df.station == 6317] # Borssele Alpha
6 df6313 = df[df.station == 6313] # Vlakte van de Raan
7 df6308 = df[df.station == 6308] # Cadzand
8 df6310 = df[df.station == 6310] # Vlissingen
9 df6312 = df[df.station == 6312] # Oosterschelde
10
11 def dropperNC(df):
12     column_map = {"wdsensor10minmin": "dn", "wdsensor10minavg": "dd", "wdsensor10minmax": "dx",
13     ↪ "wdsensor10minstd": "dsd", "wssensor10minavg": "ffs", "wssensor10minstd": "fsd",
14     ↪ "wgsensor10minmax": "gffs", "ws10m10minavg": "ff", "wg10m10minmax": "gff",
15     ↪ "Tip5m10minavg": "ta", "rh1p5m1minavg": "rh", "MSLP1minavg": "pp"}
16     df_new = pd.DataFrame({new_col: df[old_col] for new_col, old_col in column_map.items()})
17     return df_new
18
19 df_borssele_10_NC = dropperNC(df6317)
20 df_raan_10_NC = dropperNC(df6313)
21 df_cadzand_10_NC = dropperNC(df6308)
22 df_vlissingen_10_NC = dropperNC(df6310)
23 df_oosterschelde_10_NC = dropperNC(df6312)

```

Code Listing 13: Dividing the dataframe into separate dataframes for each station while assigning coherent names to each of the columns.

Comparison and inspection of the resulting dataframes to the dataframes constructed in Section A.3.4 shows that some data is overlapping. Combining the data from both Sections gives the most complete dataset of meteorological data. For the combining process, the dataframes resulting from the archived data sets (Appendix A.3.4) are used as a base, with missing data filled in from the dataset constructed in this section. The final step is shown in Code Listing 14.

```

1 df_borssele_10 = df_borssele_10_GZ.combine_first(df_borssele_10_NC)
2 df_raan_10 = df_raan_10_GZ.combine_first(df_raan_10_NC)
3 df_cadzand_10 = df_cadzand_10_GZ.combine_first(df_cadzand_10_NC)
4 df_vlissingen_10 = df_vlissingen_10_GZ.combine_first(df_vlissingen_10_NC)
5 df_oosterschelde_10 = df_oosterschelde_10_GZ.combine_first(df_oosterschelde_10_NC)

```

Code Listing 14: Combining the dataframes from both datasets (Appendix A.3.4 and Appendix A.3.5) into singular, 10 minutely dataframes for each weather station.

Figure A.1: Data availability plot for the relevant quantities from both data sources. Every "GZ"-suffix corresponds to the `.gz`-files discussed in Appendix A.3.4. Every "NC"-suffix corresponds to the `.nc`-files discussed in Appendix A.3.5. White regions depict datetimes outside the bounds of the dataset. Black means the value for a specific datetime is missing, i.e. `NaN`.

A.4 Meetnet Vlaamse Banken data (10 minutely)

Meetnet Vlaamse Banken provides data from Belgian weather stations located in the Belgian North Sea. This data can be obtained per variable for a one year datetime range, for example, from 2021-01-01 00:00 to 2022-01-01 00:00. So consecutive time series have one overlapping data point. Data from Wandelaar and Westhinder have been used during this study. The data can be accessed via <https://meetnetvlaamsebanken.be/>. As with the KNMI data, the timestamp denotes the end of the observation period in UTC. The pre-processing of this data is shown in code listing 15.

- Wandelaar
 - Location: 51.39416, 3.04555
 - Meteorological variables used: Average wind direction ($^{\circ}$), Average wind speed at 10 meters height ($\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$), Max 3-second wind gust at 10 meters height ($\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$), Air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), Relative humidity (%) and Air pressure (hPa).
- Westhinder

- Location: 51.38833, 2.43777
- Meteorological variables used: Average wind direction (°), Average wind speed at 10 meters height ($\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$), Max 3-second wind gust at 10 meters height ($\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$), Air temperature (°C), Relative humidity (%), Air pressure (hPa) and sea water temperature (°C). All the variables are renamed for consistency with data from other weather stations.

```

1 import pandas as pd
2 path_to_save_vlaams = r"<PATH_TO_SAVE>"
3 def combiner(paths):
4     dfs = []
5     for path in paths:
6         try:
7             with open(path, 'r', encoding='utf-8') as f: # Read first line for header parsing
8                 header = f.readline().strip().split('\t')
9                 df = pd.read_csv(path, sep='\t', skiprows=1, names=header)
10                df['Datetime'] = pd.to_datetime(df[header[0]], utc=True)
11                df = df.set_index('Datetime')[[header[1]]].astype(float).tz_convert(None)
12                dfs.append(df)
13            except Exception as e:
14                print(f"Error reading {path}: {e}")
15        if dfs:
16            df_all = pd.concat(dfs).sort_index()
17            df_all = df_all[~df_all.index.duplicated(keep='last')] # Drop duplicate times
18            return df_all
19        else:
20            return pd.DataFrame() # Empty fallback
21 # Example : pathswandelaarpressure = [path_data +
22 ↪ r"... \20210101_20211231_40ef8669-246c-4c8a-a78c-bcfc8aa719ac\MP0.LDR_001_MPOLD1LDR010.txt",
23 ↪ path_data +
24 ↪ r"... \20220101_20221231_b155bdeb-51db-4737-9623-44387df4be60\MP0.LDR_001_MPOLD1LDR010.txt",
25 ↪ path_data +
26 ↪ r"... \20230101_20231231_4dd22b23-9ac8-474b-af05-38f0c50d3d36\MP0.LDR_001_MPOLD1LDR010.txt",
27 ↪ path_data +
28 ↪ r"... \20240101_20241231_219fffb36-1432-4f4a-acf1-8b934a10af66\MP0.LDR_001_MPOLD1LDR010.txt",
29 ↪ path_data +
30 ↪ r"... \20250101_20250402_cc725a11-fe69-462f-9e7a-bd21e73c11c4\MP0.LDR_001_MPOLD1LDR010.txt"]
31 df_wandelaar = pd.concat([combiner(paths) for paths in [pathswandelaarpressure,
32 ↪ pathswandelaarhum, pathswandelaarairtemp, pathswandelaarmax3swindgust, pathswandelaaravgdir,
33 ↪ pathswandelaaravgspeed]], axis=1)
34 df_westhinder = pd.concat([combiner(paths) for paths in [pathswesthinderpressure,
35 ↪ pathswesthinderhum, pathswesthinderairtemp, pathswesthindermax3swindgust,
36 ↪ pathswesthinderavgdir, pathswesthinderavgspeed, pathswesthinderseatemp]], axis=1)
37 def renamer_vlaam(df): # To get the dataframes in the same form as previous sections.
38     df_new=df.rename(columns={'Average wind direction (deg)': "wdsensor10minavg", 'Average wind
39     ↪ speed (at 10 m height) (m/s)': "ws10m10minavg", 'Max 3-seconds wind gust (at 10 m
40     ↪ height) (m/s)': "wg10m10minmax", 'Air temperature (°C)': "T1p5m10minavg", 'Relative
41     ↪ humidity (%)': "rh1p5m1minavg", 'Air pressure (hPa)': "MSLP1minavg", 'Sea water
42     ↪ temperature (°C)': 'Tsea10minavg'})
43     return df_new
44 df_wandelaar_10 = renamer_vlaam(df_wandelaar)
45 df_westhinder_10 = renamer_vlaam(df_westhinder)
46 df_wandelaar_10.to_csv(f"{path_to_save_vlaams}//df_wandelaar_10.csv")
47 df_westhinder_10.to_csv(f"{path_to_save_vlaams}//df_westhinder_10.csv")

```

Code Listing 15: Preprocessing of Meetnet Vlaamse Banken weather data.

A.5 Ramp dates

The ramp dates are extracted using a threshold definition. The datetimes were provided by a PhD student at RMI. The dataset contains sequences of ramp starting times. If a ramp last longer than 15 minutes, it would count as multiple ramp events. The list below shows only the starting times of the ramp events. Since this list of datetimes is not publicly downloadable, I have chosen to list them below, due to space constraints, only the starting datetimes are shown, the number to the right of each column indicate the number of 15 minute intervals that need to be added to get the actual end time of the ramp. For example, the first entry of ramp type `RU100060` at 2021-01-14 4:15 has five 15-minute blocks to add to get the end time of the ramp event. In the original dataset it would have contained two datetime values for this ramp (2021-01-14 04:15, 2021-01-14 04:30). Since this ramp type has a ramp criterion of 1000 MW in 60 minutes, we add 60 minutes to the last in the ramp sequence. This results in 2021-01-14 05:30, or a ramp duration of 1:15 (5 · 15 min). The function shown in Code Listing 16 is used to convert sequences of ramp events into a starting and ending datetime.

```
1 def stripper(df):
2     df = df.sort_index() # Sorting for stripping process
3     df["end"] = df.index + pd.to_timedelta(df['Dt'], unit='m') # Adding duration criterion
4     merged, result = [], []
5     current_start, current_end, current_rows = df.index[0], df["end"].iloc[0], [df.iloc[0]]
6     for i in range(1, len(df)):
7         row = df.iloc[i]
8         start = df.index[i]
9         end = row["end"]
10        if start <= current_end: # Overlap
11            current_end = max(current_end, end)
12            current_rows.append(row)
13        else:
14            merged.append((current_start, current_end, current_rows))
15            current_start, current_end, current_rows = start, end, [row]
16        merged.append((current_start, current_end, current_rows)) # Add last group
17        for start, end, rows in merged:
18            combined = rows[0].copy()
19            combined.name = start # EventD index
20            combined['end'] = end
21            result.append(combined)
22        df2=pd.DataFrame(result)
23        df2["dur"] = df2["end"] - df2.index # Calculating duration
24        df2['Mtype'] = np.nan # For classification task
25        production_df = pd.concat([eliadf['Measured & Upscaled'],entsodf[['Norther', 'Thorntonbank
↳ NE', 'Thorntonbank SW', 'Rentel', 'Northwind', 'Seastar', 'Nobelwind', 'Belwind',
↳ 'Northwester 2', 'Mermaid', 'combined']]],axis=1)
26        for col in production_df.columns[:1]: # Adding production data
27            df2[col+"_start"] = production_df.loc[df2.index, "Measured & Upscaled"].values
28            df2[col+"_end"] = production_df.loc[df2["end"], "Measured & Upscaled"].values
29            df2[col+"_change"]=df2[col+"_end"]-df2[col+"_start"] # Calculating ramp magnitude
30        return df2
31    print(np.unique(df_rampsBE.index.date).shape) #showing unique ramp days
32    RU100060BE=stripper(RU100060) # Applying for all ramptypes, BE stands for 'BeginEnd'
33    ...
34    R100060BE=pd.concat([RU100060BE,RD100060BE]).sort_index() # Applying for all ramp types
35    ...
36    df_rampsBE=pd.concat([R100060BE,R150060BE,R050015BE,R100015BE]).sort_index() # For all
37    ...
```

Code Listing 16: Preprocessing of ramp datetimes.

	RU100060	RU100060	RD100060	RD100060	RU150060	RU150060	RU050015	RU050015	RD050015	RD050015
1	2021-01-14 4:15	5	2021-01-21 17:00	6	2021-03-16 17:15	4	2021-01-14 4:45	1	2021-01-21 17:30	1
2	2021-01-28 8:45	5	2021-01-26 15:15	5	2021-04-06 13:30	4	2021-02-16 1:00	1	2021-01-26 15:45	1
3	2021-03-16 16:45	7	2021-04-06 12:15	5	2022-02-20 2:00	4	2021-03-16 17:30	1	2021-03-11 4:00	1
4	2021-04-06 13:15	6	2021-06-17 5:45	4	2022-02-20 20:00	4	2021-03-26 21:30	1	2021-06-17 6:30	1
5	2021-05-10 0:15	5	2021-06-17 6:15	5	2022-12-23 13:00	5	2021-03-26 22:30	1	2021-08-05 23:45	1
6	2021-06-17 4:45	4	2021-09-29 1:00	6	2023-01-16 11:45	6	2021-04-06 11:45	1	2021-09-29 1:30	1
7	2021-06-17 5:15	4	2021-10-01 18:00	6	2023-01-26 1:15	4	2021-04-06 13:45	1	2021-10-01 18:30	1
8	2021-06-19 22:00	4	2021-10-20 18:30	5	2023-02-26 2:30	5	2021-05-10 1:00	1	2021-10-21 2:30	1
9	2021-07-27 6:30	5	2021-12-07 22:30	4	2023-03-10 9:15	5	2021-06-17 5:30	1	2021-11-21 19:45	1
10	2021-09-29 2:45	4	2022-01-19 21:45	4			2021-07-27 7:00	1	2021-11-28 4:00	1
11	2021-10-20 20:45	5	2022-02-14 19:30	6			2021-07-27 13:15	1	2021-12-07 23:00	1
12	2021-10-20 21:30	4	2022-02-18 11:30	6			2021-08-07 18:00	1	2022-02-02 6:00	1
13	2021-10-21 3:00	5	2022-02-22 16:30	4			2021-08-07 19:45	1	2022-02-18 11:45	1
14	2021-11-27 16:30	5	2022-02-24 11:45	4	RD150060	RD150060	2021-10-20 21:30	1	2022-02-20 19:45	1
15	2021-12-04 8:30	6	2022-04-02 5:45	4	2021-06-17 6:15	4	2021-10-21 3:30	1	2022-02-24 12:30	1
16	2021-12-10 10:00	5	2022-04-02 7:30	4	2022-05-11 19:30	5	2021-11-27 17:00	2	2022-04-01 23:30	1
17	2022-01-20 0:45	5	2022-04-02 20:30	4	2022-05-19 2:00	4	2021-12-04 9:15	1	2022-04-02 5:45	1
18	2022-02-16 20:45	4	2022-05-11 19:15	7	2022-06-27 18:15	4	2022-02-18 2:15	1	2022-04-02 20:30	2
19	2022-02-18 1:45	4	2022-05-18 0:15	4	2022-11-03 15:15	5	2022-02-20 2:30	1	2022-05-11 20:00	2
20	2022-02-20 1:45	7	2022-05-19 2:00	4	2023-07-12 21:30	4	2022-02-20 20:15	2	2022-05-18 0:15	1
21	2022-02-20 19:45	6	2022-06-19 4:15	7	2023-11-02 10:30	5	2022-02-24 12:45	1	2022-06-19 5:00	1
22	2022-02-22 6:15	4	2022-06-27 18:00	6	2024-08-24 13:15	4	2022-03-16 23:15	2	2022-06-27 18:30	2
23	2022-02-24 12:45	4	2022-07-20 6:45	6			2022-04-02 5:15	1	2022-07-20 7:15	1
24	2022-03-12 20:00	5	2022-07-25 20:30	6			2022-04-02 7:15	1	2022-09-06 19:45	1
25	2022-03-16 23:00	5	2022-09-06 19:30	4			2022-04-02 9:00	1	2022-09-08 18:15	1
26	2022-03-30 20:45	6	2022-09-08 10:15	4			2022-04-02 20:15	1	2022-09-16 1:30	1
27	2022-03-31 10:30	5	2022-09-16 13:30	5	RU100015	RU100015	2022-05-18 0:00	1	2022-09-16 14:15	1
28	2022-05-17 23:15	4	2022-09-27 16:00	5	2022-09-06 19:15	1	2022-06-19 2:15	1	2022-09-27 16:45	1
29	2022-05-18 1:15	4	2022-10-07 20:45	5	2023-02-26 3:00	1	2022-07-19 22:30	1	2022-09-27 19:45	1
30	2022-05-20 15:30	5	2022-10-17 6:45	4			2022-07-19 23:15	1	2022-10-07 21:15	1
31	2022-05-23 21:45	4	2022-11-03 15:15	5			2022-07-20 5:00	1	2022-10-17 7:15	1
32	2022-06-09 14:00	5	2022-11-15 21:15	5			2022-09-06 19:15	1	2022-10-20 8:00	1
33	2022-06-25 0:00	4	2022-11-16 22:30	4			2022-09-24 7:15	1	2022-10-23 8:45	1
34	2022-07-19 23:15	4	2022-11-20 22:45	4	RD100015	RD100015	2022-10-17 6:00	1	2022-11-03 15:30	1
35	2022-07-20 4:45	4	2022-11-24 1:30	5	2022-04-02 5:45	1	2022-12-15 20:45	1	2022-11-03 16:00	1
36	2022-09-06 18:30	5	2022-12-31 1:45	4	2023-11-09 13:45	1	2022-12-23 13:15	2	2022-11-15 21:30	1
37	2022-11-14 23:45	5	2023-01-31 15:00	6			2023-01-16 12:30	1	2022-11-16 23:15	1
38	2022-12-15 20:00	4	2023-03-10 20:00	5			2023-01-26 1:45	1	2022-11-24 2:15	1
39	2022-12-23 12:45	7	2023-03-28 16:15	4			2023-01-31 18:45	1	2022-12-07 4:30	1
40	2023-01-06 17:00	4	2023-03-31 20:15	6			2023-02-05 3:15	2	2023-02-24 21:00	1
41	2023-01-16 11:45	7	2023-04-20 9:30	4			2023-02-24 21:15	1	2023-02-24 23:30	1
42	2023-01-26 1:00	7	2023-06-20 12:00	4			2023-02-26 3:00	1	2023-02-25 1:45	1
43	2023-02-05 2:45	6	2023-07-05 0:15	5			2023-03-10 9:45	2	2023-02-26 1:00	1
44	2023-02-26 2:15	7	2023-07-12 21:15	6			2023-03-14 8:15	1	2023-02-26 22:30	1
45	2023-03-10 9:15	7	2023-07-30 16:30	5			2023-03-14 9:15	1	2023-03-06 17:30	1
46	2023-03-26 11:15	5	2023-09-21 1:45	5			2023-03-27 6:15	1	2023-03-14 8:45	1
47	2023-03-30 22:30	4	2023-10-03 4:30	4			2023-03-28 12:45	1	2023-03-14 20:00	1
48	2023-04-12 10:45	5	2023-10-21 20:15	4			2023-03-30 11:45	1	2023-03-26 19:45	1
49	2023-04-21 17:15	5	2023-10-24 10:15	5			2023-04-10 21:00	1	2023-03-27 5:30	2
50	2023-04-28 5:15	5	2023-10-27 11:00	5			2023-04-12 11:30	1	2023-03-27 6:45	1
51	2023-06-18 23:45	5	2023-11-02 10:15	7			2023-04-21 17:30	1	2023-03-27 7:30	1
52	2023-06-20 11:00	4	2023-11-09 11:15	5			2023-04-22 23:15	1	2023-03-31 21:00	1
53	2023-06-25 20:30	5	2023-11-09 13:00	6			2023-04-25 4:45	1	2023-04-12 10:30	1
54	2023-07-02 13:45	5	2023-11-10 14:00	5			2023-06-19 0:00	1	2023-06-20 12:00	1
55	2023-07-04 21:30	4	2023-11-14 13:30	5			2023-07-02 14:30	1	2023-07-05 0:45	1
56	2023-07-05 1:30	4	2023-11-27 3:45	7			2023-07-05 1:45	1	2023-07-05 16:30	1
57	2023-07-05 13:45	4	2023-12-12 14:45	6			2023-07-05 14:15	1	2023-07-12 21:45	2
58	2023-07-14 23:30	6	2023-12-25 10:00	4			2023-07-15 0:15	1	2023-08-05 11:00	1
59	2023-07-26 23:45	5	2024-03-15 23:30	4			2023-07-30 18:30	1	2023-08-08 14:15	1
60	2023-07-30 18:15	5	2024-03-23 15:00	5			2023-08-05 21:45	1	2023-09-21 2:30	1
61	2023-08-05 21:00	6	2024-04-25 16:45	4			2023-08-08 13:45	1	2023-09-28 15:00	1
62	2023-08-08 16:00	5	2024-08-24 13:00	6			2023-08-08 16:15	1	2023-09-29 8:00	1
63	2023-09-13 2:30	4	2024-09-05 13:00	4			2023-10-21 22:15	1	2023-10-13 3:45	1
64	2023-09-18 5:15	5	2024-11-17 20:30	6			2023-10-24 12:00	1	2023-10-20 10:30	1
65	2023-10-13 1:15	6	2024-11-19 5:45	6			2023-10-31 16:30	1	2023-11-02 11:15	1
66	2023-10-21 22:00	5	2025-01-01 22:45	4			2023-11-02 12:45	1	2023-11-09 11:45	1
67	2023-10-24 11:15	5					2023-11-09 8:45	1	2023-11-09 13:45	1
68	2023-10-31 16:00	6					2023-11-09 12:45	1	2023-11-14 14:00	2
69	2023-11-02 12:30	5					2023-11-18 4:45	1	2023-12-12 12:00	1
70	2023-11-04 2:00	4					2023-12-12 12:30	1	2023-12-12 15:15	1
71	2023-11-05 5:45	4					2023-12-12 18:45	1	2024-02-23 15:15	1
72	2023-11-09 8:00	4					2024-02-08 14:45	1	2024-02-24 17:00	1
73	2023-11-09 12:15	5					2024-03-01 22:30	1	2024-03-01 21:15	1
74	2023-11-09 14:00	4					2024-03-27 0:15	1	2024-03-23 15:30	1
75	2023-11-10 16:00	6					2024-05-02 23:30	1	2024-04-08 20:30	1
76	2023-11-21 16:15	4					2024-06-13 21:30	1	2024-08-16 4:00	1
77	2023-12-12 18:15	5					2024-07-15 23:15	1	2024-08-24 13:15	2
78	2024-02-08 14:15	4							2024-11-17 21:00	2
79	2024-03-01 21:45	6								
80	2024-04-23 17:15	6								
81	2024-05-02 23:15	5								
82	2024-06-10 4:30	5								
83	2024-07-03 14:15	5								
84	2024-07-15 22:45	4								
85	2024-08-20 21:30	4								
86	2024-09-12 15:15	4								
87	2024-11-17 18:00	5								
88	2025-01-05 9:00	5								

	Start	Dur	Ramp type	Ramp driver		Start	Dur	Ramp type	Ramp driver
0	2021-01-14 04:15	75	overlapU	Frontal related	111	2023-02-26 01:00	15	only RD050015	Unknown (meso)
1	2021-01-21 17:00	90	overlapD	L passage	112	2023-02-26 02:15	105	overlapU	Unknown (meso)
2	2021-01-26 15:15	75	overlapD	Unknown (meso)	113	2023-02-26 22:30	15	only RD050015	Unknown (meso)
3	2021-01-28 08:45	75	only RU100060	L passage	114	2023-03-06 17:30	15	only RD050015	Frontal related
4	2021-02-16 01:00	15	only RU050015	Frontal related	115	2023-03-10 09:15	105	overlapU	L passage
5	2021-03-11 04:00	15	only RD050015	Frontal cut-out	116	2023-03-10 20:00	75	only RD100060	L passage
6	2021-03-16 16:45	105	overlapU	Frontal related	117	2023-03-14 08:15	15	only RU050015	Frontal convection
7	2021-03-26 21:30	15	only RU050015	Frontal convection	118	2023-03-14 08:45	15	only RD050015	Frontal convection
8	2021-03-26 22:30	15	only RU050015	Frontal convection	119	2023-03-14 09:15	15	only RU050015	Frontal convection
9	2021-04-06 11:45	15	only RU050015	Non-frontal convection	120	2023-03-14 20:00	15	only RD050015	Frontal related
10	2021-04-06 12:15	75	only RD100060	Non-frontal convection	121	2023-03-26 11:15	75	only RU100060	L passage
11	2021-04-06 13:15	90	overlapU	Non-frontal convection	122	2023-03-26 19:45	15	only RD050015	Frontal related
12	2021-05-10 00:15	75	overlapU	Frontal convection	123	2023-03-27 05:30	30	only RD050015	Unknown (meso)
13	2021-06-17 04:45	90	overlapU	Frontal convection	124	2023-03-27 06:15	15	only RU050015	Unknown (meso)
14	2021-06-17 05:45	105	overlapD	Frontal convection	125	2023-03-27 06:45	15	only RD050015	Unknown (meso)
15	2021-06-19 22:00	60	only RU100060	Frontal convection	126	2023-03-27 07:30	15	only RD050015	Unknown (meso)
16	2021-07-27 06:30	75	overlapU	Non-frontal convection	127	2023-03-28 12:45	15	only RU050015	Frontal related
17	2021-07-27 13:15	15	only RU050015	Non-frontal convection	128	2023-03-28 16:15	60	only RD100060	Frontal related
18	2021-08-05 23:45	15	only RD050015	Frontal related	129	2023-03-30 11:45	15	only RU050015	Unknown (meso)
19	2021-08-07 18:00	15	only RU050015	Frontal convection	130	2023-03-30 22:30	60	only RU100060	Frontal convection
20	2021-08-07 19:45	15	only RU050015	Frontal convection	131	2023-03-31 20:15	90	overlapD	L passage
21	2021-09-29 01:00	90	overlapD	Frontal convection	132	2023-04-10 21:00	15	only RU050015	Frontal convection
22	2021-09-29 02:45	60	only RU100060	Frontal convection	133	2023-04-12 10:30	15	only RD050015	Frontal convection
23	2021-10-01 18:00	90	overlapD	Frontal related	134	2023-04-12 10:45	75	overlapU	Frontal convection
24	2021-10-20 18:30	75	only RD100060	L passage	135	2023-04-20 09:30	60	only RD100060	Frontal related
25	2021-10-20 20:45	105	overlapU	L passage	136	2023-04-21 17:15	75	overlapU	Frontal convection
26	2021-10-21 02:30	15	only RD050015	L cut-out	137	2023-04-22 23:15	15	only RU050015	Frontal convection
27	2021-10-21 03:00	75	overlapU	L cut-out	138	2023-04-25 04:45	15	only RU050015	Unknown (meso)
28	2021-11-21 19:45	15	only RD050015	Non-frontal convection	139	2023-04-28 05:15	75	only RU100060	Frontal related
29	2021-11-27 16:30	75	overlapU	L passage	140	2023-06-18 23:45	75	overlapU	Frontal convection
30	2021-11-28 04:00	15	only RD050015	Frontal convection	141	2023-06-20 11:00	60	only RU100060	Frontal convection
31	2021-12-04 08:30	90	overlapU	Frontal related	142	2023-06-20 12:00	60	overlapD	Frontal convection
32	2021-12-07 22:30	60	overlapD	Frontal related	143	2023-06-25 20:30	75	only RU100060	Frontal related
33	2021-12-10 10:00	75	only RU100060	L passage	144	2023-07-02 13:45	75	overlapU	Unknown (meso)
34	2022-01-19 21:45	60	only RD100060	Frontal related	145	2023-07-04 21:30	60	only RU100060	L passage
35	2022-01-20 00:45	75	only RU100060	Unknown (meso)	146	2023-07-05 00:15	75	overlapD	L passage
36	2022-02-02 06:00	15	only RD050015	Frontal related	147	2023-07-05 01:30	60	overlapU	L passage
37	2022-02-14 19:30	90	only RD100060	Frontal related	148	2023-07-05 13:45	60	overlapU	Non-frontal convection
38	2022-02-16 20:45	60	only RU100060	Frontal cut-out	149	2023-07-05 16:30	15	only RD050015	Non-frontal convection
39	2022-02-18 01:45	60	overlapU	Frontal related	150	2023-07-12 21:15	90	overlapD	Frontal related
40	2022-02-18 11:30	90	overlapD	Frontal cut-out	151	2023-07-14 23:30	90	overlapU	Frontal related
41	2022-02-20 01:45	105	overlapU	Frontal related	152	2023-07-26 23:45	75	only RU100060	Frontal related
42	2022-02-20 19:45	15	only RD050015	Frontal cut-out	153	2023-07-30 16:30	75	only RD100060	Frontal related
43	2022-02-20 19:45	90	overlapU	Frontal related	154	2023-07-30 18:15	75	overlapU	Frontal related
44	2022-02-22 06:15	60	only RU100060	Frontal related	155	2023-08-05 11:00	15	only RD050015	Frontal convection
45	2022-02-22 16:30	60	only RD100060	Frontal related	156	2023-08-05 21:00	90	overlapU	L passage
46	2022-02-24 11:45	60	overlapD	Frontal related	157	2023-08-08 13:45	15	only RU050015	Unknown (meso)
47	2022-02-24 12:45	60	overlapU	Frontal convection	158	2023-08-08 14:15	15	only RD050015	Unknown (meso)
48	2022-03-12 20:00	75	only RU100060	Frontal related	159	2023-08-08 16:00	75	overlapU	Unknown (meso)
49	2022-03-16 23:00	75	overlapU	Frontal related	160	2023-09-13 02:30	60	only RU100060	Frontal related
50	2022-03-30 20:45	90	only RU100060	Frontal related	161	2023-09-18 05:15	75	only RU100060	Frontal related
51	2022-03-31 10:30	75	only RU100060	Frontal related	162	2023-09-21 01:45	75	overlapD	Frontal related
52	2022-04-01 23:30	15	only RD050015	Non-frontal convection	163	2023-09-28 15:00	15	only RD050015	Unknown (meso)
53	2022-04-02 05:15	15	only RU050015	Non-frontal convection	164	2023-09-29 08:00	15	only RD050015	Frontal related
54	2022-04-02 05:45	60	overlapD	Non-frontal convection	165	2023-10-03 04:30	60	only RD100060	Frontal related
55	2022-04-02 07:15	15	only RU050015	Non-frontal convection	166	2023-10-13 01:15	90	only RU100060	Frontal related
56	2022-04-02 07:30	60	only RD100060	Non-frontal convection	167	2023-10-13 03:45	15	only RU050015	Frontal related
57	2022-04-02 09:00	15	only RU050015	Non-frontal convection	168	2023-10-20 10:30	15	only RD050015	Frontal related
58	2022-04-02 20:15	15	only RU050015	Non-frontal convection	169	2023-10-21 20:15	60	only RD100060	L passage
59	2022-04-02 20:30	60	overlapD	Non-frontal convection	170	2023-10-21 22:00	75	overlapU	L passage
60	2022-05-11 19:15	105	overlapU	Frontal related	171	2023-10-24 10:15	75	only RD100060	Frontal related
61	2022-05-17 23:15	60	overlapU	Frontal convection	172	2023-10-24 11:15	75	overlapU	Frontal related
62	2022-05-18 00:15	60	overlapD	Frontal convection	173	2023-10-27 11:00	75	only RD100060	Frontal convection
63	2022-05-18 01:15	60	only RU100060	Frontal convection	174	2023-10-31 16:00	90	overlapU	Frontal convection
64	2022-05-19 02:00	60	only RD100060	Frontal convection	175	2023-11-02 10:15	105	overlapD	L cut-out
65	2022-05-20 15:30	75	only RU100060	Frontal convection	176	2023-11-02 12:30	75	overlapU	L cut-out
66	2022-05-23 21:45	60	only RU100060	Frontal convection	177	2023-11-04 02:00	60	only RU100060	Frontal related
67	2022-06-09 14:00	75	only RU100060	Unknown (meso)	178	2023-11-05 05:45	60	only RU100060	Complex (syn)
68	2022-06-19 02:15	15	only RU050015	Frontal convection	179	2023-11-09 08:00	60	overlapU	Frontal convection
69	2022-06-19 04:15	105	overlapD	Frontal convection	180	2023-11-09 11:15	75	overlapD	Frontal convection
70	2022-06-25 00:00	60	only RU100060	Frontal related	181	2023-11-09 12:15	75	overlapU	Frontal convection
71	2022-06-27 18:00	90	overlapD	Frontal related	182	2023-11-09 13:00	90	overlapD	Frontal related
72	2022-07-19 22:30	15	only RU050015	Frontal related	183	2023-11-09 14:00	60	only RU100060	Frontal related
73	2022-07-19 23:15	60	overlapU	Frontal related	184	2023-11-10 14:00	75	only RD100060	Complex (syn)
74	2022-07-20 04:45	60	overlapU	Frontal convection	185	2023-11-10 16:00	90	only RU100060	Complex (syn)
75	2022-07-20 06:45	90	overlapD	Frontal convection	186	2023-11-14 13:30	75	overlapD	Frontal related
76	2022-07-25 20:30	90	only RD100060	Frontal related	187	2023-11-18 04:45	15	only RU050015	Frontal related
77	2022-09-06 18:30	75	overlapU	Frontal related	188	2023-11-21 16:15	60	only RU100060	Frontal related
78	2022-09-06 19:30	60	overlapD	Frontal related	189	2023-11-27 03:45	105	only RD100060	L passage
79	2022-09-08 10:15	60	only RD100060	Non-frontal convection	190	2023-12-12 12:00	15	only RD050015	Frontal related
80	2022-09-08 18:15	15	only RD050015	Non-frontal convection	191	2023-12-12 12:30	15	only RU050015	Frontal related
81	2022-09-16 01:30	15	only RD050015	Non-frontal convection	192	2023-12-12 14:45	90	overlapD	Frontal convection
82	2022-09-16 13:30	75	overlapD	Non-frontal convection	193	2023-12-12 18:15	75	overlapU	Frontal convection
83	2022-09-24 07:15	15	only RU050015	L passage	194	2023-12-25 10:00	60	only RD100060	Frontal related
84	2022-09-27 16:00	75	overlapD	Non-frontal convection	195	2024-02-08 14:15	60	overlapU	Frontal related
85	2022-09-27 19:45	15	only RD050015	Non-frontal convection	196	2024-02-23 15:15	15	only RD050015	Unknown (meso)
86	2022-10-07 20:45	75	overlapD	Frontal related	197	2024-02-24 17:00	15	only RD050015	Non-frontal convection
87	2022-10-17 06:00	15	only RU050015	Frontal convection	198	2024-03-01 21:15	15	only RD050015	Frontal related
88	2022-10-17 06:45	60	overlapD	Frontal convection	199	2024-03-01 21:45	90	overlapU	Frontal related
89	2022-10-20 08:00	15	only RD050015	Frontal convection	200	2024-03-15 23:30	60	only RD100060	Frontal related
90	2022-10-23 08:45	15	only RD050015	Frontal convection	201	2024-03-23 15:00	75	overlapD	Non-frontal convection
91	2022-11-03 15:15	75	overlapD	Frontal related	202	2024-03-27 00:15	15	only RU050015	Frontal related
92	2022-11-14 23:45	75	only RU100060	Frontal related	203	2024-04-08 20:30	15	only RD050015	Frontal related
93	2022-11-15 21:15	75	overlapD	Frontal related	204	2024-04-23 17:15	90	only RU100060	Frontal related
94	2022-11-16 22:30	60	overlapD	Frontal related	205	2024-04-25 16:45	60	only RD100060	Frontal related
95	2022-11-20 22:45	60	only RD100060	Frontal convection	206	2024-05-02 23:15	75	overlapU	Frontal convection
96	2022-11-24 01:30	75	overlapD	Non-frontal convection	207	2024-06-10 04:30	75	only RU100060	L passage
97	2022-12-07 04:30	15	only RD050015	Unknown (meso)	208	2024-06-13 21:30	15	only RU050015	Unknown (meso)
98	2022-12-15 20:00	60	overlapU	Non-frontal convection	209	2024-07-03 14:15	75	only RU100060	Frontal related
99	2022-12-23 12:45	105	overlapU	Frontal related	210	2024-07-15 22:45	60	overlapU	L passage
100	2022-12-31 01:45	60	only RD100060	Frontal related	211	2024-08-16 04:00	15	only RD050015	Frontal related
101	2023-01-06 17:00	60	only RU100060	Frontal related	212	2024-08-20 21:30	60	only RU100060	Frontal related
102	2023-01-16 11:45	105	overlapU	L passage	213	2024-08-24 13:00	90	overlapD	Frontal related
103	2023-01-26 01:00	105	overlapU	Frontal related	214	2024-09-05 13:00	60	only RD100060	Frontal related
104	2023-01-31 15:00	90	only RD100060	Frontal related	215	2024-09-12 15:15	60	only RU100060	Non-frontal convection
105	2023-01-31 18:45	15	only RU050015	Frontal related	216	2024-11-17 18:00	75	only RU100060	Non-frontal convection
106	2023-02-05 02:45	90	overlapU	Frontal related	217	2024-11-17 20:30	90	overlapD	Non-frontal convection
107	2023-02-24 21:00	15	only RD050						

Appendix B

Supplementary results

This appendix contains some supplementary results, that are too specific or are take much space in the main body of this work.

R100060	R150060	R50015	R100015
26-1-2021 15:15:00 (d)		26-1-2021 15:45:00 (d)	
20-1-2022 0:45:00 (u)			
9-6-2022 14:00:00 (u)			
		7-12-2022 4:30:00 (d)	
		25-2-2023 1:45:00 (d)	
		26-2-2023 1:00:00 (d)	
26-2-2023 2:15:00 (u)	26-2-2023 2:30:00 (u)	26-2-2023 3:00:00 (u)	26-2-2023 3:00:00 (u)
		26-2-2023 22:30:00 (d)	
		27-3-2023 5:30:00 (d)	
		27-3-2023 6:15:00 (u)	
		27-3-2023 6:45:00 (d)	
		27-3-2023 7:30:00 (d)	
		30-3-2023 11:45:00 (u)	
		25-4-2023 4:45:00 (u)	
2-7-2023 13:45:00 (u)		2-7-2023 14:30:00 (u)	
		8-8-2023 13:45:00 (u)	
		8-8-2023 14:15:00 (d)	
8-8-2023 16:00:00 (u)		8-8-2023 16:15:00 (u)	
		28-9-2023 15:00:00 (d)	
		23-2-2024 15:15:00 (d)	
		13-6-2024 21:30:00 (u)	

Table B.1: Unexplainable ramp datetimes. Horizontal lines mean that it is a different day. This table also illustrates that multiple ramp events can belong to a single meteorological feature.

Borssele Alpha - wg10m10minmax - 2022-06-13 00:00:00 to 2025-03-09 22:45:00 (UTC)

Figure B.1: Borssele Alpha wind gust speed plotted against production.

Borssele Alpha - wg10m10minmax - 2022-06-13 00:00:00 to 2025-03-09 22:45:00 (UTC)

Figure B.2: Westhinder wind gust speed plotted against production.

Figure B.3: Dashboard for 2023-3-27. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Figure B.4: Dashboard for 2022-7-19. A cold convergence line behaving like a cold front. The synoptic charts and lightning discharge maps are from KNMI, KNMI is not affiliated with this work.

Appendix C

Full scripts

C.1 Scraper for ENTSO-E

```
1 import time
2 import pandas as pd
3 from selenium import webdriver
4 from selenium.webdriver.common.by import By
5 from selenium.webdriver.support.ui import WebDriverWait
6 from selenium.webdriver.support import expected_conditions as EC
7 from selenium.webdriver.chrome.service import Service
8 from selenium.webdriver.chrome.options import Options
9 from selenium.webdriver.common.keys import Keys
10 from tqdm import tqdm
11 from datetime import datetime, timedelta
12 import numpy as np
13 import os
14
15 #DATES = np.unique(df_ramps.index.date) # Can be used for specific list of dates
16 DATES = pd.date_range(start='20210101', end='20250309') # Date range to go through
17 start = 0 # To resume after error or crash
18 USERNAME = "<username>" # USER INPUT
19 PASSWORD = "<password>" # USER INPUT
20 OUTPUT_DIR = r"<output_folder>" # USER INPUT
21
22 COUNTRY_CODE = "10YBE-----2" # Belgium BZN
23 PRODUCTION_TYPE = "B18" # Offshore wind
24 delay=0 # Initial delay, will adjust to not trip request limit
25
26 farms = ["Nobelwind", "Rentel", "Norther", "Northwester 2", "Mermaid", "Seastar", "Belwind", "Northwind",
27 ↪ "Thorntonbank NE", "Thorntonbank SW"]
28
29 def safe_click(driver, xpath, timeout=600): # Safe clicking s.t it will wait for element to load, if 600
30 ↪ seconds have past, it will try to reload the page to start over from the beginning of that day.
31     global delay
32     try:
33         elem = WebDriverWait(driver, timeout).until(EC.element_to_be_clickable((By.XPATH, xpath)))
34         driver.execute_script("arguments[0].click();", elem)
35         return True
36     except Exception as e:
37         print(f"[WARN] Could not click {xpath}")
38         SCRAPER(date)
39
40 def safe_find(driver, xpath, timeout=600): # Safe clicking s.t it will wait for element to load, if 600
41 ↪ seconds have past, it will try to reload the page to start over from the beginning of that day.
42     global delay
43     try:
44         elem = WebDriverWait(driver, timeout).until(EC.presence_of_element_located((By.XPATH, xpath)))
45         return elem
46     except Exception as e:
47         print(f"[WARN] Could not find {xpath}")
48         SCRAPER(date)
49
50 def login(driver): # Automatic log-in by clicking on log-in, filling in information
51     driver.get("https://transparency.entsoe.eu/generation/r2/actualGenerationPerGenerationUnit
52 ↪ /show?name=&defaultValue=false&viewType=TABLE&areaType=BZN&atch=false
53 ↪ &dateTime.dateTime=01.01.2021+00:00|UTC|DAYTIMERANGE
54 ↪ &dateTime.endDateTime=01.01.2021+00:00|UTC|DAYTIMERANGE
55 ↪ &area.values=CTY|10YBE-----2!BZN|10YBE-----2&masterDataFilterName=
56 ↪ &masterDataFilterCode=&productionType.values=B18&dateTime.timezone=UTC
57 ↪ &dateTime.timezone_input=UTC&dv-datatable_length=50")
```

```

49 safe_click(driver, "/html/body/div[5]/div[2]/div[2]/div/span") # Accept cookies
50 safe_click(driver, "/html/body/header/div[2]/div/a[1]") # Click Login
51 email_input = safe_find(driver, "/html/body/div/div[2]/div/div/div[1]/div/form/div[2]/input")
52 if email_input:
53     email_input.send_keys(USERNAME + Keys.TAB + PASSWORD + Keys.ENTER)
54     time.sleep(3) # Allow time for login
55
56 def setup_driver(): # Setup of selenium chromedriver
57     chrome_options = Options()
58     service = Service()
59     return webdriver.Chrome(service = service, options = chrome_options)
60
61 def make_output_dir(): # Makes output directory in the case it does not exist.
62     if not os.path.exists(OUTPUT_DIR):
63         os.makedirs(OUTPUT_DIR)
64
65 # --- MAIN ---
66
67 # Setup
68 make_output_dir()
69 driver = setup_driver()
70 login(driver)
71 columns = ["Datetime", "Date", "T"] + farms # Initialising dataframe columns for storing scraped data.
72
73 def SCRAPER(date):
74     print("beginning with ", date) # for monitoring purposes.
75     global delay
76     ii = np.where(DATES == date)[0][0] # obtaining index
77     try:
78         # Build URL
79         date_str = date.strftime("%d.%m.%Y")
80         url = (
81             f"https://transparency.entsoe.eu/generation/r2/actualGenerationPerGenerationUnit/show?"
82             f"name=&defaultValue=false&viewType=TABLE"
83             f"&areaType=BZN&atch=false"
84             f"&dateTime.dateTime={date_str}+00:00|UTC|DAYTIMERANGE"
85             f"&dateTime.endDateTime={date_str}+00:00|UTC|DAYTIMERANGE"
86             f"&area.values=CTY|{COUNTRY_CODE}|BZN|{COUNTRY_CODE}"
87             f"&productionType.values={PRODUCTION_TYPE}&dateTime.timezone=UTC"
88         )
89         driver.get(url) # Opening the url
90         # Wait for table to load.
91         safe_find(driver,
92             ↪ "/html/body/div[2]/section/form/div[3]/div[2]/div[3]/div/div/table/tbody/tr[1]/td[5]/a")
93         dfdummy = pd.DataFrame(columns = columns) # Daily dummy dataframe
94         for i, farm in enumerate(farms, start = 1):
95             startfarm = time.time() # For request speed monitoring for adjusting wait time.
96             # Expand farm (first "+" button).
97             if not safe_click(driver,
98                 ↪ f"/html/body/div[2]/section/form/div[3]/div[2]/div[3]/div/div/table/tbody
99                 ↪ /tr[{i}]/td[5]/a"):
100                 continue
101             time.sleep(delay)
102             # Show 25 units button
103             safe_click(driver,
104                 ↪ f"/html/body/div[2]/section/form/div[3]/div[2]/div[3]/div/div/table/tbody/tr[{i+1}]
105                 ↪ /td/div/div/div[2]/div[1]/a[2]")
106             time.sleep(delay)
107             j = 1
108             while j < 25: # Looping through the differnt hours of the day [0,1,..,23]
109                 startj = time.time()
110                 try:
111                     # Finding average (hourly) production value (clickable) to get to 15-minutely data.
112                     valueavg = safe_find(driver,
113                         ↪ f"/html/body/div[2]/section/form/div[3]/div[2]/div[3]/div/div/table/tbody
114                         ↪ /tr[{i+1}]/td/div/div/table/tbody/tr[{j}]/td[2]/span")
115                     if valueavg:
116                         valueavg.click()

```

```

110     time.sleep(delay)
111     # Expanding the popup to see 15-minutely data
112     plus2 = safe_find(driver,
113     ↪ f"/html/body/div[6]/div[2]/div[5]/table/tbody/tr[1]/td[9]/div")
114     if plus2:
115         driver.execute_script("arguments[0].click();", plus2)
116         time.sleep(delay)
117     # Scraping the data and saving them to a daily dataframe.
118     for k in range(1, 5):
119         timeint_el = safe_find(driver,
120         ↪ f"/html/body/div[6]/div[2]/div[5]/table/tbody/tr[2]/td/table/tbody
121         ↪ /tr[{k}]/td[1]")
122         value_el = safe_find(driver,
123         ↪ f"/html/body/div[6]/div[2]/div[5]/table/tbody/tr[2]/td/table/tbody
124         ↪ /tr[{k}]/td[3]")
125         if timeint_el and value_el:
126             timeint = timeint_el.text
127             value = value_el.text.replace(",", ".")
128             dfdummy.loc[int((j-1)*4+k), "Date"] = date
129             dfdummy.loc[int((j-1)*4+k), "T"] = timeint[:5]
130             dfdummy.loc[int((j-1)*4+k), "farm"] = float(value)
131
132         safe_click(driver, "/html/body/div[5]/a") # Close popup to go to next hour
133         time.sleep(delay)
134         endj = time.time()
135
136     except Exception as e:
137         print(f" second [WARN] Problem inside farm {farm}, hour {j}:{e}")
138         SCRAPER(date)
139         j += 1
140     endfarm = time.time()
141     timediff = endfarm-startfarm
142     if timediff < 35: # Delay adjusting logic
143         delay += 0.05
144     elif (timediff > 40) & (delay > 0.05):
145         delay -= 0.05
146     print(ii, date, i, f"time for farm: {endfarm-startfarm:.2f}\t delay=", delay)
147     # Collapse farm, to go to the next farm. This seems to be necessary to maintain a coherent HTML
148     ↪ structure.
149     safe_click(driver, f"/html/body/div[2]/section/form/div[3]/div[2]/div[3]/div/div/table/tbody
150     ↪ /tr[{i}]/td[5]/a")
151     time.sleep(delay)
152
153     # Save daily
154     date_out = date.strftime("%Y%m%d")
155     # "Date" and "T" are redundant. They are used for checking if the "Datetime" column corresponds to the
156     ↪ correct data.
157     dfdummy["Datetime"] = pd.date_range(date_out, periods = 96, freq = '15Min')
158     dfdummy.to_csv(os.path.join(OUTPUT_DIR, f"ENTSO_{date_out}.csv"), index = False)
159     print(date, "is saved")
160     except Exception as e: #Repair attempt, to start over with the day when a error occurs, and waiting does
161     ↪ not fix it.
162         print(f" first [ERROR] Failed on {date}:{e}")
163         input("test")
164         SCRAPER(date)
165
166 for date in tqdm(DATES[start:]): # tqdm is used for monitoring and ETA.
167     SCRAPER(date)
168     print(date, "is done")
169
170 driver.quit() # Closing the tab and the destroying the chromedriver.
171 print("Done Scraping.") # Done

```

Code Listing 17: Scraper for ENTSO-E 15 minutely generation data of the individual farms.

C.2 KNMI Data Platform: Download a full dataset

```
1 import asyncio, logging, os, requests
2 from concurrent.futures import ThreadPoolExecutor
3 from pathlib import Path
4 from typing import Any
5 from requests import Session
6 logging.basicConfig()
7 logger = logging.getLogger(__name__)
8 logger.setLevel(os.environ.get("LOG_LEVEL", logging.INFO))
9 def download_dataset_file(session: Session, base_url: str, dataset_name: str, dataset_version: str,
10 ↪ filename: str, directory: str, overwrite: bool, ) -> tuple[bool, str]:
11     # if a file from this dataset already exists, skip downloading it.
12     file_path = Path(directory, filename).resolve()
13     if not overwrite and file_path.exists():
14         logger.info(f"Dataset file '{filename}' was already downloaded.")
15         return True, filename
16     endpoint = f"{base_url}/datasets/{dataset_name}/versions/{dataset_version}/files/{filename}/url"
17     get_file_response = session.get(endpoint)
18     # retrieve download URL for dataset file
19     if get_file_response.status_code != 200:
20         logger.warning(f"Unable to get file: {filename}")
21         logger.warning(get_file_response.content)
22         return False, filename
23     # use download URL to GET dataset file. We don't need to set the 'Authorization' header,
24     # The presigned download URL already has permissions to GET the file contents
25     download_url = get_file_response.json().get("temporaryDownloadUrl")
26     return download_file_from_temporary_download_url(download_url, directory, filename)
27 def download_file_from_temporary_download_url(download_url, directory, filename):
28     try:
29         with requests.get(download_url, stream=True) as r:
30             r.raise_for_status()
31             with open(f"{directory}/{filename}", "wb") as f:
32                 for chunk in r.iter_content(chunk_size=8192):
33                     f.write(chunk)
34     except Exception:
35         logger.exception("Unable to download file using download URL")
36         return False, filename
37     logger.info(f"Downloaded dataset file '{filename}'")
38     return True, filename
39 def list_dataset_files(session: Session, base_url: str, dataset_name: str, dataset_version: str, params:
40 ↪ dict[str, str], ) -> tuple[list[str], dict[str, Any]]:
41     logger.info(f"Retrieve dataset files with query params: {params}")
42     list_files_endpoint = f"{base_url}/datasets/{dataset_name}/versions/{dataset_version}/files"
43     list_files_response = session.get(list_files_endpoint, params=params)
44     if list_files_response.status_code != 200:
45         raise Exception("Unable to list initial dataset files")
46     try:
47         list_files_response_json = list_files_response.json()
48         dataset_files = list_files_response_json.get("files")
49         dataset_filenames = list(map(lambda x: x.get("filename"), dataset_files))
50         return dataset_filenames, list_files_response_json
51     except Exception as e:
52         logger.exception(e)
53         raise Exception(e)
54 def get_max_worker_count(filesizes):
55     size_for_threading = 10_000_000 # 10 MB
56     average = sum(filesizes) / len(filesizes)
57     # to prevent downloading multiple half files in case of a network failure with big files
58     if average > size_for_threading:
59         threads = 1
60     else:
61         threads = 10
62     return threads
63 async def main():
64     api_key = "<API_KEY>" # USER INPUT
65     dataset_name = "<DATASET_NAME>" # USER INPUT, example: "Actuele10mindataKNMIstations"
66     dataset_version = "<DATASET_VERSION>" # USER INPUT, example: "2"
```

```

65 start = 0 # USER INPUT, for resuming after crash
66 base_url = "https://api.dataplatform.knmi.nl/open-data/v1"
67 # When set to True, if a file with the same name exists the output is written over the file.
68 # To prevent unnecessary bandwidth usage, leave it set to False.
69 overwrite = False
70 download_directory = r"<PATH_TO_SAVE_ON_SYSTEM>" # USER INPUT
71 # Make sure to send the API key with every HTTP request
72 session = requests.Session()
73 session.headers.update({"Authorization": api_key})
74 # Verify that the download directory exists
75 if not Path(download_directory).is_dir() or not Path(download_directory).exists():
76     raise Exception(f"Invalid or non-existing directory: {download_directory}")
77 filenames = []
78 max_keys = 500
79 next_page_token = None
80 file_sizes = []
81 # Use the API to get a list of all dataset filenames
82 while True:
83     # Retrieve dataset files after given filename
84     dataset_filenames, response_json = list_dataset_files(session, base_url, dataset_name,
85     ↪ dataset_version, {"maxKeys": f"{max_keys}", "nextPageToken": next_page_token},)
86     file_sizes.extend(file["size"] for file in response_json.get("files"))
87     # Store filenames
88     filenames += dataset_filenames
89     # If the result is not truncated, we retrieved all filenames
90     next_page_token = response_json.get("nextPageToken")
91     if not next_page_token:
92         logger.info("Retrieved names of all dataset files")
93         break
94 logger.info(f"Number of files to download: {len(filenames)}")
95 worker_count = get_max_worker_count(file_sizes)
96 loop = asyncio.get_event_loop()
97 # Allow up to 10 separate threads to download dataset files concurrently
98 executor = ThreadPoolExecutor(max_workers=worker_count)
99 futures = []
100 # Create tasks that download the dataset files
101 for dataset_filename in filenames[start:]:
102     # Create future for dataset file
103     future = loop.run_in_executor(executor, download_dataset_file, session, base_url, dataset_name,
104     ↪ dataset_version, dataset_filename, download_directory, overwrite,)
105     futures.append(future)
106 # # Wait for all tasks to complete and gather the results
107 future_results = await asyncio.gather(*futures)
108 logger.info(f"Finished '{dataset_name}' dataset download")
109 failed_downloads = list(filter(lambda x: not x[0], future_results))
110 if len(failed_downloads) > 0:
111     logger.warning("Failed to download the following dataset files:")
112     logger.warning(list(map(lambda x: x[1], failed_downloads)))
113 if __name__ == "__main__":
114     asyncio.run(main())

```

Code Listing 18: Script for downloading an entire dataset from KNMI Data Platform. Code adapted from KNMI, URL: <https://developer.dataplatform.knmi.nl/open-data-api>.

Afterword

For those who came this far into the this document, a small reflection on the project. I want to say thank you to my supervisors and the renewable energy group at RMI. I also want to say thank you to all the people that let me use their VPN for the ENTSO-E scraping process. Thanks to my sister for letting me use her Overleaf account. Thanks to my father for spending an entire day proof reading this document for grammar mistakes, double words and missing letters. Finally, thanks to my girlfriend who had to endure my 10-12 hour working sessions. This project has been a lot of fun, and I am a bit sad that I could not have spread the project over a longer time period.

I learned a lot about meteorology, a lot more than what is presented in this document. In addition, I learned a lot about programming. I was not new to programming, but I have programmed many kind of things I have not done before. I mostly solved differential equations using python in the past. This time I used a lot of pandas. The web scraper forced me to learn about HTML webpage structures, which I did not expect to learn during this period. I also learned a lot about matplotlibs interactive features. Qt is also really cool. I wish I discovered that earlier. I would have made all my interactive tools with Qt. It is kind of a shame that this document does not reflect the amount of work put in the interactivity of the plots, for analysing meteorological situations. I am kind of a perfectionist. When I do something I want to excel. I really overestimated my knowledge on meteorology at the start of the project. I have had a fluid dynamics course and a course on the physics and chemistry of the atmosphere. The first 3 weeks were really hard because I had to learn a lot about meteorology, since my background is in physics. I sometimes have a hard time accepting things without feeling satisfied about with my understanding of a certain topic. I want to at least know where a claim comes from. This meant I had to learn a lot more on the topic than I actually used in the end. At my university, only ~ 330 hours is designated for conducting a bachelor research project. I wanted to do a lot more than can be done in this time frame. At the time of writing this afterword, I have invested 914 hours into this project. I have so many things I still would like to do, I could easily fill multiple years delving further into this topic. Actually, on June 21, I came into contact with someone who told me he maybe could help me get access to real-time data from the Dutch wind farm clusters. This would open up many possibilities for further research using the methods discussed in this work. Maybe something for a Master thesis? Who knows...

Sincerely,

William Vaughan Jones